

Effects of Audio Production Degradations on Perceptual CODECs

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Abstract

In music production, perceived audio quality is shaped by the interaction between production-induced degradations and perceptual audio coding processes. While cumulative audio CODEC artefacts and audio distortion have been extensively studied in isolation, their interactions within realistic workflows remain insufficiently understood. In parallel, the reliability of objective metrics and the role of optimisation algorithms in analysing such production contexts have not been systematically established.

This thesis addresses three fundamental research questions concerning objective metric reliability, optimisation algorithm effectiveness, and CODEC-specific degradation sensitivity through an integrated methodological framework. Rather than optimising for perceptual quality, the optimisation process, as a stress-testing mechanism, deliberately exposes the regions of the degradation space where perceptual audio CODECs fail most severely.

The research comprises three interconnected experimental studies: the Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index (HAAQI) provides the most reliable prediction under production-degradation conditions. Second, a perceptually guided machine learning (ML)-based degradator framework enabled optimisation experiments that showed that reinforcement learning outperforms Monte Carlo sampling and genetic algorithms in identifying the most perceptually degraded configurations while maintaining broader exploration of high-dimensional parameter spaces. Finally, CODEC sensitivity analysis identifies an invariant core dominated by noise-related degradations (hum and hiss), along with drums and vocals as the most affected instruments. The CODEC-specific sensitivities to audio degradations arise from fundamental differences between psychoacoustic masking and generative reconstruction mechanisms.

Together, this inverse approach enables the systematic examination of CODEC failure modes to understand the impact of audio degradation on music production. Providing empirical guidance on audio quality metrics selection, clarifying fundamental differences between conventional and neural CODECs and practical guidance for production workflows on which degradation combinations to avoid.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Background and context

In modern music production, maintaining audio quality throughout the signal chain represents a fundamental technical challenge with significant perceptual consequences. The increasing accessibility of music production, facilitated by the proliferation of bedroom studios and digital audio workstations (DAWs), has substantially broadened access to music creation in genres such as pop and rock [1]. However, this accessibility has simultaneously introduced quality vulnerabilities that were previously constrained within professional studio environments, where equipment quality, acoustic treatment, and technical expertise provided inherent safeguards against degradation.

Audio typically passes through a sequence of recording, mixing, mastering, and distribution stages. Practical issues such as unbalanced cabling, electromagnetic interference, overheating equipment, clipping caused by overloaded signal paths, or exaggerated dynamics from misused compressors and limiters can be embedded in signals. Each stage can introduce artefacts or reveal previously inaudible issues, and the resulting degradation is often cumulative, ultimately affecting the quality of the final product [2].

At the same time, audio coding has become the default component for audio delivery across streaming, broadcasting, consumer electronics, and AI audio generation. Conventional CODECs such as MP3 and AAC [3] employ transform-based representations with psychoacoustic model calculations, while emerging neural CODEC architectures [4],[5] utilise learned latent representations to achieve even higher compression ratios through fundamentally different mechanisms. When audio has already been degraded during production, the subsequent CODEC perceptual process is shaped not by a single controlled parameter (e.g., bitrate, format), but also by the CODEC's underlying design. The internal

processing mechanisms of different CODECs may interact with these degradations, resulting in CODEC-dependent amplification or perceptual transformation of artefacts.

Considering these complex nonlinear interactions between degradation and CODECs, audio coding can modify or amplify existing degradations, even at a relatively severe level, as demonstrated by a "13dB miracle" [6]. Despite the practical significance, existing research predominantly examines CODEC artefacts and audio distortion types through isolated manipulation [7], [8]. This methodological separation fails to capture the cumulative, interaction-driven nature of quality degradation in realistic production workflows. Thus, an integrated analytical framework is required to clarify how different degradation types affect perceptual quality across CODEC architectures within a production signal chain.

1.2 Research gaps

Three interrelated gaps motivate this research. First, production-induced degradations and audio CODEC artefacts are examined predominantly in isolation, with limited investigation of their interactions within music production chains. It remains unclear how degraded input signals influence CODEC processes and whether conventional and neural CODEC architectures exhibit distinct sensitivities to specific degradation types. This limits current understanding of how degradations affect perceived audio quality in practical production workflows.

Second, although objective perceptual metrics provide a practical alternative to subjective evaluation, most are developed and validated under assumptions of isolated or largely linear degradations [9]. As a result, there is insufficient evidence regarding their reliability when applied to music production signals involving interacting degradations and subsequent CODEC processing. Furthermore, the potential use of such metrics as analytical tools for probing degradation behaviour, rather than solely as end-point quality predictors, remains underexplored.

Third, research in intelligent music production has largely treated optimisation as a tool for generating perceptually acceptable or stylistically consistent final mixes [10]. Whether using population-based methods [11] or deep learning approaches [10], optimisation approaches are limited to its application in convergence to a ground truth or datasets. In contrast, optimisation algorithms aim to identify both the broader scope and the optimal solutions using perceptual quality metrics, which have received little attention. While reinforcement learning offers a principled framework for continuous control beyond population-based approaches [12]. Its use in the intelligent music production (IMP) contexts remains underexplored.

1.3 Research aim and objectives

This research aims to develop and validate a methodological framework that integrates objective perceptual evaluation with an ML-based degradation-optimisation system, enabling the systematic identification of risk factors that degrade perceptual quality in music production signal chains. The framework emulates common production degradations, including additional noise and nonlinear distortions, by manipulating them and evaluating how they interact with perceptual CODEC effects on quality.

The study is guided by the following objectives:

- To evaluate the reliability of widely used objective audio quality metrics under audio-production degradations and select a perceptually valid metric for subsequent experiments.
- To design an integrated signal-chain that combines parameterised production degradations, CODEC processing, and objective evaluation within a closed-loop optimisation architecture.
- To compare optimisation algorithms, Monte Carlo sampling (MC), Genetic Algorithms (GA), and Reinforcement Learning (RL) under identical conditions,

then quantify how algorithm choice affects identifying the most degraded case and search diversity.

- To analyse which degradation types and instrument sources most deteriorate audio quality, and to compare the sensitivity of conventional (MP3, AAC) and neural (EnCodec) CODECs under optimiser-driven degraded input.

1.4 Research Questions

Drawing on the gaps identified in the preceding sections, this thesis is guided by three core research questions (RQs), each addressing a limitation in current approaches to audio quality evaluation, optimisation algorithms, and CODEC-specific behaviour in music production contexts.

RQ1: Which listener evaluation metric provides the most reliable explanation of audio quality in music production signal chains?

While objective perceptual metrics offer a practical alternative to subjective listening tests, existing metrics are typically developed and validated under restricted conditions [9] and exhibit inconsistent behaviour across diverse applications [13], [14], [15], [16]. As a result, their reliability in production signal chains remains insufficiently established. Addressing this question requires a systematic comparison and validation test to identify which metric provides the most consistent and perceptually aligned assessment.

RQ2: Does the choice of optimisation algorithm influence degradation maximisation outcomes?

Identifying the most degraded perceptual parameters involves exploring high-dimensional spaces characterised by nonlinear interactions and complex objective targets. Different optimisation algorithms offer distinct approaches to exploration and exploitation in this inverse problem. However, their relative effectiveness in production workflows remains

underexplored, particularly with respect to the target shaped by perceptual quality metrics as objective functions. This question examines whether different optimisation algorithms behave differently when exploring perceptually defined production parameter spaces, and how this affects optimisation system design.

RQ3: Which types of degradation exert the most significant negative impact on perceived audio quality, and how does this impact differ between conventional and neural CODECs?

Production-related interactions with perceptual audio CODECs may amplify, attenuate, or fundamentally alter the perceptual salience of production errors and degradations. In particular, understanding the architectural differences between conventional and neural CODECs, which lead to distinct sensitivities to specific degradation types, remains limited. This question investigates comparative degradation effects across CODEC, with particular focus on identifying CODEC-invariant versus CODEC-specific degradation mechanisms.

1.5 Contributions

This thesis makes three main novel contributions to knowledge and practice:

Contribution 1 (C1): This thesis establishes a combined subjective and objective validation framework to identify quality metrics suitable for music production contexts. By evaluating commonly used metrics beyond their original application domains, the work provides a scalable approach for assessing production-induced degradation using perceptually motivated objective metrics.

Contribution 2 (C2): A comparative analysis of optimisation techniques, including MC, GA, and RL, is conducted to evaluate their performance in both converging to maximise and exploring diverse solutions with a non-analytic gradient metric function within an ML-based degradator system, providing a case study of reinforcement learning for perceptually guided audio optimisation.

Contribution 3 (C3): An integrated evaluation framework is developed that combines CODEC processing and objective evaluators under degradation conditions. This study systematically compares conventional and neural CODECs, offering insights into their design and sensitivity with different degradation types under practical music production contexts.

1.6 Thesis structure

The remainder of this thesis is organised as follows.

Chapter 2 reviews literature on production-related degradations, perceptual audio CODEC mechanisms, subjective and objective evaluation approaches, and intelligent music production systems and optimisation. The review motivates the thesis by highlighting how perceived audio quality in production arises from interactions between degradations and perceptual encoding across the signal chain.

Chapter 3 describes all related degradation sources and their implementation in the parameterised degradation module used throughout the thesis.

Chapter 4 addresses RQ1 by comparing candidate objective metrics using a MUSHRA-based listening study and an objective test to select a metric suitable for production signal chains.

Chapter 5 addresses RQ2 by evaluating MC, GA, and RL within the ML-based degradator framework, analysing the optimiser's performance in identifying maximum-degradation configurations and the diversity of high-degradation configurations.

Chapter 6 addresses RQ3 by applying the integrated framework to compare conventional and neural CODEC performance behaviour under production degradations, identifying CODEC-related sensitivity patterns across degradation types and instrument sources.

Chapter 7 summarises the overall findings and discusses the research question.

Chapter 8 outlines contributions, limitations and directions for future research.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

This chapter establishes the theoretical and methodological foundations for the thesis. It first defines perceptual audio quality and reviews how different stages of music production introduce signal degradation that affects perceived fidelity and interacts with perceptual audio CODECs. Different CODEC architectures are then introduced, with emphasis on the differences between their underlying mechanisms and responses to degraded input signals. The chapter then reviews approaches to audio quality evaluation, covering both subjective and objective methodology for assessing perceived quality.

In parallel, the chapter reviews the application of optimisation algorithms, outlining their role within intelligent music production (IMP) systems and their operational principles. Finally, the statistical methods employed throughout the chapters are described, providing a unified analytical framework for interpreting the experimental results.

2.1 Audio quality in music production

This section reviews the definitions of audio quality perception and examines how different stages of music production can introduce signal degradation. It outlines common degradation mechanisms, including recording noise, digital artefacts, and mixing-related manipulations and discusses their potential impact on perceived quality and interaction with perceptual audio CODECs.

2.1.1 Audio quality: objective fidelity and subjective perception

In music production, audio quality is central to conveying artistic intent and preserving the integrity of the creative work. As noted by [17], “Even for the layperson, sonic quality does matter.” Beyond musical content alone, perceived quality is shaped by recording equipment, signal processing, playback systems, and listening environments.

From a technical perspective, audio quality may be defined as “the degree of representation accuracy of an examined audio signal, disregarding the intended changes introduced by an audio system” [18]. This definition emphasises objective fidelity and highlights unintended degradations that may occur at any stage of the production chain.

Subjective listening studies further link this technical notion to perceptual experience, rather than to isolated physical signal attributes. Timbral fidelity is the subjective perceived similarity of a signal’s non-spatial spectral characteristics to an undegraded reference. In the controlled subjective experiments, altering bandwidth and spectrum degradation govern subjective rating on the Basic Audio Quality (BAQ) [19] and Overall Listening Experience (OLE) [8].

Together, these perceptual constructs link technical signal degradation to listener experience, providing a structured way to interpret how production-related changes are perceived in practice.

2.1.2 Music production workflows and cumulative degradation

Music production is conventionally structured into three stages: recording, mixing, and mastering. During recording, performances are captured using microphones in a given acoustic environment, where signal integrity is influenced by microphone placement, room acoustics, and recording equipment. The mixing stage involves applying signal processing techniques to individual tracks to shape their dynamic, spectral, and spatial characteristics. Mastering subsequently applies global adjustments to refine spectral balance and ensure consistency across playback systems.

Audio quality may be affected at each of these stages, and degradations introduced at earlier stages are often carried forward and modified by subsequent processing, ultimately influencing the quality of the final digital recording. Subsequently, CODEC processing of an already composite signal in the next stage can reinforce or mask earlier distortions, as

discussed in 2.2. As a result, degradations in music production should be understood as cumulative rather than isolated events.

Music genres, such as pop and rock, increasingly rely on home-studio production environments, enabled by the widespread availability of digital audio workstations (DAWs) and affordable recording hardware [1]. While these technologies have lowered barriers to music creation, they are frequently associated with budget signal chains, consumer-grade interfaces, and acoustically untreated rooms [2]. Beyond environmental and hardware-related impacts, creative signal processing tools used during mixing, such as equalisation (EQ) and dynamic range compression (DRC), further modify the temporal and spectral structure of audio signals. Although these processes are applied intentionally for artistic control, they may also introduce secondary distortions or alter signal statistics, thereby influencing subsequent processing stages. Consequently, modern music production environments provide a context in which multiple degradations can accumulate and interact, motivating a systematic examination of their combined effects on perceived audio quality.

2.1.3 Degradation in music production: focus, limitation, and scope

Degradations in music production arise from multiple sources and manifest across spectral, temporal, and perceptual dimensions. Broadly, they can be categorised as follows:

- Content-unrelated noise, including broadband noise and pitch-related interference caused by unstable hardware, cabling, or grounding issues [20]. Such additive noise is predominantly level-dependent [21], with signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) closely linked to perceptual quality degradation.
- Content-related inharmonic degradation, such as clipping resulting from improper gain staging [22] or nonlinear processing [23]. Clipping is consistently identified as a highly disruptive degradation and is often perceived as particularly annoying [24], [25].

- Temporal transient degradations, such as glitches/dropouts, occurring in digital audio workstations (DAWs)[26]. These artefacts can cause severe perceptual degradation during communication and streaming contexts [27].
- Processing-induced degradations introduced by creative mixing tools such as EQ, DRC and reverberation. While these processes are intentionally applied, they may introduce distortion and interact unfavourably with perceptual audio CODECs when altering temporal or spectral signal characteristics.

While additive noise and CODEC-stage artefacts have a direct and observable impact on perceived quality, degradations introduced by creative signal processing are more complex, as their perceptual consequences depend on parameterisation, signal context, and interactions with subsequent processing stages.

Among common production processes, DRC has been shown to correlate with perceived audio quality in popular music [28]. It represents a controlled but potentially non-transparent process, whose perceptual impact depends on its parameter settings and the signal being processed. Beyond loudness reduction, DRC introduces temporal envelope distortion and nonlinear interactions. [29] shows improper compression of multiple signals can generate intermodulation distortion, leading to spectral congestion, reduced instrument separation, and increased masking. Although moderate compression may be subjectively preferred due to loudness enhancement, [30] claims perceptual quality consistently degrades once loudness is controlled, with losses in dynamic contrast, spatial depth, and naturalness becoming dominant. Compared to clipping, DRC is generally perceived as a lower-severity degradation; however, its effects become salient through temporal degradations such as transient suppression and pumping, which are strongly influenced by attack and release behaviour and by interactions with other nonlinear processes [24].

While the signal chain adopted in this study reflects typical music production practice, the space of possible degradations is considerably broader. Additional factors include room

acoustics [31], equipment colouration [32], and dithering strategies [33]. Degradation has also been studied beyond perceptual quality assessment, [34] notably in evaluating the robustness of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) systems for tasks such as transcription [35] and source restoration [36]. Furthermore, audio CODEC artefacts [7] are often treated as independent sources of degradation in simulation studies. This work, instead, argues that CODEC processing can modify or amplify existing degradations, altering their perceptual behaviour rather than acting as an isolated factor; a perspective explored further in Section 2.2.5.

2.1.4 Summary

This section reviewed audio quality in music production from objective and perceptual perspectives, showing how degradations emerge and accumulate across recording, mixing, and mastering. It highlighted common sources of degradation: noise, nonlinear artefacts, temporal disruptions, and processing-induced distortions. And emphasised that their perceptual impact is cumulative, context-dependent, and shaped by signal interactions.

The existing literature largely treats each production-induced degradation and perceptual audio CODEC artefact as an isolated contributor to perceptual audio quality, with limited consideration of their interaction within realistic music production chains. In particular, there is a lack of systematic investigation into how integrity parameterised mixing processes and controlled degradations are reshaped by perceptual audio CODECs.

2.2 Audio CODECs

This section introduces conventional and neural CODECs, outlining their underlying mechanisms, architectural differences, and discuss their potential responses to degraded input signals.

2.2.1 Introduction to CODECs

Perceptual audio CODECs aim to reduce data size while preserving perceived quality by using efficient encoding and decoding strategies. Traditionally, psychoacoustic models reduce data size in a digital signal processing pipeline by discarding information less critical to human hearing while preserving a perceptually close approximation of the original audio. Examples of such CODECs include MP3 [37], AAC [38], Opus [39], etc.

The standard for the CODEC is commonly traced back to the MPEG-1 [40], MPEG-2 [41], and MPEG-2 Advanced Audio CODEC [42]. These standards specified the bitstream and the decoding, but did not restrict the encoding and the psychoacoustic model involved. On the one hand, they ensure that the various decoders produce the same decompressed output, or “bitstream compliant,” from a given input. On the other hand, they provide the flexibility to optimise both encoder quality and efficiency.

More recently, deep learning has transformed audio coding by enabling data-driven approaches that achieve lower bitrates while maintaining perceptual quality comparable to that of conventional CODECs. Unlike conventional processes, as demonstrated by SoundStream [4] and EnCodec [5], these methods do not rely on explicit psychoacoustic models or filterbank-based frequency analysis. However, the trade-offs for these neural CODECs are obvious. They are based on machine learning models, typically incur higher computational and storage costs, and are often constrained to specific frameworks and datasets.

2.2.2 Psychoacoustic mechanism in conventional CODEC

The CODEC compresses audio data by removing perceptually irrelevant parts of the signal; it exploits the human auditory system's inability to hear quantisation noise under conditions of auditory masking [43].

2.2.2.1 Auditory modelling foundations

The cochlea exhibits frequency-dependent resolution, with hair cells more densely packed at lower frequencies. This non-linear distribution is modelled computationally using critical

band filterbanks based on either the Bark scale [43] or the Equivalent Rectangular Bandwidth (ERB) scale [44]. This frequency dependency can be expressed in terms of critical band widths, which range from less than 100 Hz at the lowest audible frequencies to more than 4 kHz at the highest.

2.2.2.2 Masking effects

Simultaneous (Spectral) Masking occurs when a strong signal masks weaker signals in adjacent frequency bands, making them imperceptible. The slope of the masking curve is less steep on the high-frequency side; that is, higher frequencies are more easily masked. The masking threshold spreads across the critical band surrounding the masker, with asymmetric slopes that vary with sound pressure level.

Temporal Masking extends masking effects in time. Post-masking persists 50–200 milliseconds after the masker ceases, while pre-masking occurs approximately 2–5 milliseconds before the onset of the masker [43]. The duration of pre-masking is significantly shorter than that of post-masking. Both spectral and temporal masking are being exploited in CODEC algorithms.

2.2.2.3 Tonality estimation and masking asymmetry

Tonality estimation distinguishes tonal (sinusoidal, harmonic) components from noise-like signal regions. Generally, tone-like sounds are less effective maskers than noise-like sounds. The latter often exhibit stronger, more irregular, and more rapid envelope fluctuations. This asymmetry offset between masker and masking threshold varies with the tonality of the components.

Model 1 (Layers I/II) explicitly classifies spectral components as tonal or noise-like by identifying spectral peaks and applies separate masking functions to each class. Instead, Model 2 (Layer III/AAC) computes a continuous tonality index based on spectral predictability using linear extrapolation across successive frames. More predictable components are treated as more tonal and masked more conservatively during quantisation [45].

2.2.2.4 Psychoacoustic model output and bit allocation

The psychoacoustic model produces a Signal-to-Mask Ratio (SMR) for each subband, defined as the level difference between the signal energy and the masking threshold. This value guides quantisation by determining the allowable Signal-to-Quantisation-Noise relationship, expressed as the Mask-to-Noise Ratio (MNR). A negative MNR indicates that quantisation noise exceeds the masking threshold in that subband, resulting in audible artefacts. Consequently, bit allocation is iteratively adjusted across subbands to maintain non-negative MNRs while minimising the overall bitrate [37].

2.2.3 Mechanism in neural CODEC

Where conventional CODECs rely on a priori psychoacoustic models, neural CODECs learn perceptual relevance directly from data through end-to-end training. This paradigm shift has enabled previously unattainable compression efficiency. EnCodec demonstrates the subjective quality scores at 3 kbps exceeding those of advanced conventional CODECs at 12 kbps for mixed speech and music content [5].

2.2.3.1 CODEC architecture

The foundational architecture, established by SoundStream [27], introduces an autoencoder-based neural audio CODEC with a learned latent representation optimised using multiple loss functions. In this process, a convolutional encoder maps audio waveforms to latent representations; subsequently, a Residual Vector Quantizer (RVQ) discretises these representations into trainable codebook entries; and a convolutional decoder reconstructs audio from quantised codes. The model is trained end-to-end, learning both representation and synthesis. Unlike conventional decoders that invert the encoding transform, neural decoders are generative; they synthesise audio that is perceptually similar rather than sample-accurate to the original.

2.2.3.2 Quantisation process

RVQ addresses the challenge of representing high-dimensional latent vectors with finite codebooks. Rather than using a single large codebook, RVQ employs a cascade of smaller

codebooks: the first quantises the latent vector coarsely, and subsequent stages progressively refine the residual error. This hierarchical approach enables scalable bitrates, and adding or removing quantiser stages adjusts compression without retraining. However, in practice, optimal performance across different bitrates often requires retraining or fine-tuning to enable joint optimisation with the model.

2.2.3.3 Training objectives

Neural CODECs combine reconstruction and adversarial losses. Reconstruction losses encourage accurate signal matching, while adversarial losses encourage the reconstructed audio to sound perceptually realistic. Reconstruction losses operate in both the time domain (L1 waveform distance) and the frequency domain (multi-scale STFT or mel-spectrogram distance). Mel-spectrogram losses are adopted because their perceptually motivated frequency scaling emphasises spectral envelope similarity, whereas STFT-based losses preserve the sensitivity to fine-grained spectral structure and phase-related artefacts [46]. Meanwhile, adversarial losses derived from discriminator networks are multi-period waveform and multi-scale STFT discriminators that distinguish real from reconstructed audio. This adversarial training implicitly learns perceptual weighting, when the discriminator penalises artefacts that deviate from the training distribution and promotes perceptually relevant features.

2.2.4 CODEC comparison: deterministic decoding and generative reconstruction

The terms encoder and decoder are used in both paradigms; they denote fundamentally different operations.

In conventional CODECs, encoding applies a mathematically defined, invertible transform, typically the modified discrete cosine transform (MDCT), which maps time-domain samples to frequency-domain coefficients with a known inverse. Given the same quantised coefficients and decoder implementation, reconstruction is fully deterministic and

sample-identical across systems. Information loss arises solely from quantisation, whose magnitude and spectral distribution are explicitly controlled by the psychoacoustic model.

Neural CODECs follow a compression–generation paradigm rather than an analysis–synthesis paradigm [47]. The encoder learns a nonlinear mapping from waveforms to a latent representation via deep networks, with no closed-form inverse. The decoder is not required to invert this mapping; instead, it is trained as a generator with a combination of reconstruction and adversarial objectives. While time-domain and spectral losses encourage fidelity, adversarial training prioritises perceptual plausibility by penalising deviations from the statistics of the training data rather than enforcing sample-accurate reconstruction.

This architectural distinction has direct implications for how CODECs respond to degradation. Conventional CODECs implement a deterministic analysis-synthesis pipeline: reconstruction is additive and predictable; the decoder reproduces the encoded signal plus quantisation noise shaped by the psychoacoustic model, which is preserved at the output. Whereas neural CODECs optimise a composite objective that combines waveform, spectral, and adversarial losses, thereby governing reconstruction by learned generative priors rather than explicit inversion. When degradation drives latent codes outside the training distribution, this can lead to non-deterministic behaviour, reflecting a fundamental shift from distortion-preserving reconstruction to data-driven generation.

2.2.5 CODEC behaviour with degradation

Common degradation in music production includes noise, nonlinear distortion, and modification by temporal and spectral processing. Despite the widespread use of CODECs in storage, streaming, and broadcasting, relatively limited work has examined how production-induced degradations affect CODEC performance and perceived quality. The degradations do not merely add artefacts at the output; they alter internal CODEC mechanisms, including masking estimation, bit allocation, and the regeneration quality.

2.2.5.1 Conventional CODEC behaviour

Conventional CODECs employ signal-dependent psychoacoustic analysis, meaning that changes in input signal characteristics directly affect coding decisions. Quantisation noise is shaped by bitrate and signal complexity: slowly varying tonal signals are efficiently encoded, whereas noise-contaminated or spectrally complex signals require substantially higher bitrates to avoid distortion, resulting in degradation such as high-frequency loss or clipping [48].

Temporal coding further assumes quasi-stationarity within short analysis frames; degradations that introduce abrupt temporal variations (e.g., clipping or glitches) increase transient density, thereby forcing frequent short-window switching. This reduces frequency resolution, increases side information, and can exacerbate temporal artefacts such as pre-echo [49], [50], [51].

Degradations also affect masking threshold estimation. Psychoacoustic models rely on tonality measures, as tonal signals generally act as weaker maskers than noise-like signals [52]. Extra noise or DRC processing that introduces randomness, amplitude modulation, or spectral and envelope distortion reduces spectral predictability [53]. This can lead to misclassification of signal components and suboptimal bit allocation, increasing the audibility of coding artefacts [54].

2.2.5.2 Neural CODEC behaviour

Neural CODECs employ encoder–decoder architectures trained end-to-end to generate perceptually plausible audio from compressed representations, without relying on psychoacoustic models. Prior work has shown that, while neural CODECs achieve high quality on clean speech and music, their performance can degrade noticeably under mild degradations such as background noise, indicating limited robustness in realistic conditions [55]. Because reconstruction is guided by learned data distributions, degradations that are absent in the training set may be treated as out-of-distribution inputs, leading the decoder to prioritise perceptual plausibility over signal fidelity [56]. This behaviour can result in

characteristic artefacts, including tonal distortions or periodicity errors, and produce outputs that are perceptually distinguishable from the originals [46].

There are audio processing scenarios that are not strictly generative audio modelling tasks, such as music restoration or speech denoising, in which neural networks are trained on paired degraded–clean signals. Despite their discriminative training formulation, these tasks operate in a regime where generation is unavoidable, as irreversibly lost signal components must be synthesised from learned priors rather than directly recovered. MSR Bench indicate strong content-dependent behaviour: transient-dominated sources such as drums and percussion exhibit catastrophic failure under objective quality metrics, vocals show poor reconstruction quality, while bass and other harmonic-rich instruments achieve mid-range or higher restoration performance [57]. In contrast, learning-based approaches in speech denoising and historical restoration, particularly neural declipping methods, consistently report substantial improvements over conventional signal-processing techniques [58], [59], [60].

Taken together, these findings suggest that the generative bias of neural models interacts strongly with signal structure and training distribution, with their inherent generative bias providing perceptual advantages for suitable audio structures while exposing limitations for transient-dominated signals and unseen degradation conditions.

2.2.6 Summary

This section reviewed the mechanisms of conventional and neural audio CODECs, with a particular focus on how input signal characteristics influence their behaviour. Conventional CODECs rely on explicit psychoacoustic models, where degradations directly affect masking estimation, bit allocation, window switching, and the placement of quantisation noise in a deterministic and predictable manner. Neural CODECs, by contrast, employ learned representations and generative decoders, in which reconstruction is guided by the training data distribution rather than by explicit perceptual rules.

A key gap in the existing literature is that CODEC evaluation is predominantly conducted using clean or idealised signals, providing limited insight into how production-related degradations interact with the CODEC process mechanism. This limitation is critical because degradations may influence CODEC behaviour by altering signal characteristics that guide internal processing, rather than simply adding audible artefacts at the output. While prior studies indicate that both conventional and neural CODECs are sensitive to degraded inputs, it remains unclear which architectures are more severely affected by specific types of degradation.

2.3 Perceptual audio quality evaluation

This section outlines the principal approaches to audio quality evaluation, covering both subjective listening tests and objective computational metrics. Subjective methods provide direct assessments of perceived quality through controlled human evaluation, while objective methods estimate perceptual quality automatically using psychoacoustic models. Together, these approaches underpin the analysis of how degradations and signal processing affect perceived audio fidelity.

2.3.1 Subjective evaluation methods

It is possible to measure the physical properties of an audio signal; however, these measurements do not always reflect how the human auditory system perceives and evaluates sound. According to [61], the most direct approach to assessing audio quality is through subjective listening tests, where participants rate the perceived quality of audio samples under controlled conditions. To ensure reproducibility, factors such as room acoustics, playback equipment, program material, listener training, and experiment instructions must be carefully standardised.

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) provides key methodologies for subjective assessment. Recommendation BS.1284 [62] outlines general procedures for

designing listening tests, including stimulus selection, panel requirements, and evaluation methods. Two primary test strategies are widely used: BS.1116 [63], known as ABX, designed for detecting minor impairments, employs a five-grade impairment scale from -4 (very annoying) to 0 (inaudible); and BS.1534 [64], known as Multiple Stimuli with Hidden Reference and Anchor (MUSHRA), targets quality evaluation through a multi-stimulus comparison using hidden references and anchors. In multi-condition scenarios, continuous quality scales from 0 to 100 are commonly applied. Variants of MUSHRA are also used in related studies [65], where references or anchors may be omitted.

Despite its reliability in capturing human perception, the subjective listening test faces notable challenges. Results often show low reproducibility due to listener bias [66] and variations in test environments [67]. Additionally, these tests are time-consuming and costly, requiring large participant groups to achieve statistically robust conclusions.

2.3.2 Objective evaluation metrics

The aim of objective perceptual measurements is to predict BAQ using computational models that incorporate psychoacoustic principles. These measurements were developed to overcome the limitations of time-consuming, costly subjective listening tests by providing an automated means to predict how humans perceive audio quality. The effectiveness of these objective quality measurements is typically validated by comparing them with scores obtained from subjective listening tests.

Objective perceptual measurements are designed to mimic the human auditory system's response to sound. They analyse various aspects of the audio signal: loudness, temporal-spectral masking, and distortion levels, to provide a quantitative audio quality assessment. Psychoacoustic models play a crucial role in these metrics. Non-perceptual metrics, such as Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), can be used to measure audio quality. However, these metrics are insufficient for applications in music production quality, which involve complex psychoacoustic interaction manipulation. For example, the

"13dB miracle" demonstrated by [6] showed that noise can be made inaudible by shaping it below the masking threshold, even at an overall signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of approximately 13 dB.

2.3.2.1 Objective metrics by application domain

Objective perceptual measurement models are typically designed and trained on audio material and distortion types relevant to their specific application domain. According to [9] these domains can be categorised into four fields: speech enhancement (e.g., Perceptual Evaluation of Speech Quality, PESQ), audio coding (e.g., Perceptual Evaluation of Audio Quality, PEAQ), source separation (e.g., Perceptual Evaluation Methods for Audio Source Separation, PEASS), and hearing aids (e.g., Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index, HAAQI). Table 1 observes that metrics are used far beyond their original fields, adapting to various distortions.

Table 1 Summary of Objective Audio Quality Metrics: Cross-Domain Applications and Limitations

Metric	Original Domain	Cross-Domain Applications	Limitation
PEAQ (ITU-R BS.1387)	Audio Coding	Audio broadcasting [68],[69] Non-linear distortion [13], [70], Hearing aid [71], Neural Generative Audio [72]	Poor on low-bitrate [68]; Poor on Non-linear distortion [13], [71];
PEMO-Q	General Quality	Source separation [9], CODEC evaluation [14]	Reduced sensitivity once quality is high [14]; struggles with complex distortions [9];
ViSQOL/ ViSQOLAudio	Speech/ Audio Quality	CODEC evaluation [14], Neural Generative Audio [15], [72], Source separation [9]	Reduced robustness to non- standard distortions [9]; Sensitivity depending on degradation type [15];
HAAQI/ HASQI	Hearing aids Quality Prediction	Source separation [9], Non-linear distortion [24]	Monaural only [71]; Computational heavy [16];

2.3.2.2 Metric-specific perceptual modelling approaches

Understanding why objective metrics behave differently under various degradation conditions requires examining their underlying psychoacoustic models. Each metric employs

distinct approaches to modelling human auditory perception, resulting in characteristic strengths and limitations when applied to specific distortion types.

PEAQ, standardised as ITU-R BS.1387 [73] models auditory perception using a psychoacoustic framework comprising a peripheral ear model followed by a cognitive-mapping stage. Perceptual differences between reference and processed signals are analysed via time–frequency excitation patterns derived from either an FFT-based ear model in the Basic version or a higher-resolution filterbank-based ear model in the Advanced version [74]. From these internal representations, a set of Model Output Variables (MOVs) that are related to noise-to-mask ratio, loudness disturbance, and modulation changes is extracted and mapped to a predicted subjective quality score using a trained neural network. As PEAQ was developed and validated primarily using perceptual audio CODEC artefacts dominated by linear and quantisation-related small distortions. And its correlation with subjective quality ratings deteriorates for nonlinear processing, such as low-bitrate [69] or DRC [13], [71], limiting its reliability in music-production scenarios where such effects are prevalent.

PEMO-Q [13] modelling by explicitly incorporating modulation-domain processing to capture perceptually relevant temporal envelope fluctuations. Signals are analysed using a gammatone filterbank, followed by adaptation loops that simulate neural adaptation and a modulation filterbank that represents envelope dynamics. Audio quality is estimated by cross-correlating the resulting internal representations of reference and degraded signals, yielding a Perceptual Similarity Measure (PSM). This correlation-based formulation provides strong sensitivity to temporal disruptions and modulation degradation, but exhibits ceiling effects at high quality levels when subtle differences become difficult to resolve[14]. Moreover, the emphasis on envelope modulation can reduce sensitivity to fine spectral detail, limiting the detection of complex degradation [9].

ViSQOL [75] estimates audio quality by comparing spectro-temporal “neurogram” representations derived from gammatone filterbank analysis and mapping the resulting Neurogram Similarity Index Measure (NSIM) scores to perceptual results using a supervised

regression model trained on subjective listening data. Unlike explicitly model-driven metrics such as PEMO, ViSQOL’s perceptual behaviour is strongly shaped by its training corpus, which predominantly contains CODEC-related distortions. The use of fixed-length spectro-temporal patches provides robustness to overall level differences but reduces sensitivity to brief events. Consequently, ViSQOL performs well for CODEC impairments but shows reduced reliability for nonlinear distortions that fall outside its training distribution [15].

HAAQI [71] was originally designed for hearing-aid evaluation, simulating both normal and impaired hearing through gammatone filtering, envelope extraction, compression, and temporal fine-structure analysis. Audio quality is assessed using a combination of cepstral correlation and basilar-membrane vibration similarity between reference and degraded signals. This dual sensitivity to envelope and fine-structure information enables HAAQI to capture both temporal disruptions and subtle spectral or timbral changes, making it well-suited to nonlinear degradations in music production. Its main limitations are monaural-only operation and relatively high computational cost [16], but its perceptual accuracy often yields stronger alignment with subjective judgments across diverse degradation types [9].

2.3.2.3 Implications for music production evaluation

From the existing review, there is no direct link between the current application and the music production degradation process. Objective audio quality metrics are harder to apply in music production because of polyphonic content, intentional nonlinear processing, and aesthetic decisions that differ from those used in common quality evaluation applications.

2.3.3 Summary

This section reviewed methods for evaluating perceptual audio quality, including subjective listening and objective perceptual metrics. Subjective methods, particularly MUSHRA, provide the most reliable assessment across diverse and interacting degradation types, making them well-suited to complex audio conditions. However, it restricts their use in large-scale or iterative studies due to the plausibility. Objective metrics offer a practical alternative by modelling aspects of human auditory perception, but their reliability depends

on the underlying perceptual models and the training data. It varies depending on the type of degradation, signal content, and underlying psychoacoustic assumptions.

A key gap concerns the choice and use of objective audio quality metrics. Most existing metrics are developed and validated for specific domains, such as CODEC artefacts or source separation, and typically assume isolated or largely linear degradations. In contrast, music production involves polyphonic, multitrack signals and intentional nonlinear processing, where multiple degradations interact perceptually. Moreover, these metrics generally produce a single monotonic quality score, offering limited insight into how individual, parameterised production processes influence perceived quality. As a result, it remains unclear how existing metrics respond to production-related degradations, whether their behaviour is consistent across different CODEC architectures, and to what extent they can be used as analytical tools rather than only as end-point quality predictors.

2.4 Optimisation methods in Intelligent Music Production (IMP)

The field of intelligent music production (IMP) has developed a range of computational approaches to support audio engineers in mixing and mastering tasks. [76] identifies three key design considerations: levels of control, knowledge representation, and audio manipulation. Although the present study does not focus on conventional applications, such as advancing autonomous mixing systems or improving mix quality, these conceptual dimensions remain relevant. This work employs optimisation algorithms to systematically synthesise maximum degradation conditions for CODEC evaluation. The associated optimisation algorithms are therefore used to maximise perceptual degradation rather than to converge towards an optimal mix. Nevertheless, the optimisation methodologies developed within the IMP literature remain directly applicable to this inverted objective. This section reviews optimisation techniques developed within the IMP literature, focusing on their original context and algorithmic characteristics.

From a general perspective, pre-existing optimisation approaches in IMP systems can be broadly categorised into two classes: supervised, data-driven learning methods, including regression-based models and deep neural networks trained to predict mixing behaviour from data; and population-based optimisation methods that directly explore DSP parameter spaces through iterative evaluation.

2.4.1 Supervised learning-based optimisation and deep learning methods

Data-driven supervised learning models commonly formulate mixing as a supervised learning problem, in which models are trained either to map audio features to mixing parameters (“parameter estimation”) or to directly generate processed audio outputs (“direct transformation”) [10]. Direct transformation approaches are particularly useful in scenarios where explicit modelling of complex DSP chains or fixed processing orders is undesirable, such as [77]. Parameter estimation approaches, by contrast, are applicable when a parametric loss can be defined between predicted effect settings and reference mix configurations. Examples include learning embeddings sensitive to DRC parameters [78], or extracting DSP parameters using differentiable neural network frameworks [79], [80]. However, these approaches rely heavily on well-curated datasets that pair raw audio with corresponding professional mixes. As a result, most proposed neural models target to minimise prediction error rather than to explore the broader parameter space, limiting their applicability in inverse optimisation settings without reliable ground-truth labels.

2.4.2 Population-based optimisation methods

In contrast, conventional population-based optimisers, such as genetic algorithms (GA) and particle swarm optimisation (PSO), remain viable candidates for parametric optimisation in IMP. Population-based methods are heuristic optimisation methods inspired by natural selection and are well-suited to exploring complex, non-convex parameter spaces without requiring gradient information. Their flexibility and simplicity have led to widespread adoption in research on high-dimensional parameter spaces.

For example, [11] combines timbral classification with GA-based optimisation to adjust track gains towards a target mix. [81] frames masking reduction in mixing as an optimisation problem, using PSO guided by masking metrics to adjust parameters in order to improve clarity. Additionally, GAs have been applied to intelligent equalisation systems, demonstrating improved perceptual outcomes compared to manual adjustment, especially for listeners with hearing impairment [82]. Interactive genetic algorithms (IGAs) have also incorporated user feedback for personalised mixing in object-based audio and broadcasting contexts [83]. In this work, the Monte Carlo model was used as a random-sampling baseline.

Despite these advantages, GAs are susceptible to premature convergence and may become trapped in local optima under high selection pressure, particularly when population diversity is not explicitly maintained [84].

2.4.3 Learning-based optimisation

To address these limitations, recent work has explored learning-based optimisation paradigms, including Learning-to-Optimise (L2O), which leverages deep learning to accelerate optimisation [85]. Reinforcement learning (RL) has also been investigated for sequentially adapting audio processing parameters. For instance, [86] employs a value-based RL framework to adjust compression parameters based on predicted user preference rewards. However, the application of RL to IMP remains relatively unexplored, largely due to challenges in framework design, environment parameterisation, and action-space control. While RL has been successfully applied to discrete audio transformation tasks such as DJ-style mixing [87], there remains a methodological gap in extending these approaches to high-dimensional, continuous DSP parameter spaces. Recent advances suggest that RL can outperform population-based optimisers in high-dimensional inverse problems by learning adaptive exploration–exploitation strategies [12], highlighting its potential relevance to ML-based degradator optimisation.

2.4.4 Summary

Despite substantial progress in IMP systems and optimisation algorithms, existing research predominantly formulates optimisation as a target-seeking process, aiming to produce perceptually acceptable mixes or match reference outcomes. While supervised learning models can effectively replicate mixing decisions when large, paired datasets are available, their reliance on ground-truth mixes and predictive loss functions limits their suitability for inverse optimisation or exploratory analysis.

Although population-based methods can operate in both optimisation directions, they often prematurely converge toward suboptimal solutions, obscuring the diversity of perceptual failure modes. Moreover, reinforcement learning approaches have rarely been evaluated in continuous, multi-parameter IMP contexts where no reference mix or explicit ground-truth optimum exists.

2.5 Statistical methods

This section outlines the statistical methods used across the experimental chapters to analyse subjective listening data, explore multivariate structure, and interpret model-based feature importance. The framework combines repeated-measures inference for MUSHRA evaluations, exploratory dimensionality reduction via PCA (Principal Component Analysis), and supervised tree-based modelling with permutation importance and SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) analysis.

2.5.1 Statistical analysis of MUSHRA

The MUSHRA methodology [64] employs a within-subjects design wherein each participant evaluates all experimental conditions, enabling the use of repeated-measures analysis of variance (rmANOVA). This approach partitions variance attributable to experimental factors from individual listener differences, increasing statistical power relative

to independent-samples designs [88]. Due to its robustness and statistical power, rmANOVA is well-suited for MUSHRA data. The

2.5.1.1 Normality assumptions

The general linear model underlying rmANOVA does not assume raw responses are normally distributed; rather, it assumes the residuals are normally distributed. Thus, normality tests must be applied to the model residuals for each experimental condition (each combination of audio system and audio material), not to raw ratings. Recommended tests include Royston's multivariate Shapiro-Wilk [89] and Mardia's [90] tests for multivariate skewness and kurtosis.

Simulation studies demonstrate rmANOVA is robust to moderate normality violations with balanced designs [91], [92]. BS.1534 acknowledges that "due to the lack of rules concerning acceptable deviation from normality," parametric analysis remains feasible when violations are not severe. When skewness exceeds 1.0, non-parametric alternatives such as the Friedman test [93] may be considered:

$$\chi_F^2 = \frac{12}{nk(k+1)} \sum_{j=1}^k R_j^2 - 3n(k+1) \quad \text{Equation 2.1}$$

where n is the number of subjects, k is the number of conditions, and R_j is the sum of ranks for condition j . The statistic follows a chi-squared distribution with $k-1$ degrees of freedom.

2.5.1.2 Sphericity and correction procedures

An assumption of rmANOVA is sphericity, which requires that the variances of the pairwise differences across all conditions be equal [94]. When sphericity is violated, the F-statistic becomes inflated, increasing Type I error rates. Corrections adjust the degrees of freedom by a factor ε , where $\varepsilon = 1$ indicates perfect sphericity. The adjusted F-test uses:

$$df_{\text{adjusted}} = \varepsilon \times df_{\text{original}} \quad \text{Equation 2.2}$$

BS.1534 also recommends the Huynh-Feldt correction [95] because the Greenhouse-Geisser [96] tends to produce overly conservative tests. The selection guideline recommends the univariate approach with Huynh-Feldt correction when $\tilde{\varepsilon} > 0.85$ and $N < K + 30$, where N is the number of assessors and K is the maximum number of within-subjects factor levels.

2.5.1.3 Effect size

Effect size quantifies the practical magnitude beyond statistical significance. Generalised eta-squared (η^2) is recommended for rmANOVA as it accounts for repeated-measures correlation structure and enables comparison across studies [97], [98]. Conventional benchmarks classify effects as small ($\eta^2 < 0.06$), medium ($0.06 \leq \eta^2 < 0.14$), and large ($\eta^2 \geq 0.14$) [99].

2.5.2 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA is a multivariate technique that transforms correlated variables into a set of linearly uncorrelated components, ordered by the amount of variance explained [100]. Given a data matrix X with n observations and p variables, PCA seeks orthogonal directions (principal components) that maximise variance. The k th principal component is a linear combination of the original variables:

$$PC_k = \sum_{j=1}^p w_{jk} X_j \quad \text{Equation 2.3}$$

where w_{jk} are the loadings (eigenvector elements) for variable j on component k . The ordering of components reflects decreasing variance contribution. Prior to analysis, variables should be standardised ($mean = 0$, $SD = 1$) when measured on different scales to prevent variables with larger variances from dominating the solution.

Prior to conducting PCA, two prerequisites should be verified: sufficient inter-variable correlation to justify dimensionality reduction, and adequate sampling to ensure stable and interpretable component estimates. These conditions are commonly assessed using inspection of the correlation matrix, Bartlett's test [101] of sphericity, and the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin

(KMO) measure [102] of sampling adequacy. KMO ranges from 0 to 1 ; values above 0.6 are considered acceptable, above 0.7 good, and above 0.8 excellent [103].

Selecting the number of components to retain is a critical step in PCA. The Kaiser criterion retains components with eigenvalues greater than one, reflecting the requirement that a component explain at least as much variance as a single standardised variable [104]; however, it is known to overestimate dimensionality, particularly in high-dimensional datasets [105]. The scree test [106] identifies the point at which the eigenvalue spectrum flattens, though its interpretation can be subjective when no clear inflexion is present. Parallel analysis [107] offers a more objective approach by retaining only components whose eigenvalues exceed those of randomly generated data of the same dimensionality, typically using a 95th-percentile threshold. Simulation studies consistently show that parallel analysis outperforms both the Kaiser criterion and the scree test [105], [108].

Component loadings represent the correlation between standardised variables and principal components. In correlation circle plots, variables are vectors from the origin: vector length indicates communality (the proportion of variance shared), while the angle between vectors reflects their correlation. Variables aligned with a component axis load strongly on that component, whereas orthogonal vectors are uncorrelated. Supplementary variables, such as outcome measures, may be projected post hoc without affecting the component structure, allowing relationships between exploratory dimensions and external criteria to be visualised [109]. When correlations between principal components and outcome variables are weak, it indicates a failure to build an outcome-relevant structure. Motivating the use of supervised or nonlinear methods.

2.5.3 Tree-Based model and SHAP value

2.5.3.1 Tree-Based ensemble methods and XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting)

Decision trees recursively partition the feature space using loss-minimising binary splits, but typically suffer from high variance and limited predictive accuracy when used in isolation [110]. Ensemble methods mitigate these limitations by combining multiple trees.

Random Forests are ensemble models that improve prediction by averaging many decision trees. They use bootstrap aggregating (bagging), training trees on resampled datasets with random feature selection at each split to reduce variance [111]. Gradient boosting instead builds trees sequentially, with each tree fitted to the negative gradient of a specified loss function, enabling progressive error correction [112].

This study employs XGBoost as the primary modelling framework. XGBoost extends gradient boosting by incorporating explicit regularisation to control model complexity [113].

The objective function is

$$Obj = \sum_i L(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_k \Omega(f_k), \quad \Omega(f) = \gamma T + \frac{1}{2} \lambda \|w\|^2 \quad \text{Equation 2.4}$$

where T is the number of leaves, w is the vector of leaf weights, and the regularisation terms γ and λ are parameters controlling tree complexity and weight magnitude, respectively. By exploiting second-order loss information and efficient computational optimisations, XGBoost can capture nonlinear relationships and higher-order feature interactions without distributional assumptions. These properties make it particularly suitable for modelling contexts where complex parameter interactions may arise [114], [115], [116].

2.5.3.2 Feature Importance Methods

Quantifying which features drive model predictions is essential for interpretability. Two complementary approaches address different questions: permutation importance identifies which features are necessary for predictive performance, while SHAP values quantify how features contribute to individual predictions.

Permutation importance [111] measures the decrease in model performance when a feature's values are randomly shuffled, breaking its relationship with the target. For a model with baseline performance s (e.g., R^2), the importance of feature j is:

$$PI_j = s - s_{\pi(j)} \quad \text{Equation 2.5}$$

where $s_{\pi(j)}$ is the performance after permuting feature j . This approach is model-agnostic, accounts for feature interactions, and avoids biases in impurity-based measures that favour high-cardinality features [117]. Bootstrap resampling provides confidence intervals for statistical inference [118].

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) attributes model predictions to individual features using cooperative game theory [119]. The Shapley value ϕ_j for feature j is defined as:

$$\phi_j = \sum_{S \subseteq F \setminus \{j\}} \frac{|S|!(|F| - |S| - 1)!}{|F|!} [f(S \cup \{j\}) - f(S)] \quad \text{Equation 2.6}$$

where F is the full feature set and $f(S)$ is the prediction using only features in S . SHAP values satisfy local accuracy (attributions sum to the prediction), missingness (absent features receive zero attribution), and consistency (increased feature contribution does not reduce attribution). For tree ensembles, TreeSHAP provides exact attribution in polynomial time [120]. Compared to permutation importance, SHAP captures both the magnitude and direction of feature effects, making it well-suited for interpreting nonlinear, interaction-complex models such as XGBoost [121].

2.5.3.3 Cross-Condition Comparison of Feature Importance

When models are trained independently across multiple conditions (e.g., different audio CODECs), comparing feature importance requires statistical methods that assess both ranking consistency and group-level differences. Accordingly, these methods allow the analysis to address whether feature importance rankings are consistent across conditions, and whether

importance differs systematically across feature categories (e.g., instrument or degradation type).

Ranking Agreement and Effect Direction Consistency. Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) measures agreement among m conditions ranking n features [122]:

$$W = \frac{12S}{m^2(n^3 - n)} \quad \text{Equation 2.7}$$

where S is the sum of squared deviations of rank sums from their mean. W ranges from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (perfect agreement). Pairwise Spearman rank correlations ρ further characterise monotonic agreement between specific condition pairs [123]. Spearman correlation also serves as a local function for assessing whether individual features exhibit consistent effect directions across conditions. For each feature j under the condition c , the correlation between SHAP values and the corresponding raw feature values is computed as:

$$\rho_{j,c} = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_i d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \quad \text{Equation 2.8}$$

A consistent sign of $\rho_{j,c}$ across conditions indicates a stable perceptual impact direction, even when effect magnitudes vary.

Bootstrapped Pairwise Comparisons. To test whether importance magnitudes differ between condition pairs, bootstrap resampling generates confidence intervals for the differences in importance magnitudes [124]. For conditions A and B, the bootstrap difference for feature j is:

$$\Delta_j^{(r)} = \bar{\theta}_{j,A}^{(r)} - \bar{\theta}_{j,B}^{(r)}, r = 1, \dots, R \quad \text{Equation 2.9}$$

where $\bar{\theta}_j^{(r)}$ denotes the mean normalised importance estimated from the bootstrap sample r , where r indexes bootstrap resampling iterations and R denotes the total number of resamples. Statistical significance is assessed using the 95% percentile [$\Delta_{0.025}$, $\Delta_{0.975}$]; an interval

excluding zero indicates a significant difference in importance magnitude between conditions.

Group-Level Differences. To test whether feature importance differs by categorical grouping (e.g., degradation type), the Kruskal-Wallis test [125] provides a non-parametric comparison when importance values may not satisfy normality assumptions:

$$H = \frac{12}{N(N+1)} \sum_i \frac{R_i^2}{n_i} - 3(N+1) \quad \text{Equation 2.10}$$

where N is the total sample size, n_i is the size of the group i , and R_i is its rank sum. H follows a χ^2 distribution with $k - 1$ degrees of freedom. The effect size was quantified using

$$\eta_H^2 = (H - k + 1)/(N - k) \quad \text{Equation 2.11}$$

indicating the proportion of rank variance attributable to the feature category[126].

2.5.4 Summary

This section outlines the statistical methods that analyse perceptual quality metrics and degradation sensitivity across CODEC architectures. Each method is selected to support a specific analytical objective in the subsequent experimental chapters. Statistical analysis of MUSHRA represent the subjective test results in the 4.3.2. PCA is used to examine the structure in the high-dimensional degradation parameter space in the 6.4.3, and Tree-Based modelling in 6.4.4 is used to quantify the contribution of individual degradation parameters across conditions and CODECs.

2.6 Conclusion

This chapter reviewed the literature on audio quality in music production signal chains, covering production-related degradations, perceptual audio CODEC mechanisms, audio

quality evaluation methods, intelligent music production and optimisation systems, and the statistical methods applied in this study.

Collectively, perceived audio quality in music production arises from complex interactions between parameterised degradations and perceptual encoding. These interactions are cumulative and context-dependent, and their perceptual consequences cannot be attributed to individual processing stages in isolation. Existing audio quality metrics with inherently scalar properties are widely applied across diverse evaluation contexts, offering potential as analytical tools for examining degradation behaviour in complex production workflows. In parallel, research on intelligent music production provides a structured framework for systematically parameterising and manipulating production processes, enabling the investigation of the perceptual consequences of degradation in a controlled and reproducible manner.

These limitations motivate the experimental framework developed in the following chapters to analyse audio degradation in music production, provide empirical guidance on metric selection and the design of ML-based degradator systems, and clarify fundamental differences in how conventional and neural CODECs respond to degraded input signals.

Chapter 3 Classification and Implementation of Signal Degradations

This chapter defines and categorises the audio degradations implemented in the experimental signal chain. Rather than attempting to exhaustively reproduce all real-world production degradations, the selected degradations represent common, perceptually salient failure modes encountered in music production and digital audio processing. Each degradation is parameterised to enable systematic exploration by optimisation algorithms and controlled analysis of how perceptual quality metrics and audio CODECs respond to increasing degradation severity.

3.1 Extra Noise and degradations

3.1.1 Content-unrelated pitched noise (Hum):

Hum is typically caused by power-line interference arising from inadequate power-supply stabilisation, grounding issues, or insufficient cable shielding [127]. It consists of a fundamental frequency (*50* Hz in Europe or *60* Hz in the United States) and a series of harmonics. Spectrograms commonly reveal prominent components at the fundamental and its odd harmonics, such as *150* Hz [128]. In this study, hum is simulated by synthesising these harmonic structures at controlled levels, parameterised using the signal-to-hum-noise ratio (SNR).

3.1.2 Content-unrelated broadband noise (Hiss):

Hiss refers to steady broadband noise resembling a continuous “s” sound. As noted by [129], random noise is inherent in all electronic systems and may originate from microphones [130] or overdriven transducers [131]. Additive white Gaussian noise is widely used to model hiss in controlled simulations [132]. Accordingly, hiss is introduced here as white noise at adjustable levels, parameterised by the signal-to-hiss-noise ratio (SNR).

3.1.3 Content-related inharmonic noise (Clipping):

Digital clipping occurs when a signal exceeds the system's maximum amplitude threshold, truncating waveform peaks and producing nonlinear distortion with additional harmonic components. Previous studies identify clipping as a particularly disruptive and perceptually annoying degradation [24], [25]. In this work, clipping is modelled using a peak-relative threshold, ensuring that signals of different absolute levels are exposed to the same relative degree of distortion for a given clipping percentage, as a example demonstrate in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Time-domain waveform of a 110 Hz tone showing distortion at 10 % and 30 % clipping.

3.1.4 Temporal noise (Glitches)

Glitches, or dropouts, are transient interruptions in the digital audio stream caused by buffer underflows or delayed data transfer within digital audio workstations (DAWs) [26]. These interruptions manifest as audible clicks or pops and typically arise from failures in real-time communication between the operating system and the audio interface. When processed samples are not delivered to the audio buffer within the required timeframe, dropouts occur [133].

To emulate this behaviour, glitches are simulated by randomly zeroing short segments of the audio signal, for example, Figure 2 demonstrates a segment of glitch at 50 milliseconds s at a 48 kHz sample rate using 256 samples buffer. Only unintentional glitches are considered, excluding creative or stylistic glitch effects used intentionally in certain musical contexts [134].

Figure 2 Simulated glitch in a 100 Hz test tone at a 48 kHz sample rate

3.2 Signal-processing effects as sources of perceptual degradation

3.2.1 Spectral modification through equalisation

Equalisation (EQ) is a fundamental tool in music production for shaping the spectral content of audio signals. Practitioners commonly describe EQ adjustments using perceptual terms such as “warm” or “bright” [135]. In addition to creative applications, EQ is frequently used for corrective purposes, such as attenuating high-frequency noise or suppressing narrow-band resonances.

While digital EQ offers high flexibility and precision, perceived audio quality is strongly linked to spectral and dynamic balance [28]. Excessive or inappropriate EQ can disrupt this balance and be perceived as a form of degradation. In this study, EQ processing is associated with perceived roughness, a psychoacoustic attribute related to musical dissonance [136] and acoustical annoyance [137]. Previous work suggests that increased roughness may interfere with masking relationships and influence CODEC behaviour [53]. Methods for emphasising modulation components associated with roughness are described in [138].

In this study, EQ-induced roughness is treated not as a creative attribute but as a controlled perturbation that alters masking conditions. This makes EQ a suitable mechanism

for examining how perceptual CODECs and objective metrics respond to spectral imbalance introduced by common production processes.

3.2.2 Dynamic-range modification through compression and limiting

Dynamic range describes the difference between the quietest and loudest parts of an audio signal. dynamic range compression (DRC) reduce this range by attenuating signals above a threshold or, in some configurations, amplifying quieter components as demonstrated in Figure 3. When applied judiciously, compression can enhance perceived loudness, presence, and consistency [17]. However, excessive compression with very short release times or aggressive settings can introduce degradation, such as pumping and reduced naturalness [24]. Historically, widespread overuse of compression contributed to the so-called “loudness war” [139].

DRC behaviour is governed by several parameters [140]: threshold, ratio, attack time, release time, and make-up gain. Additional controls, such as knee width, side-chain filtering, hold, and look-ahead, further shape the compressor’s temporal and spectral response.

Figure 3 The effect of different attack and release settings on a waveform. (a) The original levels before compression. (b–e) The resultant levels after compression. Extract from [17]

A limiter is a specialised form of DRC operating with a very high compression ratio (typically $\geq 10:1$) to prevent signals from exceeding a specified maximum level. Limiters employ fast attack and release times and often use look-ahead processing to anticipate peaks and apply gain reduction pre-emptively. They are commonly used to avoid digital clipping in recording and mastering workflows [26].

DRC is selected for its widespread use in music production and its ability to introduce subtle, nonlinear perceptual artefacts. By parameterising threshold, ratio, attack, and release, the compressor defines a multidimensional degradation space that provides a realistic and sensitive test case for evaluating optimisation algorithms under plausible production conditions.

3.3 Conclusion

The degradations defined in this chapter constitute a structured, parameterised degradation space spanning additive, nonlinear, spectral, and temporal artefacts across processing stages. The degradations outlined here are applied in the subsequent experimental chapters, where perceptual quality metrics are analysed to assess their sensitivity and robustness, and optimisation algorithms are employed to explore worst-case degradations in a music-production mixing system.

Chapter 4 Experiment I: metric selection

4.1 Introduction

Reliable evaluation of audio quality is essential in music production signal chains. When degradation interacts with perceptual audio CODECs, generating the cumulative effect, it may severely degrade the audio quality. Objective metrics offer a practical alternative by modelling aspects of human auditory perception, but their reliability depends on the underlying perceptual models and the training data. It varies depending on the type of degradation, signal content, and underlying psychoacoustic assumptions. No single metric has been shown to be universally reliable across the diverse conditions encountered in music production workflows.

This creates a practical challenge in music production contexts: although multiple objective metrics are available, it remains unclear which provides the most reliable assessment of audio quality in music production signal chains. Selecting an inappropriate metric risks misleading conclusions about degradation behaviour and system performance.

To address the Research Question 1 (RQ1): Which listener evaluation metric provides the most reliable assessment of audio quality in music production signal chains? This chapter presents two test frameworks to evaluate five common quality metrics and determine which objective metric best reflects perceived audio quality in music production contexts. First, a Multiple Stimulus with Hidden Reference and Anchor (MUSHRA) [64] based subjective listening test is conducted to establish correlations between listener ratings and objective metric outputs. Second, an objective robustness analysis evaluates how each metric responds to progressively increasing levels of controlled degradation. Together, these tests allow both perceptual validity and consistency under degradation to be assessed.

4.2 Method Framework

This chapter presents a methodology for identifying a suitable objective metric from the candidates. Validation is composed of two complementary approaches: a subjective listening test to assess correlation with listener perception and a series of objective tests to evaluate accuracy under controlled degradation conditions.

4.2.1 Objective quality metric

Five objective metrics algorithms are utilised in this study: Perceptual Evaluation of Audio Quality (PEAQ, both Basic and Advanced version) [74], PEMO-Q [13], Virtual Speech Quality Objective Listener (ViSQOLAudio) [75], and Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index (HAAQI) [71], which have broad applications across various distortion assessments (detail in 2.3.2.1), with the summary in Table 2. Metrics developed for telecommunications or speech coding may not generalise to music signals or to production-style degradations and thus are not included in the test. In terms of the implementation, the study applies PEAQ by gstPEAQ [141] (both basic and advanced versions), PEMO-Q and ViSQOLAudio from the original paper, and the HAAQI implemented by [142].

Table 2 Objective audio quality metrics evaluated in this study

Metric	Design Approach	Intended Use
PEAQ-Basic	FFT-based perceptual model simulating the human auditory system; Computes basic Model Output Variables (MOVs) mapped to quality score via neural network.	Objective evaluation of perceptual distortion in coded audio, standard in ITU-R BS.1387. Low computational complexity.
PEAQ-Adv	Combined FFT and filter-bank ear model with enhanced psychoacoustic features; Applied additional MOVs for improved accuracy.	Higher-accuracy CODEC evaluation. standard in ITU-R BS.1387. High computational complexity.
PEMO-Q	Psychoacoustically validated auditory model computing internal representations; Using the Perceptual Similarity Measure (PSM) based on cross-correlation of assimilated representations.	General audio quality assessment with robustness to unknown distortions; also related source separation application.
ViSQOLAudio	Spectro-temporal similarity measure using gammatone filterbank analysis; Comparing reference and degraded signals via Neurogram Similarity Index Measure (NSIM).	Predicting perceptual quality of encoded music for low-bitrate streaming CODEC
HAAQI	Auditory periphery model incorporating hearing loss effects; measures changes in envelope modulation, temporal fine structure, and long-term spectrum.	Predicting music quality for hearing aid application; supports both normal and impaired hearing configurations.

4.2.2 Audio conditions preparation flow

Figure 4 Overview of the evaluation workflow. The process begins with dataset loading, followed by simulated degradations applied to the audio mix. After level matching and MP3 CODEC compression, degraded and reference signals are generated for subsequent subjective and objective quality evaluation.

The overall evaluation procedure is illustrated in Figure 4. Each audio example is duplicated and then used to create a degraded version by introducing audio production-related degradation (details in Chapter 3). The degraded and reference signals are then loudness-matched and compressed using the MP3, while the uncompressed Standard WAV format version is retained for subjective listening tests. Finally, the subjective ratings and predefined degradation conditions are jointly analysed to assess the performance of the quality metrics.

During calculation, scores are computed offline on Linux, primarily using Python scripts, with PEMO-Q executed in MATLAB. Processing is done at a *48 kHz* sample rate and *16-bit* precision, as required by implementation methods. All metrics used floating-point arithmetic to ensure consistent accuracy. HAAQI is run in normal-hearing mode without hearing-loss adjustments. Due to the differing scales of these metrics, their outputs are normalised to [0,1] before generating the comparative plots presented in the results section.

To minimise loudness-related bias, the degraded and reference tracks are normalised to – *14 LUFS*, a target for the popular streaming platform [143], ensuring consistency across evaluations. Audio compression is applied using the LAME MP3 encoder [144] as a representative distribution-stage encoder, providing a controlled and reproducible reference.

4.2.3 Summary

This production process generates representative degradation conditions through controlled degradation, CODEC compression, and loudness normalisation. The first test correlates subjective listener scores with objective metrics on EQ-manipulated audio to establish a perceptual reference, while the second test evaluates these metrics across multiple degradation types to assess their reliability and robustness. Together, this two-stage design identifies objective metrics that most closely align with subjective perception and remain stable across varying degradation conditions.

4.3 Subjective listening test

This section investigates the relationship between spectral manipulation and the perceived audio quality of CODEC-compressed musical intervals. Building on the roughness hypothesis: when closely spaced tones create modulation rather than distinct pitches, they are often perceived as harsh or dissonant [53]. The experiment evaluates how such conditions interact with CODEC processing, leading to changes in audio quality. A MUSHRA-based

listening test is conducted to assess perceived audio quality across controlled spectral manipulations (EQ), musical intervals, and compression conditions.

4.3.1 Experimental design

The experiment follows a factorial design with the following factors:

- Instrument: piano, cello, pipe organ.
- Musical interval: minor second (C–C \sharp), tritone (C–F \sharp), perfect fifth (C–G), minor seventh (C–A \sharp).
- EQ condition: none (original), acoustic roughness enhancement, musical roughness enhancement.
- CODEC condition: uncompressed (Standard WAV), MP3 at 96 kbps, MP3 at 32 kbps as Anchor.

This results in 7 stimulus conditions per interval and instrument, yielding a total of 168 audio stimuli ($7 \text{ conditions} \times 4 \text{ intervals} \times 3 \text{ instruments}$).

4.3.1.1 EQ manipulation design

Spectral manipulation is applied to emphasise frequency regions associated with perceived roughness. Two distinct EQ strategies are implemented:

- Musical roughness enhancement, targeting interactions between harmonically related partials by amplifying the subharmonic regions of the interval tones.
- Acoustic roughness enhancement, targeting low-frequency modulation effects by amplifying subharmonic regions within approximately 1 kHz of the fundamental frequency.

EQ processing is implemented using a peak equaliser in iZotope Neutron 3, following approaches similar to [138], [145]. Gain values ranged from +3 dB to +6 dB, depending on

instrument and interval, and are chosen to produce audible but controlled spectral changes without introducing clipping.

A spectral analysis verified the intended changes, as illustrated in Figure 5, which compares the spectral distribution of a cello playback at C3–C#3 under three conditions. With musical roughness enhancement targeting lower-order harmonics (e.g. C4–C#4) and acoustic roughness enhancement emphasising higher-order harmonics around 1 kHz (e.g. C6–C#6).

Figure 5 Spectral comparison (Welch method) of cello playback at C3–C#3 with three Spectral manipulation settings: original signal, acoustic enhancement, and musical enhancement.

4.3.1.2 Audio stimulus preparation

Audio stimuli are produced using a digital audio workstation (DAW) with the Audio sample library, which includes piano, cello, and pipe organ samples. Samples are rendered at a 48 kHz sample rate/ 16-bit precision in the stereo mode. Musical intervals are generated within the C3–C4 register to control pitch range and timbral consistency.

Following EQ processing, all audio files are loudness-normalised to -14 LUFS to ensure consistent playback levels across conditions. Each stimulus is rendered in both uncompressed (WAV) and compressed (MP3, 96 kbps) formats, representing a common low-bitrate

distribution scenario. All files are fixed to 4 seconds in duration and randomly labelled during tests to prevent listener bias.

4.3.1.3 Listening test procedure

The listening test is conducted using WebMUSHRA [146], an online framework that conforms to the BS.1534 [64] guidelines (Figure 6). For each trial, participants rated seven stimulus versions on a continuous 0–100 scale, where 0 indicated very poor quality and 100 excellent qualities.

Figure 6 . Web-based MUSHRA interface used for the subjective listening test. Listeners compare multiple stimulus conditions against a reference by playing each version independently and assigning quality ratings on a continuous 0–100 scale. All stimuli within a trial are accessible simultaneously, allowing direct perceptual comparison in accordance with ITU-R BS.1534 recommendations.

Tests were conducted in a controlled listening room compliant with BS.1116 [63] at the University of Salford (Figure 7) to minimise external noise and environmental distractions. Playback is delivered via a Windows laptop, routed through a MOTU 4pre audio interface, and reproduced using Beyerdynamic DT 1990 Pro circumaural headphones.

Participants were instructed to evaluate overall sound quality, tonal balance, and the presence of distortions or artefacts. The presentation order is randomised per listener to

minimise ordering effects. Each session lasted approximately 30 minutes, including short breaks.

Seventeen volunteers (15 male, 2 female), aged 21–64, participated in the experiment. None reported hearing impairments. Most participants had musical or audio-engineering backgrounds. All participants provided informed consent, and ethical approval was granted by the University of Salford Research Ethics Committee (*Ref: 0842*).

Figure 7 The listening room for the experiment

4.3.2 Subjective test results

This section analyses the subjective listening test results and evaluates their relationship with objective audio quality metrics. Listener ratings are first statistically examined to confirm perceptual differences across conditions, followed by correlation analyses assessing the alignment between subjective judgments and objective metric outputs.

4.3.2.1 Subjective data evaluations

Figure 8 Box plots of audio quality rating versus audio conditions. (The "32k" and "96k" are lossy versions of the original lossless audio file "Wav" in the corresponding bitrate. The "wav_ak" is the acoustic roughness enhancement on the original wav, whereas the "96k_ak" is the lossy version in the 96k bitrate. The "wav_muk" is the musical roughness enhancement on the original wav, whereas the "96k_muk" is the lossy version in the 96k bitrate.)

The subjective ratings were collected across three independent variables: Interval, Instrument, and Audio Condition, with the perceived audio quality score as the dependent variable. Each listener provided a rating on a continuous 0–100 scale for all stimuli.

Figure 8 presents the box plots of the aggregated results. The 32k anchor condition is consistently rated lowest, confirming its effectiveness as a perceptual anchor. The distributions across all conditions were relatively symmetric, suggesting consistent participant responses with no significant outliers.

Across all instruments, the original WAV files received the highest median scores ($M = 76.0$, $SD = 21.3$), followed by 96k compressed ($M = 74.5$, $SD = 21.1$). Both roughness-enhanced versions (wav_ak_EQ and wav_muk_EQ) showed lower but comparable ratings to their original counterparts, indicating that mild spectral manipulation does introduce perceptual degradation.

Prior to selecting the analysis method, the Royston and Mardia tests assess normality by examining univariate skewness and kurtosis, as well as multivariate normality. The multivariate normality test indicated a mild deviation from normality ($p \approx 0.011$), while multivariate skewness and kurtosis were not significant. Some univariate skewness values exceeded 0.5 but remained below 1.0, indicating limited departures from normality. BS.1534 [64] notes that no strict thresholds for acceptable deviation from normality are defined for listening test data; therefore, repeated-measures ANOVA (rmANOVA) remains appropriate in this context.

The Huynh–Feldt correction was applied to account for potential violations of sphericity in the three-way rmANOVA. The analysis revealed significant main effects of audio condition ($F = 31.9$, *Effect size* = 0.421, $p < 0.001$) and a significant interaction between audio condition and instrument ($F = 20.5$, *Effect size* = 0.073, $p < 0.001$). All single effects are significant, though all have small effect sizes. Table 3 lists all significance levels and effect sizes across conditions.

Based on these validated subjective variations, correlations between listener ratings and objective metrics are computed in the next section.

Table 3 The result of three-way ANOVA indicates the effect on the audio condition, Intervals, instruments, audio conditions across intervals, and audio conditions across instruments. F is the F distribution level; DFn is the value of degrees of freedom numerator; DFd is the degrees of freedom denominator. Effect size is measured by the generalised eta-squared. The magnitude of the measure scale large \rightarrow effect size >0.14 , medium \rightarrow effect size >0.06 , small \rightarrow effect size <0.06 ; large and medium effect sizes are in bold. The three-way interactions (Conditions \times Intervals \times Instruments) and the across-intervals \times instruments interaction are not significant at the required significance level ($p < 0.05$), and the significant interaction is in bold.

Effect Type	DFn	DFd	F	p	Effect Size	Effect Size Magnitude
Audio Conditions	2.11	27.47	31.907	<0.001	0.421	Large
Intervals	8.87	115.27	2.467	0.023	0.008	Small
Instruments	1	13	5.903	0.03	0.004	Small
Audio Conditions \times Intervals	42	546	2.139	<0.001	0.035	Small
Audio Conditions \times Instruments	4.34	56.43	20.481	<0.001	0.073	Medium
Intervals \times Instruments	4.74	61.62	0.949	0.453	-	-
Audio Conditions \times Instruments \times Intervals	42	546	0.826	0.774	-	-

4.3.2.2 Correlation calculation

For each audio condition, objective quality scores were computed across all instruments and intervals using 5 metrics: PEAQ-Basic, PEAQ-Advanced, VISQOL, PEMO-Q, and HAAQI. All metric outputs were normalised to the [0, 1] range for comparability. Table 4 lists the coefficients of determination (R^2) and significance levels (p) with respect to the subjective ratings.

Table 4 Correlation between subjective listening scores and objective audio quality metrics. The table coefficients of determination (R^2), and significance levels (p -values) for each metric.

Objective Metric	R	R^2	P
PEAQ – Basic	0.613	0.376	< 0.001
PEAQ – Advance	0.713	0.509	< 0.001
VISQOL	0.558	0.311	< 0.001
PEMO	0.477	0.227	< 0.001
HAAQI	0.663	0.440	< 0.001

Figure 9 Correlation between subjective ratings and objective audio quality metrics (HAAQI, PEAQ_B, PEAQ_ADV, VISQ, and PEMO). Red lines indicate linear regression fits with 95% confidence intervals.

The PEAQ-Advanced ($R^2 = 0.51$) achieved the strongest correlation with listener ratings, followed by HAAQI ($R^2 = 0.44$) and PEAQ-Basic ($R^2 = 0.38$). PEAQ-Advanced and HAAQI are the two best metrics for capturing partial perceptual degradations arising from EQ-manipulated spectral imbalance during CODEC compression. This perceptual correlation in PEAQ is possible because it is sensitive to changes in CODEC-related artefacts, making it a reliable predictor of perceived quality when spectral manipulation and encoding interact.

4.3.3 Subjective test results summary

This experiment assessed how EQ-manipulated spectral modifications and perceptual CODECs influence perceived audio quality. Stimuli comprising different instruments, musical intervals, and EQ manipulations were evaluated through MUSHRA listening tests conducted under controlled conditions. A significant difference with a large effect size is found for the audio conditions dimension, including EQ manipulation and CODEC

compression degradation. Further, a correlation is found between subjective perceived quality and objective metrics, revealing that PEAQ Advanced ($R^2 = 0.51$) and HAAQI ($R^2 = 0.44$) are the two metrics that most closely align with listener ratings. The following test further examines the effectiveness and robustness of these objective predictors.

4.4 Objective evaluation test

This test evaluates the effectiveness and robustness of metrics under production-style degradations. Using 12 music tracks from the MUSDB18 dataset [147]. The test examines metric responses to typical degradations, including hum, hiss, clipping, and glitches. Two complementary evaluations are conducted: an effectiveness test assessing responsiveness to increasing degradation level, and a robustness test evaluating stability under fixed but randomised conditions. Together, these analyses assess each metric's suitability for perceptual quality assessment in music production contexts.

4.4.1 Experiment design

This section describes the design of a system to simulate common degradation in music production and presents an evaluation process that applies various objective metrics. The subsequent content details the experimental preparation, including the selection of audio tracks, the choice of evaluation metrics, the software environment and the methodology employed for the evaluation.

4.4.1.1 Audio examples selection

Table 5 lists 12 audio tracks from the MUSDB18 dataset [147], focusing on pop and rock genres representative of home-studio production workflows. Only the final stereo mixtures (mixture.wav) were evaluated. To reduce computational load and fit to the metric limitations, the first 8-second excerpt of each track is extracted and downmixed to mono.

Table 5 The tracks of audio samples for objective testing

Track title	Original Duration (seconds)
#MD1– Beatles	33
#MD2– Britpop	33
#MD3– Country1	32
#MD4– Country2	16
#MD5– Disco	114
#MD6– Gospel	69
#MD7– Grunge	38
#MD8– Hendrix	18
#MD9– Punk	26
#MD10– Reggae	17
#MD11– Rock	12
#MD12– Rockabilly	23

Each audio excerpt is processed through a multi-step degradation procedure and CODEC compression pipeline before evaluation. Objective metrics compared degraded signals against reference versions, both in MP3-encoded, as illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Audio-quality evaluation pipeline for clean reference vs. degraded signal. The degradation type applied in the process includes hum, hiss, clipping, and glitch.

4.4.1.2 Degradation model and definitions

4 degradation types were applied to simulate a common production signal chain: hum, hiss, clipping, and glitches. These respectively represent Content-unrelated pitched noise, Content-unrelated broadband noise, Content-related inharmonic noise, and Temporal noise (details in Chapter 3). Each degradation is parameterised to allow controlled variation in severity, enabling systematic evaluation of metric behaviour. The degradation types and parameter ranges are summarised in Table 6.

Table 6 Degradation types and parameterisation used in the objective evaluation

Degradation	Description	Control parameter	Range
Hum	Sinusoidal interference simulating power-line noise	Signal-to-hum ratio (dB)	1–80 dB
Hiss	Broadband white noise	Signal-to-noise ratio (dB)	1–80 dB
Clipping	Nonlinear amplitude distortion	Percentage of clipped samples	1–100%
Glitches	Transient signal dropouts or discontinuities	Number of events	1–100

4.4.1.3 Objective evaluation tests

The study assumes that an ideal metric should reflect changes in audio quality with reasonable sensitivity as degradation levels increase (effectiveness), while remaining stable under fixed degradation conditions and across audio samples (robustness).

Effectiveness Test: Metric effectiveness is assessed by applying progressively increasing levels of each degradation type. Signal-to-hum and signal-to-hiss ratios ranged from 1 to 80 dB, clipping ranged from 1% to 100% of samples, and glitches ranged from 1 to 100 events. Metric scores were averaged across audio examples at each degradation level to evaluate sensitivity to degradation severity.

Robustness Test: Metric robustness is evaluated under fixed degradation settings with randomised variations, including fluctuation noise realisation in hiss and glitch placement. Conditions comprised 60 dB signal-to-hum and signal-to-noise ratios, 1% clipping, and 5 glitch events. Each metric is computed over 100 iterations per audio example to assess output stability.

4.4.2 Effectiveness test results

This section explores the performance of metrics across 4 degradation types. Metrics are evaluated against lossy (MP3) references to identify trends and limitations as degradations increase. 12 audio examples show similar trends across the sections' figures; therefore, the curves represent the mean values across all examples. Individual results for each audio example are provided.

The findings provide insights into the practical effectiveness and unintended behaviours of these metrics when applied to different audio degradation types and quantities, highlighting critical regions where each metric performs well or struggles to capture perceptual quality changes.

4.4.2.1 Hum noise degradation test

Figure 11 Mean metric trends with rising signal-to-hum noise ratio, comparing degraded audio to lossy MP3 references.

All metrics in Figure 11 rise with increasing signal-to-hum noise ratio and plateau between 30–50 dB, indicating improved quality as hum noise decreases. Eventually, scores converge toward 1, a high similarity to the MP3 reference.

PEMO-Q and ViSQOLAudio show stable scores across all SNR levels. This early convergence indicates lower sensitivity to the hum noise. The PEAQ Advanced shows an over-scale score above 1, suggesting potential limitations. PEAQ Basic and HAAQI show

greater sensitivity at lower SNR; PEAQ Basic improves sharply beyond 20 dB, while HAAQI increases gradually, both capturing incremental quality changes.

4.4.2.2 Hiss noise degradation test

Figure 12 Mean metric trends with rising signal-to-white noise ratio, comparing degraded audio to lossy MP3 references.

All metrics in Figure 12 exhibit an upward trend as the signal-to-white noise ratio increases, indicating that low SNR conditions result in significant signal degradation. Additionally, the metrics tend to plateau at higher SNR levels above 60 dB, where the noise becomes negligible and has minimal impact on perceived audio quality. The most critical region for evaluation occurs at mid-range SNR values, where the metrics show notable variability in their response to moderate levels of degradation.

As SNR increases, PEMO-Q and PEAQ Basic show a sharp quality improvement between 40-60 dB, while HAAQI and ViSQOLAudio exhibit a more gradual rise starting around 30 dB SNR. PEAQ Advanced displays an anomalous peak at 0-10 dB SNR, indicating potential algorithmic limitations in low-SNR conditions.

4.4.2.3 Clipping degradation test

Figure 13 Mean metric trends with rising percentage of clipping, comparing degraded audio to lossy MP3 references.

All metrics in Figure 13 exhibit a downward trend as the clipping percentage increases, highlighting the severe distortion introduced even at levels below 5%. PEAQ Basic and PEMO-Q drop sharply and plateau around 20%, while HAAQI declines more gradually, stabilising near 50%. This stabilisation across metrics likely occurs as the signal becomes heavily distorted and unrecognisable.

Notably, PEAQ Basic's early decline aligns with findings from [71], which reported its limitations in handling non-linear distortion. In contrast, ViSQOLAudio demonstrates a more gradual decline, reflecting its moderate sensitivity to clipping distortion across all levels. However, this behaviour underscores its limited effectiveness in accurately identifying and assessing the impact of severe clipping degradation. Supported by [15], which reports that ViSQOLAudio performs poorly when applied to datasets containing clipping distortion. Furthermore, PEAQ Advanced exhibits an unintended trend after reaching its lowest point. This anomaly also indicates its limitations when handling extreme clipping conditions.

4.4.2.4 Glitch degradation test

Figure 14 Mean metric trends with rising occurrence of glitch, comparing degraded audio to lossy MP3 references.

All metrics in Figure 14 generally decline as the number of glitch occurrences increases. This trend is expected, as an increasing number of glitches introduces severe interruptions in the audio signal, leading to a readily perceived degradation in quality. Also, due to the randomness of glitch occurrences, all metrics exhibit a certain degree of fluctuation as the number of glitches increases.

PEAQ Basic and PEMO-Q emerge as the most sensitive metrics to glitch degradation. PEAQ Basic shows a steep decline in quality scores within the 10 glitch occurrence, indicating a rapid response to early interruptions. However, PEAQ Basic and PEMO-Q exhibit noticeable fluctuations throughout the plot, where scenarios with more glitches occasionally achieve higher scores than those with fewer glitches. The PEAQ Advanced metric demonstrates similar behaviour; additionally, while the reference is in a lossy condition, over-threshold values (scores exceeding 1.0) are observed. In contrast, the HAAQI and VISQOLAudio show a more stable decline. Whether this counterintuitive behaviour reflects real-world conditions remains an open question.

4.4.2.5 Effectiveness test summary

The effectiveness test evaluates how each metric responds to increasing levels of degradation, revealing differences across degradation types. HAAQI shows a smooth, gradual trend that aligns well with linear degradation. PEAQ Basic and PEMO-Q also track changes

effectively but display more abrupt shifts and fluctuations under glitches. ViSQOLAudio responds to white noise and clipping but remains flat under hum and glitches. PEAQ Advanced shows inconsistent behaviour, including an unexpected peak with white noise and unusually high scores at severe clipping levels.

4.4.3 Robustness test results

In addition to effectiveness, metric robustness was quantified as the dispersion of metric outputs across repeated trials under fixed degradation parameters with randomised realisations (white-noise seed and glitch placement). For each audio example i and metric m , scores $m_{i,r}$ were computed across $R = 100$ repetitions, yielding:

$$\{m_{i,r}\}_{r=1}^R \tag{Equation 4.1}$$

Robustness was defined as the within-condition standard deviation $Std_{i,m}$, with lower values indicating greater robustness.

Metric variability was summarised across all audio examples using boxplots and by reporting the mean and standard deviation of $Std_{i,m}$. Robustness was evaluated under fixed degradation settings of 60 dB SNR hum, 60 dB SNR white noise, 1% clipping, and 5 glitch events. Randomised noise realisations and glitch placements introduce controlled variability across repetitions, providing a principled basis for assessing metric stability.

Figure 15 The variability of audio quality metrics score under the conditions of fixed level degraded signal against the lossy MP3 reference across the audio samples.

Table 7 Mean of each metric normalised score across each audio example

Metric	Country1	Country2	Punk	Rock	Beatles	Rockabilly	Gospel	Reggae	Britpop	Hendrix	Grunge	Disco
PEAQ-Basic	0.4	0.429	0.545	0.341	0.443	0.397	0.156	0.215	0.382	0.319	0.462	0.577
PEAQ-Adv	0.683	0.773	0.786	0.695	0.719	0.629	0.52	0.694	0.639	0.65	0.763	0.783
PEMO-Q	0.625	0.679	0.547	0.704	0.609	0.707	0.41	0.671	0.651	0.687	0.517	0.733
HAAQI	0.759	0.797	0.828	0.829	0.805	0.773	0.762	0.815	0.8	0.798	0.826	0.83
ViSQOL	0.907	0.91	0.898	0.9	0.91	0.906	0.869	0.89	0.899	0.907	0.905	0.914

Table 8 Standard deviation (STD) of each metric normalised score across each audio example

Metric	Country1	Country2	Punk	Rock	Beatles	Rockabilly	Gospel	Reggae	Britpop	Hendrix	Grunge	Disco
PEAQ_Basic	0.04	0.076	0.009	0.086	0.032	0.056	0.041	0.089	0.052	0.069	0.079	0.063
PEAQ_Advance	0.039	0.068	0.012	0.099	0.045	0.067	0.054	0.144	0.038	0.09	0.063	0.065
PEMO-Q	0.023	0.023	0.018	0.023	0.023	0.015	0.02	0.035	0.021	0.024	0.021	0.011
HAAQI	0.007	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.006	0.006	0.008	0.013	0.005	0.007	0.01	0.005
ViSQOL	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.001

Figure 15 presents the score distributions as boxplots, while Table 7 and Table 8 report the corresponding means and standard deviations aggregated across all audio examples and metrics. On average, while ViSQOLAudio ($Std = 0.004$) has the lowest standard deviation, indicating superior robustness, followed by close second HAAQI ($Std = 0.007$) and PEMO-Q ($Std = 0.021$).

The results also reveal perceptual differences across audio samples. All metrics assign lower scores to the gospel track, perhaps because its prominent vocals make degradations more noticeable. ViSQOLAudio shows stable variability across iterations but also slight variation across examples, suggesting most stable to genre-specific differences.

4.4.3.1 Robustness test summary

In the robustness experiment, metrics were evaluated under fixed but fluctuating degradations across audio examples. ViSQOLAudio and HAAQI demonstrated the highest stability, with the lowest standard deviations across the degradation.

4.4.4 Objective test results summary

This experiment evaluated the performance of five objective audio quality metrics. The audio mixtures from the MUSDB18 dataset [147] are subjected to controlled degradations. The test framework comprised two stages: an effectiveness test, assessing metric responsiveness to increasing levels of hum, hiss, clipping, and glitch degradations, and a robustness test, examining metric stability under fixed but randomised degradation conditions.

In the effectiveness test, results show that HAAQI provides the most consistent and perceptually aligned responses, maintaining smooth, linear behaviour across degradation types. While ViSQOLAudio remains stable yet less sensitive to certain degradation, PEAQ Basic and PEMO-Q track degradation effectively but fluctuate under glitches. PEAQ Advanced displays irregular behaviour in low-SNR and severe clipping conditions. In terms

of robustness, both ViSQOLAudio and HAAQI show stable variability, indicating strong robustness across iterations.

Overall, HAAQI and ViSQOLAudio emerge as the two most reliable and versatile metrics for practical, objective audio quality evaluation in the presence of complex or perceptually diverse degradations.

4.5 Conclusion

This chapter evaluated objective audio quality metrics through two complementary test frameworks. First, a MUSHRA-based listening test examined how well candidates reflect perceived quality under the audio conditions of EQ-manipulated spectral modification, interacting with the CODEC process. Second, an objective evaluation assessed the metric's effectiveness and robustness under controlled common production-style degradations across a range of music examples.

In the first experiment, PEAQ-Advanced and HAAQI showed a strong correlation with subjective listener judgments, while in the second test, HAAQI and ViSQOLAudio exhibited the most consistent behaviour across degradation types and conditions. Together, HAAQI is the most suitable metric for subsequent experiments, particularly given its ability to assess quality under nonlinear distortion, agree with the finding [9].

The strong performance of PEAQ-Advanced is expected, as the test stimuli align closely with those used in CODEC evaluation; however, PEAQ-Advanced is unstable under objective testing, despite reports of reduced reliability compared with the basic version in certain conditions [69].

ViSQOLAudio showed high consistency in the robustness test, but its degradation-dependent sensitivity is consistent with previous findings [15], which reduced responsiveness to certain artefact types. While this behaviour supports robustness, it constrains its effectiveness as a general analytical tool for investigating degradation mechanisms.

These findings establish a perceptually validated metric foundation for subsequent chapters. The next chapter builds on this foundation by examining how different optimisation algorithms behave when exploring large, multi-parameter control degradation parameter spaces with a reliable objective-quality metric.

Chapter 5 Experiment II: optimiser selection

5.1 Introduction

An intelligent music production system (IMP) often involves exploring high-dimensional parameter spaces with multiple interacting processing stages. While the optimisation techniques are well established for such tasks (details in 2.4), they do not suit the inverse problem of exploring the degradation parameter space and diagnosing worst-case scenarios for stress-testing the CODEC.

This optimiser application difference is non-trivial. When optimisation algorithms used in IMP are designed to converge to the reference target datasets, they do not automatically perform well when seeking the maximised solution region with a non-analytic gradient perceptual metric. The applications fundamentally differ in their search topology, convergence properties, and exploration requirements. No validated algorithmic framework exists for the degradation-maximising problem, and the relative performance of different methods remains empirically unknown.

To address Research Question 2 (RQ2): Does the choice of optimisation algorithm significantly influence degradation maximisation outcomes? This chapter compares Monte Carlo sampling (MC), Genetic Algorithms (GA), and Reinforcement Learning (RL) within a novel perceptually oriented machine learning (ML)-based degradator framework. The system applies controlled production degradations: noise, clipping, and dynamic range compression (DRC); and evaluates perceptual quality using the Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index (HAAQI), and iteratively searches for maximum-degradation configurations. All optimisers operate under identical conditions (same parameter spaces, evaluation budgets, and objective functions), enabling a systematic comparison of their performance in terms of convergence effectiveness and search diversity.

5.2 ML-based degradator system setup

To evaluate how different optimisers perform under realistic production conditions, this experiment implements a modular ML-based degradator framework that integrates perceptual evaluation into the optimisation loop. The system is designed to simulate the professional audio production chain before CODEC processing and quality evaluation. The quality metric HAAQI, with its reliability proven in Chapter 4, assess production quality through iterative optimisation. By simulating degradations (noise, clipping, and DRC), the framework enables quantitative analysis of how optimisation algorithms (GA, MC, RL) search performance maximises objective degradation and probe diversity in high-dimensional parameter spaces. The system design is described in the following sections.

5.2.1 System design overview

Figure 16 Overview of the optimisation system architecture. The workflow comprises four interconnected modules: (1) the degradator, which applies controlled degradations to simulate real-world production artefacts; (2) the Codec Processor, which compresses the signal to model transmission loss; (3) the Quality Evaluator, which computes the HAAQI score to quantify perceptual degradation; and (4) the Optimiser, which iteratively updates the parameter set based on feedback from the evaluator.

The system simulates a typical music production and transmission signal chain, applying parameterised degradations as identified in Chapter 3, while supporting iterative optimisation. It comprises four interconnected modules: a degradator, a CODEC processor, a quality evaluator, and an optimiser. Together, these form a closed-loop architecture that tests how

optimisation algorithms respond to feedback on perceptual quality. An overview of the workflow is shown in Figure 16. The process begins with clean audio that passes through the degradator, where effects are applied to emulate common audio degradation, such as noise, clipping, and DRC. A perceptual CODEC then encodes the processed signal, evaluates it using the HAAQI quality metric, and returns the result to the optimiser, which updates the parameters to maximise the degradation in the next iteration.

Data flow within the system follows two concurrent paths: the audio path and the control path. The audio path transmits the signal sequentially from the degradator to the CODEC to the evaluator, while the control path carries optimisation feedback from the evaluator back to the optimiser and degradator. The optimiser generates a new parameter configuration, which is reapplied to the degradator in the next cycle. This loop continues until a predefined iteration limit condition is reached. Such a design reflects the adaptive behaviour of the systems, where parameter selection is guided by perceptual feedback to achieve the most degraded configuration.

Each module represents a functional stage in music production and distribution, except the evaluator, which provides an objective quality assessment. The degradator introduces common production degradation, and the CODEC processor models transmission effects that also alter the perceptual salience relative to the underlying signal. The evaluator uses HAAQI to quantify degradation for optimisation, which demonstrated its superior performance in evaluating perceptual quality. The optimiser, implemented as a GA, an MC search, or an RL agent, explores the parameter space using the evaluation score as a signal to identify the most perceptually degraded configurations. This modular setup ensures that the workflow mirrors both perceptual evaluation and computational efficiency found in real production environments.

5.2.1.1 Terminology related to the system

Signal-to-hum noise ratio: Hum originates from power-line interference (typically 50 Hz and its harmonics at 150 Hz). Its level relative to the clean signal is expressed as a signal-

to-noise ratio (SNR). The excessive low-frequency contamination perceptually masks bass elements and reduces clarity.

Signal-to-hiss noise ratio: Hiss is broadband noise generated by electronic circuits or microphones. It is modelled as white noise added to the signal, quantified by its SNR relative to the signal RMS.

Clipping: A form of waveform distortion that occurs when an amplifier is overdriven, attempting to deliver an output voltage or current beyond its maximum capability, resulting in the waveform being "clipped" at the amplifier's limits. Clipping introduces high-frequency harmonic distortion from waveform truncation, often perceived as a harsh, "crackling" timbre.

Dynamic range compression: DRC alters the amplitude envelope according to threshold, ratio, attack, and release. In this framework, the optimiser systematically varies these parameters. With lower thresholds or higher ratios, stronger compression reduces dynamic contrast, leading to degradation.

HAAQI: an objective metric that measures the degradation of audio quality. The previous experiment concluded that its accuracy reflects the degradation in quality in the audio production context. The score is normalised to 0-1, with higher scores indicating better quality.

5.2.2 Implementing the degradator

This section describes the implementation of the ML-based degradator module used to generate controlled audio production degradation for optimisation. It outlines the degradation types and parameterisation strategy, the pre- and post-processing pipeline, and the calibration of parameter ranges to ensure perceptually meaningful and reproducible evaluation across optimisation iterations.

5.2.2.1 Degradation processing

To emulate realistic production artefacts, the degradator module applies controlled degradations to each audio track before CODEC processing and metric evaluation. These degradations reproduce common issues encountered during recording or mixing (details in Chapter 3). By parameterising their type and intensity, the system can systematically explore how optimisation algorithms respond to changes in degradation permutations with a perceptual metric evaluation.

The system supports four types of degradation: hum, hiss, clipping, and DRC. These operations are executed sequentially for each track according to the following procedural logic: hum (SNR_hum) → hiss (SNR_hiss) → clipping (clip_ratio) → DRC(threshold, ratio, attack, release). Hum and hiss typically originate during recording, whereas clipping and temporal reshaping are introduced during the mixing stage of audio production.

Hum noise is generated as a sum of sinusoids at 50 Hz and 150 Hz, representing power-line interference. Hiss is modelled as broadband white noise with a flat spectral density. Their relative intensities are determined by the SNR in decibels:

$$SNR = 10 \lg \left(\frac{P_{signal}}{P_{noise}} \right) \text{ dB} \quad \text{Equation 5.1}$$

where P_{signal} and P_{noise} are the root-mean-square (RMS) powers of the clean and noise components, respectively. Lower SNR values indicate greater degradation; clipping is simulated by saturating the digital range from $[-1, +1]$. The clipping percentage specifies the proportion of samples to clip. The algorithm ranks samples by their absolute amplitude and progressively clamps the highest values to the upper and lower limits until the specified percentage of samples is reached. DRC attenuates signal levels exceeding a defined threshold, with behaviour governed by threshold, ratio, attack, and release parameters. In this framework, the threshold is specified relative to the signal's peak level.

5.2.2.2 Diagnostic optimisation and constraint design

The system is formulated to maximise perceptual degradation rather than quality, functioning as a stress-testing framework for CODEC evaluation. As identified in 2.2.5, degradation interacts with the CODEC, which may vary depending on the content structure and degradation levels. Identifying the maximum degradation scenarios reveals which types or compound structures of degradation are most sensitive to each CODEC. However, in realistic production workflows, extremely severe degradations are unlikely to occur without an audio engineer's intervention.

Thus, to maintain perceptual relevance, the magnitude of each degradation is constrained to an HAAQI score of approximately 0.75 , corresponding to a clearly perceptible but moderate level of quality reduction, consistent with a subjective listening evaluation tier [62]. These calibrated bounds ensure perceptual validity and comparability across degradation types. Within these constraints, the optimiser iteratively explores the combined parameter space, balancing degradation strength against the resulting quality metric. The selected degradation components and their bounded ranges are summarised in Table 9.

Table 9 Parameter Ranges and Worst-Quality Conditions in the Optimisation Experiment

Parameter	Lowest range	Highest range	Value Associated with Worst Quality
Signal to Hum noise(dB)	15	60	15
Signal to Hiss noise(dB)	30	60	30
Clipping(%)	0	2	2
Compressor Threshold(dB)	-15	0	-15
Ratio	1	10	10
Compressor attack(milliseconds)	0.1	10	0.1
Compressor release(milliseconds)	50	300	50

5.2.2.3 Audio sample processing

The processing pipeline comprises three main stages: pre-processing, degradation, and post-processing, ensuring fair and reproducible evaluation across test cases.

Figure 17 Detailed manipulation and evaluation process in a single Iteration.

Pre-processing. Each audio sample is truncated to an 8-second segment, converted to mono to reduce computational cost, and resampled to 48 kHz, 16-bit precision to meet the quality metric requirements. Tracks within a mix are RMS-balanced before degradation to maintain consistent initial loudness.

Degradation stage. The optimiser supplies the parameter vector $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, p_2, \dots, p_7]$ for each single-track operation (and $4 \times \mathbf{p}$ for multi-track projects). The degradator module apply the operations described in 5.2.2.1, producing a degraded version of each track. These were then summed to form the full mix.

Post-processing. Before CODEC compression and evaluation, both reference and degraded mixes are normalised to -14 LUFS to match the loudness standard of streaming platforms. This step neutralises level bias in the objective metric. The final audio is encoded at a bitrate of 64 kbps, when [148] the artefacts at 128 kbps were "perceptible" for the stereo format. MP3 using LAME CODEC [144] to simulate perceptual coding losses, and the resulting signal quality is evaluated using the HAAQI metric.

Such pre- and post-processing controls ensure that observed metric variations arise from perceptual degradation rather than from loudness discrepancies.

5.2.3 Test audio dataset

To evaluate optimisation performance across diverse content, the experiment employed material from both music and speech domains.

The MUSDB18 [147] provided typical rock or pop music style multi-track projects with discrete tracks (vocals, drums, bass, other) and mixed versions, representative of professional mixing scenarios. For the multi-track test, the four-track tracks allow degradation control individually. For non-musical content, clean speech excerpts were drawn from the “What To Listen For” tutorial [7], where offering typical speech recordings is applied in the CODEC quality assessment context. Table 10 summarises the dataset composition.

In total, the dataset comprised 5 single-track music examples, 4 multi-track mix projects, and 3 speech samples. This combination provides spectral and dynamic diversity while maintaining experimental manageability.

Table 10 The Audio content for testing

Example Name	Category	Original Duration (seconds)	Original Source
English	Speech	8	What To Listen For
German	Speech	10	What To Listen For
Music with Speech	Speech	15	What To Listen For
Hendrix	Music	18	MUSDB18
Rock	Music	12	MUSDB18
Punk	Music	26	MUSDB18
Grunge	Music	38	MUSDB18
Britpop	Music	33	MUSDB18
Reggae	Mix	17	MUSDB18
Disco	Mix	114	MUSDB18
Beatles	Mix	33	MUSDB18
Country1	Mix	32	MUSDB18

5.2.4 Software related to the implementation of the system

The ML-based degradator system is implemented in Python using the Librosa [149] and the Audioargumentation[150] library for signal processing, and NumPy [151] for numerical computation. All audio examples are processed through a pre- and post-processing pipeline, which enables scalable testing of optimisation behaviour under controlled perceptual conditions and provides a reproducible framework for comparing algorithmic strategies.

5.2.5 Summary

This section introduced a modular ML-based degradator framework developed to examine the behaviour of different optimisation algorithms within a high-dimensional parameter space. The framework integrates controlled audio degradation, perceptual coding, and objective quality evaluation within a closed-loop optimisation architecture that simulates a realistic audio production signal chain. By parameterising production-related degradations and evaluating them with HAAQI metric, the system establishes a novel testbed for systematically analysing optimisers' performance in the high-dimensional parameter space. The following section describes the optimisation algorithms implemented within this framework.

5.3 Optimiser design

This section introduces three optimisation algorithms to explore the parameter space of audio degradation. Because the HAAQI objective is evaluated through a black-box perceptual model with no analytic gradient, optimisation relies on sampling-based methods with differing levels of adaptivity. MC sampling serves as a stochastic baseline, drawing random candidates within the defined parameter bounds. The GA introduces evolutionary search, enabling the optimiser to accumulate information across generations. An RL optimiser based on policy-gradient methods that learns a Gaussian sampling policy and updates its mean and variance using trajectory returns is a modern machine learning approach useful for this

optimisation problem. The following subsections describe each optimiser’s design, configuration, and expected behaviour.

5.3.1 Monte Carlo sampling (MC)

This section describes the MC optimiser framework, used as a baseline for evaluating optimisation performance.

The MC optimiser serves as a baseline stochastic search method for parameter exploration without using gradient or model-based guidance. In each generation, the optimiser randomly samples 60 candidate solutions from a uniform distribution within the defined parameter bounds. The search space is configured according to the project environment, with 7 dimensions for a single track or 28 dimensions for a track mix (see Table 9). Each candidate vector \mathbf{p} is rendered through the degradator to generate a degraded signal using $Deg(\mathbf{p})$ and obtain a positive objective score F using the equation:

$$F = 1 - HAAQI(Deg(\mathbf{p})) \quad \text{Equation 5.2}$$

The highest-scoring candidate from each generation is retained and logged, and after 10 iterations, the optimiser exports the best results across all steps.

5.3.2 Genetic algorithms (GA)

GAs are population-based optimisation methods inspired by evolutionary processes. This section describes their implementation within the proposed ML-based degradator framework and explores the parameter spaces of degradation.

5.3.2.1 Overview

The GA is employed for its effectiveness in exploring complex, multi-dimensional, and non-linear search spaces [83]. In each iteration, new parameter permutations are generated through selection, crossover, and mutation. Each permutation comprises degradation genes representing individual parameters, and fitness is evaluated using the HAAQI score. The

population evolves iteratively toward configurations that cause greater perceptual degradation, as measured by HAAQI.

5.3.2.2 Iteration procedure

Each iteration produces a new population of degradation vectors \mathbf{p} , where each parameter contributes to a parameter of the degradation model $Deg(\mathbf{p})$. The vector is 7 dimensions for a single track or 28 dimensions for a track mix. Each parameter is encoded as a floating-point value with a 0.01 precision step size, with the range list in Table 9. The population size is set to 60 per run, with 10 generations. The initial population is randomly generated.

In each iteration, the degrader creates an audio sample from the degradation vector, passes it to the evaluator module, and returns the fitness value. The fitness return uses Equation 5.2 to align the GA's maximisation objective. In each generation, two parents with the highest fitness scores are selected to produce offspring via uniform crossover, in which each gene is randomly inherited from either parent with equal probability, ensuring balanced genetic mixing and maintaining population diversity. In the next generation, the top-performing individual is retained through an elitist mechanism. The mutation is responsible for the offspring's gene change.

Mutation is applied to offspring genes at a 30% rate, meaning that 30% of the genes are randomly altered during inheritance. Under the random mutation strategy, new values are sampled uniformly from each parameter's defined range, rather than perturbed around the existing value. The GA is implemented using the PyGAD [152] library, which supports uniform crossover, random mutation, and optional parallel evaluation. Key configuration parameters are listed in Table 11.

Table 11 Configuration on the GA

Parameter	Value
Population size	60
Generations	10
Mutation Rate	30%
Mutation Type	Random
Crossover type	Uniform
Selection	steady-state selection (2 top as parents)
Elitism	1 top individual retained
Step size	0.01

5.3.3 Reinforcement learning (RL)

This section formulates the degradator mixing task as a reinforcement learning problem. It describes the neural network design, key components (policy, reward, loss function), and training procedure used to optimise the degradation parameter.

5.3.3.1 Overview

The study also applied an RL optimiser for audio parameter search. The evaluator is treated as a black-box function, so the RL agent receives only the HAAQI reward produced after taking an action in the degradator environments, without analytic gradient information.

Unlike MC and GA, which rely on random sampling or population-based evolution, the RL optimiser updates a learned policy based on cumulative rewards from past interactions. This allows the agent to gradually shift its sampling actions toward regions of the parameter space that have historically produced lower HAAQI scores, providing a directed, experience-driven search.

5.3.3.2 Environment design

Figure 18 Reinforcement learning interaction loop for the audio degradation mixing environment.

Figure 18 illustrates the agent–environment interaction loop used in reinforcement learning. At each step t , the agent observes the current state s_t then outputs an action a_t , which corresponds to a continuous adjustment of the audio degradator parameters. The environment applies the adjustment and renders the degraded audio, and produces the reward:

$$R_{t+1} = 1 - HAAQI(Deg(s_t)) \quad \text{Equation 5.3}$$

It then returns the next state s_{t+1} to the agent. The agent then updates its policy based on this feedback signal. This process is repeated for 30 steps to form a sub-episode. 2 sub-episodes are collected per update, and the whole training cycle is repeated across 10 iterations, matching the evaluation budget used by the GA and MC optimisers.

5.3.3.3 Policy network and agent setup

The policy network is built on the ActorDistributionNetwork from TF-agents [153], a TensorFlow Agents library for RL. It maps the current state s_t to a Gaussian distribution over continuous actions. The network consists of two fully connected layers, each with 256 units. The experiment applied a stochastic Gaussian policy with an output layer, implemented using a custom NormalProjectionNetwork derived from [12]. It generates a mean and standard deviation of the distribution:

$$\pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_{\theta}(s_t), \sigma_{\theta}(s_t)^2) \quad \text{Equation 5.4}$$

Both mean vectors $\mu_{\theta}(s_t)$ and a standard deviation vector $\sigma_{\theta}(s_t)$ are learned from the input state. The action space is bounded in $[-I, I]$, to fit the Gaussian distribution, the Tanh activation function is selected over ReLU. In the preliminary experiment, the unbounded upper bound of the ReLU creates an imbalance during training, leading to gradient explosion.

5.3.3.4 Learning objective and loss function

The RL agent is trained using a standard policy-gradient objective, which aims to maximise the expected return:

$$J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{\theta}} \left[\sum_t R_t \right] \quad \text{Equation 5.5}$$

The expected return is estimated using the gradient of the objective:

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \mathbb{E} [\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t) (R_t - \bar{R})] \quad \text{Equation 5.6}$$

where R_t is the episode reward and \bar{R} is the baseline for variance reduction. During the neural network weights θ update, the agent tries to push consistently to a higher R_t through the policy updates from the Gaussian policy $\pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t)$. With additional regularisation terms, the total loss function include:

$$L = -J + \alpha \|\theta\|^2 + \beta H(\pi_{\theta}) \quad \text{Equation 5.7}$$

where the first term $-J$ is the negative return (because the optimiser minimises loss). The term $\|\theta\|^2$ corresponds to L2 weight regularisation, which penalises large policy parameters, prevents the policy from producing large Gaussian means or variances on action, causing the state to explode. Entropy $H(\pi_\theta)$ encourages exploration by preventing the policy from becoming too narrow early in training. The coefficients α and β control the strength of these regularisers.

5.3.3.5 Training procedure

In each training cycle, the agent first interacts with the environment to collect a sub-episode of trajectories. These trajectories are stored in a replay buffer for convenient batching. The policy gradient is then computed using TensorFlow’s GradientTape, and the network parameters are updated using the Adam optimiser with a constant learning rate. Gradient clipping is applied to keep the updates stable. After each update, metrics such as entropy, action statistics, and reward are recorded to monitor how the policy balances exploration and exploitation over time.

Table 12 Configuration of Reinforcement Learning

Parameter	Value
Sub-episode length	30
Total sub-episodes per update	2
Policy Network Architecture	(256, 256)
Learning rate Initial	0.001
Gradient clipping (per-var)	30
L2 regularisation parameter(α)	0.0001
Entropy bonus(β)	0.01

5.3.4 Summary

The three optimisation methods, MC, GA and RL, represent progressively more informed approaches to exploring the audio degradation parameter space. All optimisers operate over the same degradation parameter space ($7-D$ or $28-D$) and within the specified degradation

parameter ranges. The HAAQI score serves as the fundamental objective/fitness function for all optimiser calculations. All runs under matched iteration budgets with 60 (candidates per iteration) \times 10 (iterations). All attempts to find a parameter configuration that contributes to the most degraded audio quality.

MC optimiser applied using uniform random sampling with no memory requirements; each iteration is statistically identical. GA is a population-based optimiser that produces offspring via selection, crossover, and mutation. Fitness determines parent selection and retains the top individuals as feedback. The RL optimiser's actions are drawn from a learned Gaussian policy, and the policy is updated using rewards across trajectories. The agent increases the probability of actions yielding over-average rewards. Compared with the GA's exploration source in mutation inheritance and crossover, the RL explores using a Gaussian centred on reward regions via gradient-driven movement. In this way, to expand the search range and mitigate the potential early convergence in the classical optimiser.

During the performance, MC is expected to behave as an uninformed random search and to show no measurable improvement across iterations. The GA, in contrast, exhibits noticeably more structured behaviour. However, the strategy might introduce biases toward the previous generation, limiting its exploration region. Finally, in RL, instead of relying on a population, it continuously adjusts the mean and variance of its Gaussian policy based on trajectory returns. Thereby, it deliberately shifts its sampling distribution toward high-reward areas. More akin to searching for the solution rather than a random exploration.

5.4 Results and conclusion

To understand how the optimisers shape degradation outcomes, this section examines the datasets of parameter configurations identified across the Speech, Music, and Mix datasets. The analysis focuses on the outcomes that maximise the degradation scenarios, supported by spectrogram comparisons and configuration tables. This provides a foundation for

interpreting the patterns observed in the optimiser outputs before moving to the more detailed CODEC-specific analysis in the following chapter.

All three optimisers were run under the same conditions to ensure a fair comparison. Each method explored the identical degradation parameter space ($7-D$ for single-track and $28-D$ for four-track mixes) and was evaluated using the HAAQI score as the objective. The optimisation budget was matched across methods. The same datasets, random seeds, audio conditions, and parameter bounds are used during the experiment.

5.4.1 Per-Iteration behaviour

Across all three tasks, Speech (Figure 19), Music (Figure 20), and Mix (Figure 21), the average per-iteration curves reveal the characteristic optimisation behaviour of each method. MC remains flat throughout most iterations, with only minor fluctuations. This is expected because MC samples candidates independently at each step and therefore does not accumulate information that would lead to systematic improvement.

GA shows a clear upward trend, typically improving rapidly in the early iterations before slowing. This pattern reflects the standard GA dynamics: crossover provides early gains by recombining valuable parameter sets, while reduced population diversity in later iterations leads to slower progress and occasional early plateaus due to premature convergence.

RL consistently begins with a higher initial score than both MC and GA and converges more smoothly. The higher starting point arises because the policy network outputs moderate parameter values at initialisation, which tend to produce reasonable degradation levels, whereas the GA and MC randomly sample. As training progresses, the policy benefits from continuous updates to its gradients based on the reward history, enabling RL to gradually refine its actions. This results in steady improvement and earlier stabilisation compared with the more stochastic search processes of MC and GA.

Overall, RL reaches the strongest performance by the final iteration across almost all datasets (Table 13), GA improves reliably but can become trapped in suboptimal regions, and

MC provides no directional convergence due to its random search strategy. However, in the Mix project group, GA and RL achieve very similar final values, and both retain visible upward trends by the last iteration. The Beatles example even shows GA slightly outperforming RL. However, because the Mix task has a substantially larger parameter space (28 dimensions), these results likely reflect incomplete convergence rather than a meaningful performance reversal. Both optimisers appear to be still exploring high-value regions, and additional iterations would be required to determine their asymptotic behaviour.

Table 13 Maximum optimisation score ($1 - \text{HAAQI}$) achieved by GA, MC, and RL across all Speech, Music, and Mix examples(The Max value list with bold).

<i>Examples</i>	<i>Final Result(GA)</i>	<i>Final Result(MC)</i>	<i>Final Result(RL)</i>
Speech(Average)	0.489	0.389	0.502
English Speech	0.539	0.417	0.541
German Speech	0.525	0.456	0.538
Speech with Music	0.403	0.294	0.427
Music(Average)	0.385	0.343	0.406
Hendrix	0.415	0.347	0.433
Rock	0.371	0.318	0.382
Punk	0.305	0.301	0.324
Grunge	0.434	0.406	0.47
Britpop	0.398	0.343	0.421
Multi - Mix(Average)	0.588	0.501	0.593
Reggae	0.628	0.531	0.629
Country1	0.634	0.558	0.647
Disco	0.569	0.479	0.584
Beatles	0.522	0.437	0.513

Figure 19 Per-iteration best performance curves (1 - HAAQI) of MC, GA, and RL, averaged over all Speech examples.

Figure 20 Per-iteration best performance curves (1 - HAAQI) of MC, GA, and RL, averaged over all Music examples.

Figure 21 Per-iteration best performance curves (1-HAAQI reward) of MC, GA, and RL, averaged over all multi-track project examples.

5.4.2 Performance distribution of top 25% data across optimisers

For this experiment, the optimiser must not only identify strong degradation cases but also cover a broad region of the degradation space, because the later stages of the study examine how different parameter configurations influence CODEC behaviour. To support this, all candidate evaluations generated during optimisation were recorded. The coefficient of variation ($CV = \text{standard deviation}/\text{mean}$) indicates the spread of the high-performing region: a higher CV reflects greater variability relative to the average score.

Figure 22 – Figure 24 show violin plots of the top 25% highest-performing results for each dataset category, with the corresponding summary statistics in Table 14 – Table 16. Each violin illustrates the density, distribution, and median of the top quartile of HAAQI-based reward values.

The top-25% distributions show behavioural differences among the three optimisers. GA consistently produces the narrowest violins and the lowest CV values, indicating that its high-

performing solutions are tightly clustered. This reflects GA’s tendency to concentrate around a small region of the search space once selection pressure becomes dominant; MC shows moderately wider distributions, as expected from a method that samples randomly but can still stumble upon diverse high-scoring candidates; RL exhibits the widest distributions and highest CV values across most datasets; it captures a broader range of high-degradation cases, most beneficial for the exploration.

However, a key trade-off in optimisation is between exploration and exploitation; wide CV does not automatically imply superior exploration, and high variance can also arise from policy instability or reward sensitivity [84]. The RL trajectories exhibit smooth per-iteration improvement and consistently high mean and median values (Table 14–Table 16), and the violin plots do not show fragmented or irregular distributions. The wider CV mainly reflects functional diversity in high-performing solutions rather than optimisation noise.

Table 14 Summary statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation) of the top 25% optimisation scores for GA, MC, and RL across the Speech examples (The Max CV value list with bold).

Examples	Optimiser	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Std</i>	<i>CV</i>
English Speech	GA	0.4972	0.492	0.0181	0.036
	MC	0.3327	0.327	0.0271	0.081
	RL	0.3831	0.377	0.0471	0.123
German Speech	GA	0.4892	0.488	0.0085	0.017
	MC	0.4078	0.4045	0.0167	0.041
	RL	0.4177	0.412	0.0362	0.087
Speech with Music	GA	0.3746	0.372	0.0094	0.025
	MC	0.2649	0.264	0.0099	0.037
	RL	0.327	0.32	0.0315	0.096

Figure 22 Top-25% performance distributions ($1 - \text{HAAQI}$ reward) for the optimiser across Music categories. Violins are ordered left to right as GA, MC, and RL.

Table 15 Summary statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation) of the top 25% optimisation scores for GA, MC, and RL across the Music datasets (The Max CV value list with bold).

Examples	Optimiser	Mean	Median	Std	CV
Britpop	GA	0.3758	0.374	0.0084	0.022
	MC	0.2795	0.275	0.0172	0.062
	RL	0.3319	0.328	0.0298	0.09
Grunge	GA	0.4123	0.411	0.0079	0.019
	MC	0.2928	0.2805	0.0353	0.121
	RL	0.3799	0.37	0.028	0.074
Hendrix	GA	0.3904	0.388	0.011	0.028
	MC	0.2797	0.273	0.0198	0.071
	RL	0.3354	0.33	0.0261	0.078
Punk	GA	0.289	0.289	0.0056	0.019
	MC	0.2793	0.278	0.0087	0.031
	RL	0.2627	0.261	0.0194	0.074
Rock	GA	0.3447	0.342	0.0093	0.027
	MC	0.246	0.241	0.0201	0.082
	RL	0.3026	0.2935	0.0254	0.084

Figure 23 Top-25% performance distributions (1-HAAQI reward) for the optimiser across Music categories. Violins are ordered left to right as GA, MC, and RL.

Table 16 Summary statistics (mean, median, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation) of the top 25% optimisation scores for GA, MC, and RL across the multi-track project datasets (The Max CV value list with bold).

Examples	Optimiser	Mean	Median	Std	CV
Beatles	GA	0.5084	0.509	0.0065	0.013
	MC	0.3445	0.3369	0.0223	0.065
	RL	0.4125	0.4062	0.0312	0.076
Country1	GA	0.6241	0.6254	0.0044	0.007
	MC	0.4507	0.4413	0.0266	0.059
	RL	0.5258	0.5187	0.0256	0.049
Disco	GA	0.5128	0.5148	0.0132	0.026
	MC	0.3771	0.3712	0.0226	0.06
	RL	0.47	0.4632	0.0355	0.076
Reggae	GA	0.5993	0.5989	0.0089	0.015
	MC	0.4159	0.4078	0.0273	0.066
	RL	0.5284	0.5204	0.0338	0.064

Figure 24 Top-25% performance distributions ($1 - \text{HAAQI}$ reward) for the optimiser across multi-track project categories. Violins are ordered left to right as GA, MC, and RL.

5.4.3 Degradation trend observation

To illustrate the degradation behaviour, the most degraded examples identified by the optimisers were examined for both speech (Table 17) and music (Table 18). Across these cases, the worst degradation consistently corresponds to low hum and hiss SNR values, high clipping levels, and strong DRC settings, specifically a high ratio combined with a high threshold, and short attack and release times. These configurations introduce noticeable distortion, which collectively stress the CODEC and amplify perceptual degradation (Figure 26 and Figure 28).

Speech examples generally reach higher degradation scores than music. This is likely due to the acoustic structure of speech: it has a limited dynamic range and distinct formant bands, so added noise or distortion stands out clearly (Figure 25 – Figure 26). In contrast, dense broadband genres such as punk provide stronger energetic masking across the spectrum, allowing some artefacts to be partially obscured by existing spectral content (Figure 27 – Figure 28). However, under the degradation conditions in Figure 28, the gap at high

frequency is enlarged due to sufficient bit allocation, indicating greater difficulty for the CODEC.

In the multi-track dataset, the larger parameter space (*28 dimensions*) allows more extreme degradation configurations to emerge. GA and RL produce similar worst-case patterns; this similar performance suggests that both optimisers are still exploring rather than fully converged. A more detailed analysis of parameter interactions and CODEC behaviour is discussed in Chapter 6.

Figure 25 STFT spectrogram of the reference 64 kbps MP3 audio of English speech (2048-point FFT, 75% overlap)

Figure 26 STFT spectrogram of the most degraded audio of English speech (2048-point FFT, 75% overlap)

Figure 27 STFT spectrogram of the reference 64 kbps MP3 audio of Punk Music (2048-point FFT, 75% overlap)

Figure 28 STFT spectrogram of the most degraded audio of Punk Music (2048-point FFT, 75% overlap)

Table 17 Parameter configurations corresponding to the worst-case degradation examples identified by the GA and RL optimisers for the Speech Examples

Examples	Optimiser	Hum	Hiss	CL	Thre	Ratio	Attk	Release
English Speech	RL	15.51	30.06	1.9	-14.24	8.52	0.14	56.5
	GA	15	30	1.2	-15	8.98	0.1	50
German Speech	RL	15	30	2	-15	6.17	0.1	50
	GA	17.28	30.09	1.94	-13.99	9.89	0.21	65.96
Speech With Music	RL	15	30	2	-15	10	0.1	50
	GA	15.13	32.17	1.96	-14.24	9.15	0.27	52.17

Table 18 Parameter configurations corresponding to the worst-case degradation examples identified by the GA and RL optimisers for the Music Examples

Examples	Optimiser	Hum	Hiss	CL	Thre	Ratio	Attk	Release
Hendrix	RL	15	30	1.99	-15	10	0.1	50
	GA	15.93	30.23	1.87	-14.94	6.91	0.1	63.31
Rock	RL	15	30	1.55	-15	7.72	0.1	50
	GA	16.4	30.27	1.94	-13.88	9.76	0.12	54.76
Punk	RL	15	30	1.74	-15	9.3	0.1	50
	GA	15.04	30.89	1.87	-14.31	9.81	0.99	79.92
Grunge	RL	15	30	1.39	-15	8.27	0.1	50
	GA	17.35	31.25	1.81	-13.96	9.06	0.13	71.76
Britpop	RL	15	30	2	-15	10	0.1	50
	GA	15.63	30.43	1.85	-13.76	9.54	0.46	52.71

5.4.4 Summary

Across all audio examples, RL consistently achieves the highest degradation scores and maintains the broadest spread of high-performing solutions, making it the most suitable optimiser for this project’s objective of capturing diverse degradation regions for stressing the

test CODEC. GA provides competitive results but often converges to narrower regions of the parameter space, whereas MC performs as expected for a purely random baseline.

Speech samples generally exhibit higher levels of perceptual degradation than music. This is likely because music signals have denser spectral and temporal structures; for example, highly distorted genres such as punk already contain significant nonlinear distortion, making them more resilient to additional degradations. In contrast, multi-track projects operate in higher-dimensional parameter spaces, producing more complex interference effects and substantially lower quality scores. GA and RL yield similar worst-case degradation patterns, suggesting the parameter space is not fully converged.

5.5 Conclusion

This chapter first presents the architecture of a novel ML-based degradator framework that employs the objective metric HAAQI to guide optimisers toward regions of the degradation parameter space that yield both high-performing and diverse solution. The framework integrates controlled audio degradation, perceptual coding, and objective quality evaluation within a closed-loop optimisation architecture, simulating a realistic audio production signal chain. This design establishes a controlled testbed for systematically analysing how optimisation algorithms perform in response to non-gradient analytic metric feedback in an audio degradation space.

Then three optimisation algorithms: MC, GA, and RL, are evaluated within this framework. All optimisers were assessed under identical experimental conditions, sharing the same degradation parameter space, evaluation budget, and objective function, thereby enabling a fair comparison across speech, music, and multi-track project content.

A key purpose is to identify the optimiser, which can find both the maximum-degradation cases and cover a broad range of the high-degradation space, since a later study aims to

analyse how different parameter settings interact with perceptual CODECs in an optimiser driving system. This makes search diversity as important as peak performance.

MC served as an uninformed baseline, showing no consistent improvement. GA showed clear optimisation progress but tended to collapse into a narrow region of solutions, limiting diversity and consistency agree with [84]. RL provided the best balance: it achieved the highest degradation scores overall and maintained the widest spread of high-performing configurations, supporting previous findings [12]. This broader coverage reflects stable exploration rather than noise and is valuable for studying codec sensitivity under varied conditions. Analysis of the worst-case examples revealed consistent degradation patterns, low SNR from hum and hiss, high clipping, and aggressive DRC processing. It also highlighted that speech is generally more vulnerable to degradation than dense music because of its spectral and temporal density. In the multi-track tasks, both GA and RL remained exploratory, demonstrating the increased complexity of multi-source interactions.

Overall, RL is selected as the primary optimiser for subsequent investigation. Its combination of strong worst-case identification and broad high-performance coverage makes it best aligned with the project's goal of systematically analysing CODEC behaviour under diverse degradation conditions. The next chapter focuses on mixing specific samples and examines how RL-generated degradation patterns interact with various perceptual CODECs, revealing their sensitivities and failure modes.

Chapter 6 Experiment III: effect of degradation on different CODECs

6.1 Introduction

Audio degradation introduced during production mixes with the music content and is processed by the CODEC, which can further degrade the music's quality. Conventional CODECs (MP3, AAC) and neural CODECs (EnCodec) rely on fundamentally different encoding principles. It remains unclear whether these differences affect the relative importance of applied degradation types or primarily change their perceived severity. Existing studies typically assess CODEC performance in isolation or under clean conditions, providing limited insight into CODEC robustness within realistically degraded audio workflows.

To address Research Question 3 (RQ3): Which types of degradation exert the most significant negative impact on perceived audio quality, and how does this impact differ between conventional and neural CODECs under degraded conditions? This chapter presents two complementary experiments. Experiment A applies a classical psychoacoustic analysis grounded in conventional CODEC modelling to examine perceptual responses to individual degradation processes. Experiment B adopts an inverse, optimisation-driven approach, using a reinforcement-learning optimiser guided by the HAAQI metric to systematically identify degradation configurations that maximise perceptual impairment. This stress-testing strategy enables controlled exploration of CODEC sensitivity across a high-dimensional degradation space without reliance on a reference mix. This stress-testing strategy is essential for collecting the data to examine the perceptual sensitivity of CODEC across common production degradation types. Together, these experiments characterise degradation-specific vulnerabilities across CODEC architectures and provide empirical evidence of which production errors pose the greatest perceptual risk in practical audio workflows.

6.2 Method

This section presents the methodology used to investigate how different audio CODECs respond to controlled signal and optimiser-driven degradations. The approach combines signal-level psychoacoustic analysis with optimisation-based degradation exploration, enabling both mechanistic interpretation and large-scale behavioural comparison across conventional and neural CODECs.

6.2.1 Audio test material and signal categories

Two categories of audio material are employed, corresponding to the objectives of the experiments, respectively.

For Experiment A, three types of signals are used: a deterministic test tone, a speech example, and a music excerpt. These signals allow inspection of CODEC behaviour under increasingly complex spectral and temporal structures. For each signal, both clean and degraded versions are generated for comparison.

The degraded versions are created using the worst-case degradation configuration identified in Chapter 5, which includes low signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) for hum and hiss, high clipping levels, and DRC processing. The compression settings include a high ratio, a low threshold, and short attack and release times. The specific parameter values are summarised in Table 19.

The test tone signal is 4 seconds long and consists of discrete frequencies at 100 Hz, 500 Hz, 800 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, and 5 kHz, as illustrated in Figure 29. In addition, the same English speech sample from “What to Listen For” [7] and pre-mixed music excerpt (“Brit Pop”) from [147] used in the previous chapter are retained.

Table 19 Degradation configuration for a single audio

Degradation Configuration	Hum(dB)	Hiss(dB)	CL(%)	Thre(dB)	Ratio	Attk(ms)	Release(ms)
	15.0	30.06	2	-15	10	0.1	50

Figure 29 The spectrum of the test tone signal

For Experiment B, a set of full music mixes is selected from the MUSDB18 dataset [147]. These mixed projects represent realistic production scenarios and are used to analyse CODEC behaviour under optimiser-driven degradation. Each mix consists of four tracks (drums, vocals, bass, and other), and degradation is applied independently to each track during degradator processing. The parameter ranges scope for the optimiser, along with the values associated with the worst perceived quality and selected examples, are shown in Table 21.

Table 20 The audio mix dataset for testing

Example Title	Pronoun	Original Duration (seconds)
Reggae	Mix_RE	17
Britpop	Mix_BR	33
Disco	Mix_DI	114
Beatles	Mix_BE	33
Country1	Mix_CO1	32
Country2	Mix_CO2	16
80sRock	Mix_80R	34
Hendrix	Mix_HD	18
Grunge	Mix_GR	38
Punk	Mix_PU	26
Rock	Mix_RO	12
Rockabilly	Mix_RA	23

Table 21 Parameter Ranges and Worst-Quality Conditions in the Optimisation Experiment

Parameter	Lowest range	Highest range	Value associated with worst quality
Signal to Hum noise(dB)	15	60	15
Signal to Hiss noise(dB)	30	60	30
Clipping(%)	0	2	2
Compressor Threshold(dB)	-15	0	-15
Ratio	1	10	10
Compressor attack(ms)	0.1	10	0.1
Compressor release(ms)	50	300	50

6.2.2 CODEC architectures under study

This section outlines the CODEC architectures examined in this thesis, contrasting conventional CODECs (MP3 and AAC), which rely on psychoacoustic models and transform-based bit allocation, with a neural CODEC (EnCodec) that learns a generative latent representation directly from data. This distinction motivates the subsequent experimental analysis of their perceptual behaviour under degradation

6.2.2.1 Conventional CODECs (MP3 and AAC)

Two conventional perceptual audio CODECs are examined in this study: MP3 and AAC. Both CODECs follow a similar transform-based encoding-decoding pipeline, comprising time–frequency analysis, psychoacoustic modelling, quantisation, and entropy coding. Detailed descriptions of their internal structures are provided in 2.2.2.

The key component governing audio quality in both CODECs is the psychoacoustic model (see Figure 30), which determines how quantisation noise may be shaped and distributed while remaining perceptually acceptable. For each frame, the input signal is analysed in the frequency domain using a filter bank and modified discrete cosine transform (MDCT). The psychoacoustic model estimates masking thresholds by distinguishing between tonal and noise-like components and accounting for masking effects across neighbouring frequency bands. These thresholds are combined with the absolute hearing threshold to form a global masking threshold.

Figure 30 Overview of the psychoacoustic model used in conventional CODECs (MP3/AAC), showing signal analysis, masking threshold construction, SMR computation, and their role in guiding bit allocation and quantisation.

Based on this threshold, the CODEC computes the Signal-to-Mask Ratio (SMR) for each frequency region. Higher SMR value regions are more likely to produce audible distortion and therefore require greater bit allocation, while lower SMR value regions permit more aggressive quantisation. Bit allocation is performed iteratively to meet the target bitrate while keeping quantisation noise below the estimated masking threshold.

In the experiments, MP3 encoding is performed with the LAME encoder [144], and AAC encoding uses the Fraunhofer FDK AAC [154] implementation. Both CODECs operate at a fixed bitrate of 64 kbps, and all encoded signals are decoded using FFmpeg to a sampling rate of 48 kHz.

6.2.2.2 Neural CODEC (EnCodec)

Neural CODECs represent a recent shift in audio compression, exemplified by Meta's EnCodec [155]. These systems achieve high perceptual quality, exceeding that of conventional CODECs, at extremely low bitrates (e.g., 6 kbps). Unlike conventional CODECs, which rely on hand-designed transforms and explicit psychoacoustic models, neural CODECs learn a compressed representation directly from data. As a result,

reconstruction is performed through a learned generative process, potentially introducing behaviours not observed in analytic transform-based CODECs.

EnCodec follows an encoder–quantiser–decoder architecture in Figure 31. A convolutional neural network encoder maps the input waveform to a latent representation, analogous to the analysis stage in conventional CODECs based on filter banks and MDCT. Quantisation constrains these latent features to discrete codebooks, with the bitrate determined by the number of available codewords, in contrast to the coefficient quantisation used in conventional CODECs. The decoder reconstructs audio from the quantised latent representation and operates as a generative model rather than a deterministic inverse transform. Detailed descriptions of its training process are provided in 2.2.3.

EnCodec was selected as a representative neural CODEC because it is the most widely adopted and well-documented neural audio CODEC currently available, and because its design allows controlled, reproducible evaluation within the constraints of this study. The official EnCodec implementation from Meta is used, employing a model trained at 48 kHz with a target bitrate of 24 kHz.

Figure 31 Architecture of the neural CODEC (EnCodec), consisting of a convolutional encoder, vector-quantised latent representation, and decoder, trained with multi-scale discriminators and waveform/spectral loss terms to reconstruct audio at low bitrates. Excerpt from [5]

6.2.3 Usage of psychoacoustic analysis metrics

In experiment A, the study introduces psychoacoustic measures derived from masking theory to analyse the CODEC behaviour. Providing a perceptually motivated description of how signal energy, masking thresholds, and coding noise interact between conventional and neural CODECs. The focus here is on how masking-based metrics are computed and interpreted for comparative analysis.

In experiment B, the objective evaluator metric HAAQI quantifies the perceptual degradation level between the reference and degraded signals across different CODECs. HAAQI is a metric that produces a normalised score between 0 and 1, where higher values indicate better perceived quality.

6.2.3.1 Masking Threshold and Signal-to-Mask Ratio (SMR)

The masking threshold represents the perceptual audibility limit of a signal in each frequency band and is derived from a standard psychoacoustic analysis of the reference signal. In this study, masking thresholds are used as an analytical baseline to assess perceptual relevance across the spectrum.

The Signal-to-Mask Ratio (SMR) is defined as the difference between the signal level and the corresponding masking threshold:

$$SMR(f) = SPL(f) - T_{mask}(f) \quad \text{Equation 6.1}$$

SMR indicates a spectral component that is either perceptually significant ($SMR > 0$ dB) or likely to be masked ($SMR < 0$ dB) across different frequency bins. In this study, SMR is employed to examine how different CODECs preserve or suppress spectral regions under clean and degraded conditions.

To support the interpretation of masking-related behaviour, the MP3_encoder¹ reference implementation is consulted to examine the psychoacoustic model defined in ISO/IEC 11172-3, Annex D.1 [40].

6.2.3.2 Noise-to-Mask Ratio (NMR)

The Noise-to-Mask Ratio (NMR) quantifies the audibility of distortion by comparing the noise between the reference and coded signals against the masking threshold of the reference signal.

$$NMR(f) = N(f) - T_{mask}(f) \quad \text{Equation 6.2}$$

NMR values indicate whether the distortion and artefacts remain perceptually masked ($NMR < 0 \text{ dB}$) or become potentially audible artefacts ($NMR > 0 \text{ dB}$). Aggregated NMR values are used as an objective indicator of the severity of perceptual degradation.

In this study, NMR serves as a comparative metric, consistent with its use in perceptual assessment frameworks such as PEAQ, enabling an objective comparison between conventional and neural CODECs under varying audio conditions.

6.2.3.3 Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index (HAAQI)

Based on the results of Chapter 4, HAAQI demonstrated the highest consistency with subjective ratings across a range of music production degradation conditions. For this reason, it is selected as the primary quality evaluator in this study.

Within the optimisation framework, the CODEC module compresses the reference mix, and the quality evaluation module uses HAAQI to assess degradation by comparing the CODEC-compressed signal against its degraded counterpart. The resulting degradation score ($1 - \text{HAAQI score}$) guides the optimiser in exploring the solution space by reflecting changes in perceptual quality induced by both degradation and coding.

¹ <https://github.com/silviutroskot/MP3-encoder>

6.2.4 Experiment design

CODECs do not explicitly distinguish between desired signal components and externally introduced degradation. The compression bit rate for the conventional CODEC is set to 64 kbps, while EnCodec is set to 24 kbps. Consequently, CODEC behaviour under degraded inputs is not predefined and may differ between conventional and neural ones. Conventional CODECs rely on masking-driven bit allocation, whereas neural CODECs depend on data-driven representations learned during training. These differences motivate the use of two complementary experiments to examine CODECs behaviour.

6.2.4.1 Experiment A: controlled signal-based CODEC behaviour analysis

The first experiment analyses CODEC behaviour under controlled conditions using the psychoacoustic and masking-based measures defined in Section 6.2.3. Reference and compressed signals are compared based on their spectral energy distributions relative to masking across uniform frequency subbands ($24 \text{ kHz} / 32 = 750 \text{ Hz}$ per band).

Masking-related measures, including sound pressure level (SPL), masking thresholds, SMR, and NMR, are used to examine how different CODECs preserve perceptually relevant spectral content and how CODEC-induced distortion is distributed across the frequency spectrum.

6.2.4.2 Experiment B: Optimiser-Driven degradation exploration

The second experiment evaluates CODEC behaviour under complex degradation conditions generated by the machine learning (ML)-based degrator system. Unlike Experiment A (controlled signals), Experiment B samples a broad range of degradations across multi-tracks that arise during optimisation. The CODEC type is the only factor varied (MP3, AAC, and EnCodec); all other experimental conditions are held constant.

A reinforcement learning (RL) optimiser, derived from Chapter 5, searches a 28-*parameter* space on a fixed set of mixed music projects. For each candidate permutation, a degrator renders audio examples, then processed by a CODEC; HAAQI is computed by

comparing the CODEC-processed output with its degraded counterpart. Because multiple mix projects are evaluated per iteration, the optimiser uses the mean HAAQI across projects.

The reward is defined to favour worse quality (higher degradation) by inverting the mean HAAQI score:

$$R_{t+1} = 1 - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N HAAQI_i(x_t) \quad \text{Equation 6.3}$$

where x_t denotes the degradation configuration at the optimisation step t , i indexes the N mix projects (see Table 20) evaluated in that iteration, and $HAAQI_i(x_t) \in [0,1]$ is the HAAQI score obtained for the project i under configuration x_t

To mitigate premature convergence observed previously, the number of candidate solutions evaluated per iteration is increased from 30 to 270, and the optimiser is run for 10 iterations to collect degradation data for each CODEC.

6.3 Result analysis for experiment A

Experiment A examines CODEC behaviour under controlled signal and degradation conditions to establish a perceptual and psychoacoustic baseline. By analysing NMR alongside spectral energy, masking thresholds, and SMR, the experiment compares conventional CODECs with a neural CODEC across test tones, speech, and music. The aim is to characterise how different CODEC architectures handle distortion, masking, and spectral allocation, and to provide interpretative context for the optimiser-driven analysis presented in the subsequent experiment.

6.3.1 NMR results analysis

The NMR is calculated by comparing the coded signal with the reference signal to quantify the amount of unmasked distortion. As shown in Table 22, conventional CODECs(MP3 and AAC) produce consistently negative values across all signal types,

indicating that most coding noise remains perceptually masked. AAC achieves lower NMR than MP3 for clean test tones, reflecting more effective noise shaping for simple, stationary signals.

Under degraded conditions, NMR increases for test tones and speech, as additional high-frequency distortion becomes less effectively masked. In contrast, music signals exhibit relatively stable NMR values, as their dense spectral content provides stronger inherent masking, limiting the perceptual impact of added degradation.

The EnCodec exhibits higher NMR values than conventional CODECs, including positive NMR for test tones, indicating increased unmasked distortion relative to the reference. This behaviour is consistent with its generative reconstruction approach, which does not explicitly apply psychoacoustic noise shaping and is more sensitive to reference deviation, particularly for simple signals.

Table 22 NMR for test tones, speech, and music signals encoded with MP3 (64 kbps), AAC (64 kbps), and a neural CODEC (24 kbps), reported under clean and degraded conditions. Lower negative NMR values indicate better noise masking and lower perception distortion.

CODEC	NMR of Test Tone(dBFS)		NMR of Speech(dBFS)		NMR of Music(dBFS)	
	Clean	Deg	Clean	Deg	Clean	Deg
MP3(64kbps)	-23.3	-8.2	-15.4	-7.2	-8.8	-8.1
AAC(64kbps)	-34	-8.1	-16.9	-7.7	-8.7	-8.2
EnCodec(24kbps)	10.2	3.2	-2	-3.4	-4.6	-4.7

6.3.2 Spectral and psychoacoustic behaviour analysis

This subsection analyses how CODECs modify spectral energy, masking thresholds, and SMR across different signal types and degradation conditions. By jointly examining SPL, masking, and SMR, the analysis explains CODEC-specific behaviour and provides context for the NMR results presented in the previous subsection.

6.3.2.1 General trends

Across all signal types, conventional CODECs (MP3 and AAC) exhibit behaviour consistent with psychoacoustic principles. In low- and mid-subbands, where signal energy is concentrated, masking is strong. Whereas their SPL, masking, and SMR closely follow the reference signal. Differences between MP3 and AAC are mainly observed in high-frequency transition regions: AAC shows an earlier and more stable spectral roll-off, while MP3 exhibits greater variability in this region.

The neural CODEC demonstrates a distinct behaviour pattern. While it broadly follows the reference trend, it frequently exhibits larger deviations and greater variance, even in low- and mid-subbands, particularly for clean signals. Masking calculations do not constrain these deviations relative to the reference. Consequently, the neural CODEC does not consistently align its reconstructed energy with the reference masking structure.

Across all signals, the high-frequency region is the primary area where CODEC behaviour diverge. Conventional ones tend to suppress energy when SMR becomes negative, reflecting perceptual discarding guided by masking thresholds. In contrast, the neural CODEC more often preserves or regenerates energy beyond these regions, resulting in more spectral extent, even if it is not accurate. Error bars across the figures indicate that AAC generally exhibits the most stable behaviour, MP3 shows moderate instability in transition bands, and EnCodec exhibits variability depending on the signal, consistent with a generative reconstruction approach.

6.3.2.2 Test Tone Signal

Relative to the general trends, the test tone highlights CODEC behaviour under highly controlled spectral conditions (Figure 32 and Figure 33). MP3 and AAC closely track the reference in low- and mid-subbands and apply strong high-frequency suppression under degradation. AAC again exhibits an earlier and more stable roll-off than MP3, reflecting robust perceptual bit allocation under severe noise and clipping.

The EnCodec shows larger SPL deviations and higher variance under clean conditions, despite the simplicity of the signal. Under degradation, it retains more high-frequency energy than MP3 and AAC, indicating less aggressive spectral suppression.

Masking curves for MP3 and AAC closely match the reference, whereas the EnCodec exhibits lower and more variable masking levels. SMR results show that MP3 and AAC reliably reproduce perceptually relevant mid-frequency subbands under degradation, while the neural CODEC often produces positive SMR in neighbouring subbands, indicating reconstructed energy beyond the masking threshold.

Overall, conventional CODECs preserve the test tone accurately while perceptually discarding high-frequency content, whereas the neural CODEC follows a general structure with a less constrained energy distribution.

Figure 32 Mean SPL, masking threshold, and SMR across the spectrum (750 Hz per subband) for a mixed pure-tone clean signal, comparing WAV, MP3, AAC, and EnCodec(nc) outputs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across frames.

Figure 33 Mean SPL, masking threshold, and SMR across the spectrum (750 Hz per subband) for a mixed pure-tone signal under the full degradation configuration, comparing WAV, MP3, AAC, and EnCodec(nc) outputs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across frames.

6.3.2.3 Speech Signal

For the speech signal in Figure 34 and Figure 35, MP3 and AAC closely follow the reference WAV in the low-subbands (*approximately index 0–10*), where speech energy is dominant. Above this range, both CODECs show reduced SPL compared to the reference, with attenuation becoming more pronounced under degradation. From around subband index 18, MP3 and AAC strongly suppress high-frequency energy, with AAC exhibiting an earlier and more stable roll-off. The EnCodec exceeds the reference level, with larger error bars in the middle-to-high subband range under clean conditions. Under degradation, its average SPL remains closer to the reference than those of MP3 and AAC, though its variability remains higher.

Masking curves for MP3 and AAC closely match the reference under both clean and degraded conditions, reflecting stable psychoacoustic behaviour. The EnCodec exhibits slightly shifted, more variable masking patterns, indicating modification of the local masking structure.

SMR results show positive values up to subband *index10* in the clean signal, with all CODECs tracking the reference. Beyond this region, MP3 and AAC follow the reference trend into negative SMR, while EnCodec retains more energy above the masking threshold. Under degradation, positive SMR extends to around subband *index 20*, after which AAC produces the most negative SMR, followed by MP3 and EnCodec.

Overall, conventional CODECs reliably preserve speech structure in the low and mid subbands and exhibit strong high-frequency suppression under degradation. The EnCodec follows the general trend, but with CODEC differences most evident in the upper subbands.

Figure 34 Mean SPL, masking threshold, and SMR across the spectrum (750 Hz per subband) for a clean speech signal, comparing WAV, MP3, AAC, and EnCodec(nc) outputs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across frames.

Figure 35 Mean SPL, masking threshold, and SMR across the spectrum (750 Hz per subband) for a speech signal under degradation configuration, comparing WAV, MP3, AAC, and EnCodec(nc) outputs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across frames.

6.3.2.4 Music Signal

For music signals, all CODECs closely follow the reference WAV in the low- and mid-subbands up to approximately subband *index 18*. Beyond this range, conventional CODECs apply high-frequency energy suppression, with the cut-off occurring later than in speech. AAC exhibits a stable roll-off, while MP3 shows greater variability during the transition. The EnCodec maintains a spectral shape closer to the reference across most subbands. It preserves high-frequency energy up to around subband *index 27*, with relatively low variability before the final drop.

Masking curves for all CODECs closely match the reference under both clean and degraded conditions, indicating that the hearing threshold dominates the high-frequency domain.

SMR trends mirror the SPL behaviour. Up to subband *index 18*, all CODECs exhibit similar SMR, indicating that perceptually relevant content is preserved. Beyond this range, AAC and MP3 rapidly transition to negative SMR, reflecting perceptual discarding of high-

frequency energy, with AAC showing the most stable behaviour. The EnCodec retains more high-frequency energy while maintaining comparable SMR levels.

Overall, conventional CODECs apply aggressive high-frequency suppression in music signals, with AAC showing greater stability than MP3. The EnCodec preserves more spectral structure in higher subbands, likely benefiting from training on music-dominant datasets.

Figure 36 Mean SPL, masking threshold, and SMR across the spectrum (750 Hz per subband) for a clean music signal, comparing WAV, MP3, AAC, and EnCodec(nc) outputs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across frames.

Figure 37 Mean SPL, masking threshold, and SMR across the spectrum (750 Hz per subband) for a music signal under degradation conditions, comparing WAV, MP3, AAC, and EnCodec(nc) outputs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across frames.

6.3.3 Result summary of experiment A

Experiment A analysed CODEC behaviour by combining NMR with spectral and psychoacoustic measures (SPL, masking, and SMR) across different signal types and degradation conditions.

Conventional CODECs (MP3 and AAC) consistently produce negative NMR values, indicating that most coding distortion remains perceptually masked. AAC generally achieves lower NMR than MP3, particularly for clean test tones, reflecting more stable and effective noise shaping. Under degradation, NMR increases for test tones and speech due to reduced masking effectiveness, whereas music signals show relatively stable NMR due to stronger inherent masking. Meanwhile, EnCodec consistently exhibits the highest NMR across all signal conditions, indicating greater levels of unmasked distortion associated with its generative reconstruction approach.

Psychoacoustic model analyses explain these trends across all signal types. MP3 and AAC closely follow the reference in the low- and mid-subbands and suppress high-frequency energy once SMR becomes negative, demonstrating perceptually guided discarding. AAC exhibits the most stable high-frequency roll-off, while MP3 shows greater variability in transition regions. In contrast, although EnCodec achieves the highest NMR, spectral analysis shows that this less-constrained energy reconstruction preserves or regenerates high-frequency content beyond masking thresholds and also exhibits greater variability across subbands.

Experiment A shows that conventional CODECs achieve low distortion by explicitly exploiting psychoacoustic masking, whereas the neural CODEC’s generative reconstruction results in greater spectral variability and more unmasked distortion in low-density signals(pure tone and speech), aligned with the observation in [46]. In addition, no explicit degradation suppression mechanism is observed in any CODEC, as degradations are treated as part of the input signal during encoding.

6.4 Result analysis for experiment B

Experiment B investigates CODEC behaviour under complex and unconstrained degradation conditions generated by an optimiser. Unlike the controlled analyses in Experiment A, this experiment explores how different CODECs respond when degradation parameters are jointly varied across a high-dimensional space, reflecting more realistic and interacting distortion scenarios. A reinforcement learning–based optimiser is employed to discover degradation configurations that maximise perceptual degradation, allowing both the structure of the explored degradation space and the resulting perceptual sensitivity of each CODEC to be examined. Through a combination of exploratory analysis and nonlinear modelling, this section aims to characterise shared and CODEC-specific degradation behaviours beyond what can be observed using a scalar quality assessment.

6.4.1 Optimisation solution framework

During optimisation, the agent records both the explored degradation parameters and the resulting solutions at each iteration. The dataset includes the best and average reward values, as well as the mean and standard deviation of the selected actions over time.

Table 23 lists the degradation parameter of individual track stores in each iteration during training. The constrain scope of each degradation type is inherited from the 5.2.2.2. They are applied independently to the vocal, drum, bass, and guitar tracks.

Table 23 Degradation configuration parameters. A standard set of noise, clipping, and compression parameters is instantiated per track.

Parameter Name	Meaning	Unit
Hum	Signal-to-hum noise ratio	dB
Hiss	Signal-to-hiss noise ratio	dB
CL	Clipping amount	%
Thre	Compressor threshold	dB
Ratio	Compressor ratio	–
Attk	Compressor attack time	milliseconds
Release	Compressor release time	milliseconds

6.4.2 Validity of the training process

This subsection examines the training process of the reinforcement learning optimiser in Experiment B. To confirm a stable, convergent learning behaviour across different CODECs during optimiser training.

Across all CODECs, the average reward in Figure 38 remains within a narrow range throughout training, indicating stable optimisation rather than divergent behaviour. The best reward curve in Figure 39 increases during the early training phase and slightly improves until updating plateaus. Near-optimal degradation configurations are identified early and retained. Policy entropy measures the exploration behaviour of the reinforcement learning optimiser. Across all CODECs, the trends of entropy in Figure 40, decrease gradually during

training and stabilise in later iterations, indicating a transition from exploratory sampling to a more consistent degradation selection policy.

Table 24 shows that EnCodec yields higher degradation rewards than conventional CODECs and exhibits lower relative variability, indicating that degradations are more consistently penalised in the neural CODEC.

Figure 38 Average reward per iteration. Average episode reward during training for MP3, AAC, and EnCodec.

Figure 39 Best reward achieved during training. Best reward obtained up to each training iteration for MP3, AAC, and EnCodec.

Figure 40 Policy entropy during training. Policy entropy over training iterations, showing the evolution of exploration across CODECs.

Table 24 Final training statistics for Experiment B across CODECs.

CODEC	Final best reward	Final average reward(MEAN)	Final reward standard deviation(STD)	Coefficient of variation (STD/MEAN)
MP3(64kbps)	0.524	0.392	0.03	7.7%
AAC(64kbps)	0.523	0.373	0.033	8.8%
EnCodec(24kbps)	0.657	0.566	0.02	3.5%

6.4.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA was applied to the degradation configurations collected during optimisation as an exploratory visualisation tool, rather than for feature reduction or prediction. The dataset comprises 8100 samples (270 solutions per iteration \times 10 iterations \times 3 CODEC types).

Bartlett’s test of sphericity strongly rejected the null hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix ($\chi^2 \gg 0, p < 0.001$), indicating sufficient inter-variable correlation for PCA. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy (MSA) is 0.879, which is considered acceptable when it exceeds 0.6, further supporting the suitability of PCA. No variables were excluded based on communality or MSA, as each parameter represents an intentionally designed degradation-control dimension rather than a dimension-reduction tool.

All features were standardised before analysis. In Figure 41, scree plot inspection and 95th-percentile parallel analysis indicated that approximately 5 principal components account for 54.2% of the variance beyond that expected from random noise. For visualisation, the data were projected onto the first 3 principal components, which together explain 44.5% of the total variance. Although this projection does not capture the full structure of the data, it provides a clear, interpretable overview of the dominant variance patterns.

Figure 41 Scree plot with parallel analysis (95th percentile) for the standardised degradation parameters. Real-data eigenvalues are compared with the noise cutoff and the Kaiser criterion (eigenvalue = 1), indicating approximately five meaningful principal components.

The PCA projection reveals a shared central region across all CODECs, indicating a common core of degradation configurations during optimisation. Beyond this core, CODEC-specific dispersion patterns are observed in Figure 42. MP3 and AAC exhibit clearer separation along PC1 in the PC1–PC3 view, forming opposing lobes, whereas the EnCodec shows broader dispersion and occupies intermediate regions across all projections. These differences reflect structured variation in the distribution of degradation configurations across CODECs, rather than direct perceptual or causal mechanisms.

Figure 42 PCA distribution of degradation configurations across CODECs (MP3, AAC, EnCodec-nc). Each point represents a degradation configuration projected onto the first three principal components (PC1, PC2 and PC3)

Figure 43 PCA correlation-circle plots (PC1–PC2, PC1–PC3, PC2–PC3) showing original instrument features (blue), track-level groups (black), and the reward vector (red). The unit circle indicates correlation strength; alignment with the reward vector highlights features and track groups most associated with higher reward.

Figure 44 PCA correlation-circle plots (PC1–PC2, PC1–PC3, PC2–PC3) showing original degradation features (blue), degradation-type groups (green), and the reward vector (red). The unit circle indicates correlation strength; alignment and opposition between degradation-type vectors and the reward vector indicate which degradation mechanisms are most associated with higher or lower reward.

Figure 43 and Figure 44 present PCA correlation-circle plots for the first 3 principal components. Original degradation parameters are shown alongside aggregated track-level and degradation-type vectors. The degradation vectors are computed by averaging corresponding parameters and correlating them with the PCA scores; these vectors summarise dominant co-variation patterns in the data. The reward (*1 - HAAQI score*) is included only as a post-hoc auxiliary variable and does not influence the PCA computation. A standardised scalar is applied to the reward value across different CODECs, using the z-score ($z = (x - \mu) / \sigma$) to eliminate bias from a single CODEC.

The loading patterns in Figure 43 indicate that dominant variance directions are more strongly associated with track-level groupings than with individual parameters. PC1 aligned with Bass-related parameters, PC2 and PC3 with drum-related parameters, while vocal-related parameters span multiple components. No track-level vector shows strong alignment with the reward direction, indicating that the reward is not directly associated with any single track-specific variance axis.

Individual degradation features are grouped with the degradation type level in Figure 44. PC1 aligns with hiss and compressor threshold parameters, while PC2 and PC3 align with hum-related parameters. The reward vector points in a distinct direction from degradation regimes, suggesting that high-reward configurations arise from combinations of degradation parameters rather than from a single dominant degradation type.

Table 25 shows that PC1 and PC2 are statistically correlated with reward, each accounts for a modest amount of variance ($R^2 \approx 0.12-0.14$), and PC3 shows a negligible association. Individual principal components account for only a small proportion of the variance in rewards; the degradation is not well captured by the dominant linear component. Therefore, PCA is suitable for visualising the structure of the degradation space, but insufficient for modelling degradation feature outcomes.

Table 25 Correlation of degradation score(reward) variables to principal components (Value shown is R^2 . Significant correlations highlighted in bold).

	PC1	PC2	PC3
Correlation with Reward(R^2)	.137	.121	.000

6.4.4 Tree-Based modelling and feature importance analysis

Previous analysis using PCA characterises the variance structure of the degradation configurations dataset but does not capture nonlinear relationships between parameter space and reward. This subsection applies a nonlinear modelling approach to quantify how degradation features influence perceptual outcomes across CODECs and to examine the extent of cross-CODEC consistency.

A tree-based XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting) regressor was selected due to its ability to model nonlinear effects and higher-order feature interactions without assuming linearity or normality (details in 2.5.3). XGBoost is well-suited to the present context, with complex parameter interactions; the model's hyperparameters were selected via grid search to maximise predictive accuracy.

6.4.4.1 Combined analysis across CODECs

To mitigate baseline differences across CODECs, reward values were standardised to z-scores before modelling. Under this normalisation, the XGBoost model achieved an *RMSE* of 0.18, an *MAE* of 0.12, and an R^2 of 0.968. These metrics indicate strong predictive performance, with errors small relative to the standardised target's variability. Repeated cross-validation produced comparable results, suggesting robust in-distribution generalisation.

Figure 45 Residual diagnostic plots for the XGBoost model. The predicted–actual relationship, residual scatter, and residual distribution show no obvious systematic structure, suggesting adequate in-distribution model fit

Residual diagnostics (Figure 45) were used to assess model adequacy. The predicted–actual plot closely follows the identity line; residuals are centred around zero with no visible trend with predicted values; and the residual distribution is approximately symmetric. The model captures the dominant structure in the data, with remaining errors behaving largely as noise rather than systematic bias.

Permutation importance assesses the relative contribution of each degradation parameter by measuring the decrease in R^2 when each feature is randomly shuffled (details in 2.5.3.2). Bootstrap analysis showed that all 28 features had importance estimates consistently greater than 0, suggesting statistically reliable contributions. The top 15 degradation features are listed in Table 26.

The Perceptual reward depends on multiple interacting degradation parameters. The distribution of importance values shows a clear hierarchy: the top 10 features account for 80.8% of the total permutation-importance mass, while the top 13 account for 90.7%, suggesting a non-uniform distribution across degradation parameters. Noise-related parameters dominate the ranking, with hum and hiss consistently appearing among the most influential features. Drum and vocal-related parameters are particularly prominent in the top ranks, while clipping contributes more modestly. Compression parameters on bass and guitar

tracks exhibit comparatively lower importance values, indicating a limited contribution to overall degradation within the explored configuration space

Table 26 Feature importance ranking top 15 based on permutation importance. Values represent the average decrease in R^2 when individual degradation parameters are permuted.

Rank	Feature	Importance
1	Hum_Drum	0.250
2	Hiss_Drum	0.202
3	Hum_Vocal	0.145
4	Ratio_Drum	0.141
5	Thre_Drum	0.137
6	Hiss_Vocal	0.132
7	Hum_Bass	0.104
8	Hiss_Bass	0.092
9	Ratio_Vocal	0.084
10	Hum_Guitar	0.073
11	Thre_Vocal	0.061
12	Hiss_Guitar	0.060
13	CL_Drum	0.045
14	CL_Vocal	0.043
15	Attk_Drum	0.022

6.4.4.2 CODEC-Specific analysis using SHAP

To examine CODEC-dependent differences, separate XGBoost models were trained for MP3, AAC, and EnCodec datasets. Model performance for each CODEC (Table 27) shows consistently high R^2 values, confirming that the models adequately explain the degradation interaction within each CODEC.

Rather than permutation importance, SHAP values were used for CODEC-specific interpretation. While permutation importance identifies which features are necessary for predictive performance, SHAP values quantify how individual features contribute to predictions, including direction and conditional dependence, making them more suitable for interpreting nonlinear and interaction-rich behaviour (details in 2.5.3).

Reward values were standardised independently within each CODEC before modelling, resulting in comparable prediction variances and enabling relative comparison of SHAP

magnitude across CODECs. Kendall’s coefficient of concordance ($W = 0.865, p < 10^{-5}$) indicates strong global agreement in feature ranking across MP3, AAC, and EnCodec. Pairwise Spearman correlations ($\rho \approx 0.79\text{--}0.82$) further confirm that the feature importance ordering is consistent across CODECs, suggesting a similar perceptual-relevance structure.

Table 27 Regression performance metrics by CODEC.

CODEC	R²	RMSE	MAE
MP3	0.947	0.229	0.140
AAC	0.976	0.153	0.091
EnCodec	0.970	0.170	0.102

The heatmap in Figure 46 shows that hum and hiss remain dominant across all CODECs, while differences are concentrated in a smaller subset of features, such as vocal clipping and vocal hum. These differences reflect CODEC-specific reweighting rather than a fundamental reordering of feature importance.

Feature effect direction was assessed by computing Spearman correlations between SHAP values and feature values. All features exhibited consistent effect directions across CODECs. Indicating that while parameter magnitudes vary, the perceptual impact of individual degradation parameters remains in the same direction across CODECs.

Figure 46 Feature Importance Ranking with Normalised |SHAP| Importance Value, Top 20 list is listed.

Bootstrapped comparisons of normalised SHAP importance were conducted between CODEC pairs (MP3–AAC, MP3–EnCodec, AAC–EnCodec). These comparisons reveal that most features differ in importance magnitude across CODECs (Figure 47), indicating CODEC-dependent sensitivity patterns. Noise-related parameters, particularly hum, exhibit the largest cross-CODEC shifts, with a stronger influence observed in the EnCodec for low-frequency tracks such as bass and drum.

Figure 47 Feature Importance comparison across the CODEC (Top 20): ns represent results that are not significant at $p=0.05$. ranking sorted with the highest absolute difference value.

Overall, SHAP analysis reveals a stable perceptual core of feature importance shared across CODECs, with hum and hiss consistently dominant. The effect directions remain consistent across features, and differences are limited to a small subset of parameters, such as vocal clipping and vocal hum. It reflects reweighting rather than changes in importance ordering; however, how these magnitude differences aggregate across degradation types and instrument groups remains unresolved, for further cross-CODEC comparative analysis.

6.4.4.3 Cross-CODEC importance differences and group analysis

To examine higher-level structure in feature importance, SHAP values were aggregated by instrument and by degradation parameter type. Kruskal–Wallis tests result in Table 28 revealed no significant differences across instrument groups within any CODEC ($p > 0.05$), indicating that feature importance distributions are broadly consistent across instruments. In contrast, degradation parameter type showed statistically significant differences across all CODECs ($p \approx 0.01$). The associated rank-based effect size ($\eta^2_h \approx 0.51$) suggests that approximately half of the variance in feature importance is attributable to degradation type.

Table 28 Kruskal–Wallis test results for SHAP-based feature importance across instrument groups and degradation parameter types. H denotes the rank distribution-based test statistic, and p -values indicate statistical significance of group differences.

CODEC	H(Instruments)	P-value	H(Degradation)	P-value
MP3	3.67	0.300	16.65	0.011
AAC	6.28	0.099	16.81	0.010
EnCodec	7.62	0.055	16.71	0.010

Table 29 Normalised SHAP importance (% of total) aggregated by instrument group for each CODEC.

	MP3	AAC	EnCodec
Drum	43	40.91	55.58
Vocal	29.21	35.15	23.62
Bass	17.82	14.37	10.88
Guitar	9.98	9.57	9.93

Table 30 Normalised SHAP importance (% of total) aggregated by degradation type group for each CODEC.

	MP3	AAC	EnCodec
Hum	37.47	36.37	38.27
Hiss	26.99	26.03	26.65
CL	10.64	5.69	2.57
Thre	11.54	19.74	9.24
Ratio	9.77	8.12	20.74
Attk	2.82	3.49	1.14
Release	0.77	0.57	1.39

Table 29 shows a consistent ranking of importance across all CODECs (drum > vocal > bass > guitar). Figure 48 and Table 30 further illustrate how SHAP-derived importance is redistributed across degradation parameters.

At the highest importance tier ($>20\%$), noise-related degradations (hum and hiss) form a CODEC-invariant foundation, indicating their universal influence on perceived quality. In contrast, mid-tier degradations ($>10\%$), particularly those involving DRC parameters, exhibit pronounced CODEC-dependent redistribution. In AAC, the threshold applied to drums is given greater weight, likely because changing thresholds more frequently compresses transient-rich material, altering high-frequency energy distributions and challenging masking assumptions in AAC’s psychoacoustic model. In contrast, EnCodec shows greater sensitivity to drum compression ratio; as a generative model not constrained by masking, reductions in dynamic range reshape waveform envelopes and may produce atypical latent representations, leading to increased perceptual penalties.

Beyond these trends, clipping exhibits a distinct pattern: the importance of clipping decreases from conventional CODEC to neural CODEC. Because z-score normalisation is applied on a CODEC-wise reward basis, it does not indicate a greater degree of resilience of the neural CODEC compared to conventional CODECs. Instead, relative to other degradation types, EnCodec treats clipping as less severe. This interpretation is consistent with prior observations that generative models can partially absorb or reconstruct clipped waveform characteristics [59].

Figure 48 Distribution of normalised SHAP importance across degradation mechanisms and instruments for three CODECs

6.4.5 Result summary of experiment B

Experiment B examines how CODEC behaviour changes across complex degradation mixtures, using a reinforcement-learning optimiser to systematically explore the parameter space. Degradation parameters (noise, clipping, and compression) were applied across multiple instrument tracks, and perceptual degradation was quantified via an inverted HAAQI-based reward ($1 - \text{HAAQI}$ score).

Training was stable and convergent for all CODECs. Best rewards improved rapidly before plateauing, average rewards remained consistent, and policy entropy decreased over time, indicating a shift from exploration to exploitation. EnCodec achieved higher degradation rewards with lower variability than MP3 and AAC, suggesting a higher consistent degradation penalty to the neural CODEC.

PCA was employed to visualise the explored degradation space, revealing a shared core of degradation configurations alongside CODEC-specific variation. Although the reward aligned with principal components associated with hum and hiss under degradation-type grouping, the weak correlations indicate that PCA alone does not adequately capture the structure of perceptual degradation.

Nonlinear XGBoost modelling achieved high predictive accuracy across all CODEC datasets ($R^2 \geq 0.95$). Feature importance analysis shows consistent effect directions and broadly similar importance rankings across CODECs, with observed differences primarily reflecting reweighting rather than reordering.

Importance rankings are consistent across instrument groups (drum > vocal > bass > guitar), while degradation-type analysis reveals a CODEC-invariant core dominated by noise-related parameters (hum and hiss). In contrast, DRC parameters exhibit clear CODEC-specific redistribution, with AAC showing greater sensitivity to drum compression thresholds and EnCodec to drum compression ratios. clipping follows a distinct trend, with importance

decreasing from MP3 to EnCodec, suggesting that CODEC differences are primarily driven by nonlinear degradation mechanisms.

6.5 Conclusion

This chapter combines two complementary experiments to characterise how conventional CODECs (MP3, AAC) and a neural CODEC (EnCodec) respond to audio degradation. Experiment A provides a controlled psychoacoustic baseline, showing that MP3 and AAC consistently maintain negative NMR values, indicating that most coding distortion remains perceptually masked. AAC exhibits the most stable high-frequency behaviour, reflecting effective and consistent noise shaping. In contrast, EnCodec produces higher, even positive NMR values in simple signals, due to its generative reconstruction process, which is not explicitly constrained by masking thresholds. This highlights a fundamental architectural difference: conventional CODECs discard perceptually irrelevant content based on masking [48], whereas the neural CODEC preserves or regenerates spectral energy, leading to greater variability and more unmasked distortion [55].

Experiment B extends this analysis to optimiser-driven degradation mixing. Optimisation is stable across all CODECs, but EnCodec achieves higher degradation rewards with lower variability, indicating more consistent penalisation of degradation. This extends the evidence on the fragility of generative audio quality from Experiment A. It also challenges the assumption that neural CODECs consistently outperform conventional CODECs, as reported for SoundStream [4] and EnCodec [5].

Nonlinear modelling confirms consistent effect directions and broadly similar importance rankings across CODECs, with observed differences primarily reflecting reweighting rather than reordering. Importance rankings are consistent across instrument groups (drum > vocal > bass > guitar), indicating that both types of CODECs struggle with the transient-rich structure, and agree with the finding in [51], [57].

While degradation-type analysis reveals a CODEC-invariant core dominated by noise-related parameters (hum and hiss), in contrast, DRC parameters exhibit clear CODEC-specific redistribution, with AAC showing greater sensitivity to thresholds and EnCodec to ratios. Clipping follows a distinct trend, with importance decreasing from MP3 to EnCodec, suggesting that CODEC differences are primarily driven by nonlinear degradation mechanisms.

These results reflect fundamental architectural distinctions between conventional and neural CODECs: conventional CODECs rely on explicit psychoacoustic masking models, whereas neural CODECs are shaped by data-driven generative representations rather than explicit perceptual constraints. Despite differing mechanisms, both CODEC types degrade under broadly similar conditions and exhibit largely consistent importance rankings across instruments and degradation categories. Drum-related degradations remain especially challenging across both paradigms, indicating a shared sensitivity to transient-rich content; meanwhile, noise-related degradation (hum and hiss) dominates the CODEC-invariant core. Differences arise primarily through CODEC-specific reweighting of nonlinear degradations, particularly DRC parameters such as ratio and threshold. Furthermore, neural CODECs tend to yield lower psychoacoustic scores, exhibit higher NMR in Experiment A and higher degradation scores in Experiment B, and also demonstrate distinct spectral preservation in music material in Experiment A and increased resilience to clipping in Experiment B.

Together, Experiments A and B demonstrate that the proposed integrated evaluation framework can simultaneously expose masking-based mechanisms and interaction-driven perceptual behaviour, enabling a systematic examination across fundamentally different CODEC architectures.

Chapter 7 Discussion

7.1 Summary of key findings across experiments

The three experiments presented in this thesis collectively demonstrate that audio quality evaluation in music production contexts requires consideration of metric selection, optimisation strategy, and CODEC-specific behaviour. Each experimental chapter addressed a distinct but interrelated aspect of the broader research problem, and its findings converge to provide a comprehensive understanding of the propagation of degradation through music production signal chains.

7.1.1 Reliable metric identification

Chapter 4 identifies Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index (HAAQI) as the most reliable objective metric for evaluating quality degradation, combining strong perceptual relevance with stable behaviour across conditions. The subjective tests showed that HAAQI correlated well with listener ratings; the effectiveness and robustness analyses further confirmed its suitability, with sufficient sensitivity across artefact types and low variability across randomised degradations. establishing it as a reliable foundation for subsequent optimisation and CODEC comparison experiments.

7.1.2 Optimisation algorithm performance

Chapter 5 shows that the choice of optimisation algorithm critically shapes degradation maximisation outcomes, affecting both exploitation and exploration of the parameter space. In a machine learning (ML)-based degradator framework, the objective metric HAAQI evaluates degraded signals in a simulated production chain optimisation loop. Enabling a systematic comparison of the optimisers of Monte Carlo sampling (MC), Genetic Algorithms (GA), and Reinforcement Learning (RL). As a result, RL outperformed GA and MC by

achieving the strongest degradation identification while preserving a wide diversity of solutions.

7.1.3 CODEC-Specific degradation sensitivity

Chapter 6 delivers the systematic comparison of the performance of conventional (MP3, AAC) and neural (EnCodec) CODECs under parameterised degradations, revealing both their vulnerabilities and architecture-specific sensitivities. The results showed that, while overall degradation importance rankings are largely consistent across CODECs, the underlying response mechanisms fundamentally differ. The generative reconstruction nature of EnCodec results in more severe quality deterioration under the experimental conditions. Hum and hiss are the two most important features, whereas the instrument-level importance (drum > vocal > bass > guitar) is consistent across all CODECs. CODEC-specific behaviours are mainly embodied in the importance of non-linear distortions in dynamic range compression (DRC) processing and clipping.

7.2 Findings on audio production degradation and evaluation

The experimental findings confirm that degradations in music production signal chains operate cumulatively affect audio quality [2]. Chapter 5 and Chapter 6 demonstrate that degradation severity is determined not by individual parameter magnitudes alone, but by their joint configuration in a high-dimensional degradation space. This view of perceptual impact emerges from compound processing conditions rather than isolated effects, which guided the design of the ML-based degradator.

These results reinforce the assumption in 2.3.3 that degradations interact with internal CODEC mechanisms, altering masking estimation, bit allocation, and signal reconstruction behaviour [46], [48], [49], [50], [51]. Specifically, the conventional CODEC analyses in 5.4.3, 6.3.1, and 6.4.1 show that production degradations exaggerate high-frequency loss and substantially increase the noise-to-mask ratio (NMR). In contrast, the neural CODEC exhibits

elevated NMR and a higher overall degradation penalty to perceived audio quality. When reconstruction is driven by data distribution [46], performance degrades for signal characteristics that fall outside the training dataset, limiting robustness under unfamiliar production degradations.

The application of objective audio quality metrics in music production contexts reveals two primary limitations: cross-domain reliability [9] and the inherent constraints of scalar quality scores. Under nonlinear and compound degradation conditions, metrics may exhibit sensitivity mismatches. Results from Sections 4.3.3 and 4.4.4 show that PEAQ-Advanced, despite strong subjective correlation, produced unstable responses under compound and nonlinear degradations [13], [71]. VISQOLAudio demonstrated greater stability against nonlinear degradation but performed poorly at predicting subjective ratings, indicating degradation-dependent sensitivity [15]. HAAQI showed the most consistent performance across diverse degradation types, in line with prior findings [9]; however, its scalar outputs remain insufficient to fully represent the perceptual complexity arising from interacting production degradations. These limitations motivate the development of the degradation exploration and optimisation tools introduced in the subsequent chapters, which aim to better characterise complex degradation interactions beyond single-metric evaluation.

7.3 Implications for intelligent music production systems

To investigate how degradations accumulate in realistic production workflows, this thesis develops an intelligent music production (IMP) system designed specifically for degradation exploration and analysis. Unlike conventional IMP systems, which typically aim to improve mix quality or automate mixing decisions [76], the proposed ML-based degradator framework is intended to pressure-test the CODEC by maximising perceptual degradation and identifying the degradation processes that occur during CODEC processing.

Achieving this objective requires a stable and reliable perceptual quality metric, as established in Chapter 4. The degradation processes incorporated into the system are grounded in realistic production practices reviewed in Chapter 3, while the optimisation algorithms are informed by the algorithmic review in 2.5. As demonstrated in Chapter 4, audio quality degradation arises from multiple degradation types. Thus, the high dimensionality and non-convexity of the degradation parameter space can lead to severely degraded solutions across multiple regions. Under these conditions, a metric-guided optimisation framework is more feasible than a supervised, dataset-driven learning approach [77], [78], [79], [80], which would require explicit annotation of degraded exemplars.

Across both single-track and multi-track experiments in 5.4.3 and 6.4.2, reinforcement learning (RL) consistently achieves the most severe perceptual degradation while maintaining broader exploration of the parameter space. RL training converges toward stable solution regions, accompanied by a gradual reduction in policy entropy. In contrast, MC shows no consistent improvement, while GA exhibit stronger convergence but is prone to premature collapse into narrow solution regions, limiting solution diversity.

These findings challenge common assumptions in the optimisation literature [11], [81], [82], [83] that population-based algorithms are inherently superior for inverse optimisation problems. Instead, the results suggest that RL-based approaches offer a more effective balance between exploration and exploitation when navigating complex degradation spaces in intelligent music production systems.

7.4 CODEC behaviour considering existing CODEC research

The architectural differences between conventional and neural CODECs fundamentally govern their responses to production-induced degradations. Conventional CODECs rely on explicit psychoacoustic models to estimate masking thresholds and shape quantisation noise accordingly [3]. At the decoder stage, the reconstructed signal consists of the encoded audio

plus masking-shaped quantisation noise, resulting in largely predictable, additive degradation. As shown in 6.3.1, conventional CODECs consistently maintained NMR, indicating that coding noise remained perceptually masked under most conditions.

In contrast, neural CODECs employ compression–generation architectures trained to generate perceptually plausible audio from compressed latent representations [4], [5]. Rather than explicitly preserving signal fidelity, the decoder prioritises perceptual plausibility based on learned data distributions. This architectural distinction leads to markedly different degradation responses. EnCodec exhibited elevated NMR across all signal types in 6.3.1, hallucinated tonal components in 6.3.2, and higher overall degradation penalties in 6.4.1. In the absence of an explicit psychoacoustic masking model or perceptual optimisation objective, reconstruction errors in the neural CODEC remained more perceptually salient, challenging claims that neural CODECs are inherently more effective than conventional CODECs [5].

Despite these differences, neither psychoacoustic modelling nor learned generative priors can reliably suppress degradations that spectrally overlap with signal content. Sensitivity analysis in 6.4.5 identified hum and hiss as consistently perceptually damaging across all CODECs. This finding aligns with 2.2.4, where low-frequency hum and broadband hiss elevate the noise floor and distort tonality estimation in conventional CODECs, reducing effective masking and forcing less efficient bit allocation [54]. Similarly, these noise components disrupt neural CODEC reconstruction when models are trained predominantly on clean audio datasets [46].

Instrument-level importance also maintains a consistent hierarchy: drums > vocals > bass > guitar across all CODECs. Transient-rich, spectrally sparse sources such as drums pose the greatest challenge, consistent with prior findings [51], [57]. The challenge of transient-dominated content differs from the encoding paradigm, in which conventional CODECs struggle with transient resolution due to time–frequency trade–offs, whereas generative priors in neural CODECs are biased toward stationary, harmonic structures.

Nonlinear distortion produced the most pronounced CODEC-specific differences, as observed in 6.4.5. DRC parameters revealed divergent sensitivity patterns, with AAC being more sensitive to threshold settings and EnCodec to compression ratio. In AAC, threshold variation more frequently alters transient-rich material, redistributing high-frequency energy and challenging masking assumptions. In contrast, EnCodec, as a generative model not constrained by masking, reshapes waveform envelopes and dynamic range through its process, potentially producing atypical latent representations and higher perceptual penalties. These reflect the complex of DRC processing that is able to create the sophisticated non-linear distortion for the audio test circumstance, such as [28], [29], [78].

Moreover, the neural CODEC also show its advantage compared to the conventional counterparts, the comparatively low importance of clipping degradation for EnCodec in 6.4.5 and the high-frequency reservation in 6.4.2 suggest the efficiency in the high frequency and robustness to certain nonlinear distortions, consistent with prior observations [58], [59], [60], which may be attributable not to explicit modelling but to representational flexibility.

Chapter 8 Conclusion

This thesis investigated audio quality evaluation in a music production signal chain through a literature review and three interconnected experimental studies, focusing on how the interaction between production degradations and CODECs affects perceptual audio quality. It addressed key gaps relating to metric reliability, optimisation algorithm effectiveness, and degradation sensitivity across different CODEC architectures. By systematically examining these factors within realistic music production workflows, the thesis establishes a methodological foundation for assessing the impact of audio degradation, offers empirical insights into the design of optimisation algorithms in the IMP system, and clarifies the mechanisms and performance of conventional and neural CODECs.

8.1 Contributions

This thesis makes three novel contributions to the field of audio quality evaluation in music production contexts:

Contribution 1 (C1): validated metric selection for production contexts. This thesis provides a systematic validation of objective audio quality metrics, specifically in signal chains that incorporate degradations and CODEC processing. Through combined subjective listening studies and objective evaluation experiments, the research establishes HAAQI as the most reliable metric for quality assessment. This contribution is significant because existing metrics are developed and validated under the assumption of isolated degradation or primarily specific applications, with limited evidence of their reliability when applied to complex, interacting degradations characteristic of music production workflows. Additionally, the validation methodology itself serves as a reusable framework for future metric evaluation.

Contribution 2 (C2): Comparative Analysis of Optimisation Techniques for Perceptually Guided ML-based degradator. This thesis proposes a modular, degradation-

maximising architecture that inverts common objectives in intelligent music production (IMP). Rather than seeking optimal quality by minimising the error, the framework systematically identifies worst-case production scenarios, revealing CODEC vulnerabilities and production pipeline failure modes. Using this framework, MC, GA, and RL are systematically compared, demonstrating that RL consistently outperforms the alternatives in both the achieved maximisation and the diversity-degraded solutions.

This contribution comprises two elements. First, the framework provides a reusable testbed for analysing the interaction between degradation processes, CODEC behaviour, and optimisation algorithms under perceptual feedback. Second, it demonstrates an RL-based optimisation approach that maintains effective exploration in high-dimensional parameter spaces. Together, these advances support intelligent music production and creative audio research by establishing a general methodological framework and evidence-based guidance on optimiser selection.

Contribution 3 (C3): Integrated Evaluation Framework for CODEC Degradation Sensitivity.

The thesis introduces an integrated evaluation framework for systematically comparing conventional and neural CODECs under controlled production-related degradations, revealing both shared vulnerabilities and architecture-specific sensitivity patterns. This addresses a notable gap in existing CODEC evaluation research, as the audio CODEC artefacts and audio distortion have been extensively studied in isolation.

By combining psychoacoustic measurement with non-linear tree-model analysis, the framework enables the simultaneous examination of masking-based mechanisms and interaction-driven perceptual behaviour. The results show a CODEC-invariant core dominated by noise-related degradations and stable instrument-level importance, alongside CODEC-dependent sensitivity to nonlinear distortion. These findings provide practical

guidance for CODEC selection in production workflows and inform the CODEC design of quality-enhancement strategies under distortion-prone conditions.

8.2 Limitations

This thesis advances the understanding of audio quality evaluation in music production signal chains; however, several limitations should be acknowledged.

First, the range of CODEC configurations and audio degradation types examined in this study is constrained. The CODEC bitrates are limited to 64 kbps, the maximum resolution, chosen to approximate the industry-standard 128 kbps bitrate for stereo material. And the experiments focus on a restricted subset of degradation processes. In contrast, real-world music production workflows typically involve a wider diversity of degradation types, parameter settings, and encoding conditions, which are not fully captured in the present evaluation.

Second, without the direct subjective validation for CODEC sensitivity. Subjective listening test data are incorporated into the metric selection chapter to validate the suitability of the metric; however, because CODEC-specific sensitivity analyses involve more complex interactions, additional subjective listening experiments would provide stronger perceptual validation.

Third, limitations inherent to the HAAQI framework restricted the experimental scope: the metric does not support spatial audio evaluation and requires substantial computational resources, thereby constraining exploration of larger-scale or more complex production environments.

These limitations, while constraining the scope of the current work, simultaneously indicate productive directions for future research.

8.3 Future Works

8.3.1 Expanded Metric Development and Validation.

Although HAAQI demonstrated superior performance for evaluating production-related degradations, future work could investigate the development of production-specific perceptual metrics. Such metrics could serve as real-time meters, incorporating explicit models of common production degradations and multi-track interaction effects. Additionally, given HAAQI's origins in hearing-aid research, future studies could explore how production degradations are perceived by hearing-impaired listeners or extend the metric framework to stereophonic and spatial audio contexts.

8.3.2 Advanced Optimisation Architectures.

The demonstrated RL in the ML-based degradation synthesis task suggests several methodological extensions. Multi-objective RL formulations could enable simultaneous optimisation of perceptual quality, stylistic coherence, and technical constraints, better reflecting the multi-stage decision-making processes used in music production. Alternative RL algorithms may offer improved sample efficiency or convergence behaviour in high-dimensional parameter spaces. Furthermore, an important methodological extension is the incorporation of reference-guided optimisation. The current framework operates without reference mixes, exploring the degradation space solely by maximising a black-box function. Future work could investigate semi-supervised approaches that leverage partial reference information to guide exploration, or transfer learning strategies that enable policies trained on one musical style to generalise to others.

8.3.3 Neural CODEC Development and Evaluation.

The elevated NMR values and distinct sensitivity patterns of neural CODEC indicate opportunities for architecture refinement. Future research could examine whether incorporating explicit perceptual loss functions, such as masking thresholds, into neural CODEC training would improve resilience to production degradations without sacrificing generative flexibility. Alternatively, hybrid architectures combining learned representations

with psychoacoustic constraints might achieve better performance than purely model-based or purely data-driven approaches. The clipping resilience suggests that neural CODECs may handle certain nonlinear degradations more effectively, motivating further investigation into the learned features that support this behaviour.

Chapter 9 References

- [1] A. Reuter, ‘Who let the DAWs Out? The Digital in a New Generation of the Digital Audio Workstation’, *Pop. Music Soc.*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 113–128, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1080/03007766.2021.1972701.
- [2] P. White, *The Studio SOS Book: Solutions and Techniques for the Project Recording Studio*. Taylor & Francis, 2013.
- [3] K. Brandenburg, ‘MP3 and AAC Explained’, p. 12.
- [4] N. Zeghidour, A. Luebs, A. Omran, J. Skoglund, and M. Tagliasacchi, ‘SoundStream: An End-to-End Neural Audio Codec’, *IEEEACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.*, vol. 30, pp. 495–507, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TASLP.2021.3129994.
- [5] A. Défossez, J. Copet, G. Synnaeve, and Y. Adi, ‘High Fidelity Neural Audio Compression’, Oct. 24, 2022, *arXiv*: arXiv:2210.13438. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2210.13438.
- [6] K. Brandenburg and T. Sporer, “‘NMR’ and ‘masking flag’: Evaluation of quality using perceptual criteria”, 1992, Accessed: Jun. 21, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://publica.fraunhofer.de/handle/publica/320650>
- [7] M. Erne, ‘Perceptual Audio Coders “What to listen for”’, *N. Y.*, p. 10, 2001.

- [8] M. Schoeffler and J. Herre, ‘The relationship between basic audio quality and overall listening experience’, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 140, no. 3, p. 2101, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1121/1.4963078.
- [9] M. Torcoli, T. Kastner, and J. Herre, ‘Objective Measures of Perceptual Audio Quality Reviewed: An Evaluation of Their Application Domain Dependence’, *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.*, vol. 29, pp. 1530–1541, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TASLP.2021.3069302.
- [10] C. J. Steinmetz, ‘Deep learning for automatic mixing’.
- [11] B. Kolasinski, ‘A Framework for Automatic Mixing Using Timbral Similarity Measures and Genetic Optimization’, vol. 3, May 2008.
- [12] C. Xu, Y.-B. Zhao, Z. Lu, and Y. Zhang, ‘Reinforcement-learning-based Algorithms for Optimization Problems and Applications to Inverse Problems’, Jan. 24, 2025, *arXiv*: arXiv:2310.06711. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2310.06711.
- [13] R. Huber and B. Kollmeier, ‘PEMO-Q—A New Method for Objective Audio Quality Assessment Using a Model of Auditory Perception’, *IEEE Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 1902–1911, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TASL.2006.883259.
- [14] C. Sloan, N. Harte, D. Kelly, A. C. Kokaram, and A. Hines, ‘Objective Assessment of Perceptual Audio Quality Using ViSQOLAudio’, *IEEE Trans. Broadcast.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 693–705, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TBC.2017.2704421.

- [15] T. Namgyal, A. Hepburn, R. Santos-Rodriguez, V. Laparra, and J. Malo, ‘What You Hear Is What You See: Audio Quality Metrics From Image Quality Metrics’, Aug. 30, 2023, *arXiv*: arXiv:2305.11582. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2305.11582.
- [16] D. A. M. G. Wisnu, S. Rini, R. E. Zezario, H.-M. Wang, and Y. Tsao, ‘HAAQI-Net: A Non-intrusive Neural Music Audio Quality Assessment Model for Hearing Aids’, Jan. 09, 2025, *arXiv*: arXiv:2401.01145. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2401.01145.
- [17] R. Izhaki, *Mixing Audio: Concepts, Practices, and Tools*, 4th edn. New York: Focal Press, 2023. doi: 10.4324/9781003303077.
- [18] ‘Audio quality in networked systems’. Accessed: Sep. 26, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://usa.yamaha.com/products/contents/proaudio/docs/audio_quality/01_audio_quality.html
- [19] F. Rumsey, S. Zieliński, R. Kassier, and S. Bech, ‘On the relative importance of spatial and timbral fidelities in judgments of degraded multichannel audio quality’, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 118, no. 2, pp. 968–976, Aug. 2005, doi: 10.1121/1.1945368.
- [20] Ric Viers, *The Sound Effects Bible : How to Create and Record Hollywood Style Sound Effects*. Studio City, CA: Michael Wiese Productions, 2008.
- [21] P. Kendrick, I. R. Jackson, B. M. Fazenda, T. J. Cox, and F. F. Li, ‘Microphone Handling Noise: Measurements of Perceptual Threshold and Effects on Audio

- Quality', *PLOS ONE*, vol. 10, no. 10, p. e0140256, Oct. 2015, doi:
10.1371/journal.pone.0140256.
- [22] Jerome, 'Noise Floor vs Floor Noise: Ultimate Guide - Gearank'. Accessed: Jan. 13, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gearank.com/floor-noise/>
- [23] A. Wilson and B. Fazenda, 'Characterisation of distortion profiles in relation to audio quality', 2014.
- [24] P. Kendrick and Et Al, 'Perceived Audio Quality of Sounds Degraded by Nonlinear Distortions and Single-Ended Assessment Using HASQI', *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 63, no. 9, pp. 698–712, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.17743/jaes.2015.0068.
- [25] C.-T. Tan, B. Moore, and N. Zacharov, 'The Effect of Nonlinear Distortion on the Perceived Quality of Music and Speech Signals', *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, Nov. 2003, Accessed: Dec. 02, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Effect-of-Nonlinear-Distortion-on-the-Perceived-Tan-Moore/e91b2d32b963f3fd064643ad93078a8d8b66266a>
- [26] Curtis Roads, *The Computer Music Tutorial*. Cambridge, Mass: The MIT Press, 1995. Accessed: Nov. 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://salford.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&AuthType=shib,cookie,ip,url,uid&db=nlebk&AN=49324&site=ehost-live>

- [27] L. Kozma-Spytek, P. Tucker, and C. Vogler, 'Voice Telephony for Individuals with Hearing Loss: The Effects of Audio Bandwidth, Bit Rate and Packet Loss', in *Proceedings of the 21st International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*, Pittsburgh PA USA: ACM, Oct. 2019, pp. 3–15. doi: 10.1145/3308561.3353796.
- [28] A. Wilson and B. M. Fazenda, 'Perception of Audio Quality in Productions of Popular Music', *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 64, no. 1/2, pp. 23–34, Feb. 2016.
- [29] R. Toulson, J. Paterson, and W. Campbell, 'A Quantitative Evaluation of Signal Masking in Summed and Compressed Audio', Shoreham-by-Sea, UK: Future Technology Press, 2014, pp. 20–31. Accessed: Jan. 13, 2026. [Online]. Available: <http://nimbusvault.net/publications/koala/inmusic/345.html>
- [30] N. B. H. Croghan, K. H. Arehart, and J. M. Kates, 'Quality and loudness judgments for music subjected to compression limiting)', *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 132, no. 2, pp. 1177–1188, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.1121/1.4730881.
- [31] S.-K. Lau and E. A. Powell, 'Effects of absorption placement on sound field of a rectangular room: A statistical approach', *J. Low Freq. Noise Vib. Act. Control*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 394–406, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1177/1461348418780027.
- [32] A. Bourbon, 'Hit Hard or Go Home: 12th Art of Record Production Conference', *Proc. 12th Art Rec. Prod. Conf.*, pp. 19–36, Jun. 2019.

- [33] P. Kvist, K. B. Rasmussen, and T. Poulsen, ‘A Listening Test of Dither in Digital Audio Systems: 118th AES convention’, *AES Conv.*, 2005.
- [34] M. Mauch and S. Ewert, ‘The Audio Degradation Toolbox And Its Application To Robustness Evaluation’, Jan. 2013.
- [35] M. Schwabe, T. Hoffmann, S. Murgul, and M. Heizmann, ‘Estimation of Music Recording Quality to Predict Automatic Music Transcription Performance’, in *Smart Multimedia*, S. Berretti and G.-M. Su, Eds, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 322–337. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-22061-6_24.
- [36] Y. Zang, Z. Dai, M. D. Plumbley, and Q. Kong, ‘Music Source Restoration’, May 27, 2025, *arXiv*: arXiv:2505.21827. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2505.21827.
- [37] R. Raissi, ‘The Theory Behind Mp3’, 2002. Accessed: Jan. 20, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Theory-Behind-Mp3-Raissi/ff0087cff704a99ba8766d61367b3731e785eb28>
- [38] A. C. Den Brinker *et al.*, ‘An Overview of the Coding Standard MPEG-4 Audio Amendments 1 and 2: HE-AAC, SSC, and HE-AAC v2’, *EURASIP J. Audio Speech Music Process.*, vol. 2009, pp. 1–21, 2009, doi: 10.1155/2009/468971.
- [39] J.-M. Valin, K. Vos, and T. B. Terriberry, ‘Definition of the Opus Audio Codec’, Internet Engineering Task Force, Request for Comments RFC 6716, Sep. 2012. doi: 10.17487/RFC6716.

- [40] ISO/IEC, ‘ISO/IEC 11172-3:1993’, ISO. Accessed: Mar. 12, 2023. [Online].
Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/22412.html>
- [41] ISO/IEC, ‘ISO/IEC 13818-3:1998’, ISO. Accessed: Mar. 12, 2023. [Online].
Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/26797.html>
- [42] ISO/IEC, ‘ISO/IEC 13818-7:2006’, ISO. Accessed: Mar. 12, 2023. [Online].
Available: <https://www.iso.org/standard/43345.html>
- [43] H. Fastl and E. Zwicker, *Psychoacoustics: Facts and Models*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2006.
- [44] B. C. J. Moore and B. R. Glasberg, ‘Suggested formulae for calculating auditory-filter bandwidths and excitation patterns’, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 750–753, Sep. 1983, doi: 10.1121/1.389861.
- [45] S. Quackenbush and P. Noll, ‘MPEG Digital Audio Coding Standards’, in *Video, Speech, and Audio Signal Processing and Associated Standards*, vol. 20096073, in *Electrical Engineering Handbook*, vol. 20096073. , CRC Press, 2009, pp. 1–34. doi: 10.1201/9781420046090-c2.
- [46] R. Kumar, P. Seetharaman, A. Luebs, I. Kumar, and K. Kumar, ‘High-Fidelity Audio Compression with Improved RVQGAN’, Oct. 26, 2023, *arXiv*: arXiv:2306.06546. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2306.06546.

- [47] Y. Ai, X.-H. Jiang, Y.-X. Lu, H.-P. Du, and Z.-H. Ling, ‘APCodec: A Neural Audio Codec with Parallel Amplitude and Phase Spectrum Encoding and Decoding’, Sep. 24, 2024, *arXiv*: arXiv:2402.10533. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2402.10533.
- [48] ‘Lossy encoding and peak levels’. Accessed: Jan. 14, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://izotope-rx.livejournal.com/5760.html>
- [49] A. Biswas, P. Hedelin, L. Villemoes, and V. Melkote, ‘Temporal Noise Shaping with Companding’, in *Interspeech 2018*, ISCA, Sep. 2018, pp. 3548–3552. doi: 10.21437/Interspeech.2018-2096.
- [50] A. Taleb and G. Ullberg, ‘Transient detector and method for supporting encoding of an audio signal’, US20170040024A1, Feb. 09, 2017 Accessed: Jan. 14, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20170040024/en>
- [51] M. H. Martinez, ‘Evaluation of Audio Compression Artifacts’, *Acta Polytech.*, vol. 47, no. 1, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.14311/906.
- [52] J. Herre and S. Dick, ‘Psychoacoustic Models for Perceptual Audio Coding—A Tutorial Review’, *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 9, no. 14, Art. no. 14, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3390/app9142854.
- [53] M. Bosi and R. E. Goldberg, *Introduction to digital audio coding and standards*. in The Kluwer international series in engineering and computer science, no. SECS 721. Boston: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2003.

- [54] A. Taghipour, M. C. Jaikumar, B. Edler, and H. Stahl, ‘Partial spectral flatness measure for tonality estimation in a filter bank-based psychoacoustic model for perceptual audio coding’, presented at the Audio Engineering Society (Convention) 2013, 2013. Accessed: Jan. 14, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://publica.fraunhofer.de/handle/publica/381292>
- [55] R.-C. Zheng, Y. Ai, H.-P. Du, and L.-R. Dai, ‘Enhancing Noise Robustness for Neural Speech Codecs through Resource-Efficient Progressive Quantization Perturbation Simulation’, Oct. 13, 2025, *arXiv*: arXiv:2509.19025. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2509.19025.
- [56] Z. Niu, S. Chen, L. Zhou, Z. Ma, X. Chen, and S. Liu, ‘NDVQ: Robust Neural Audio Codec with Normal Distribution-Based Vector Quantization’, Sep. 19, 2024, *arXiv*: arXiv:2409.12717. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2409.12717.
- [57] Y. Zang *et al.*, ‘MSRBench: A Benchmarking Dataset for Music Source Restoration’, Oct. 13, 2025, *arXiv*: arXiv:2510.10995. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2510.10995.
- [58] A. Russo, M. Spanio, and S. Canazza, ‘Enhancing Preservation and Restoration of Open Reel Audio Tapes Through Computer Vision’, in *Image Analysis and Processing - ICIAP 2023 Workshops*, G. L. Foresti, A. Fusiello, and E. Hancock, Eds, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 297–308. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-51026-7_26.

- [59] H. Liu *et al.*, ‘VoiceFixer: A Unified Framework for High-Fidelity Speech Restoration’, in *Interspeech 2022*, Sep. 2022, pp. 4232–4236. doi: 10.21437/Interspeech.2022-11026.
- [60] J. Imort, G. Fabbro, M. A. M. Ramírez, S. Uhlich, Y. Koyama, and Y. Mitsufuji, ‘Distortion Audio Effects: Learning How to Recover the Clean Signal’, Sep. 13, 2022, *arXiv*: arXiv:2202.01664. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2202.01664.
- [61] S. Bech and N. Zacharov, *Perceptual Audio Evaluation - Theory, Method and Application*. John Wiley & Sons, 2007.
- [62] International Telecommunication Union, ‘Recommendation ITU-R BS.1284-1: General methods for the subjective assessment of sound quality’. 2003.
- [63] International Telecommunication Union, ‘Recommendation ITU-R BS.1116-3: Methods for the subjective assessment of small impairments in audio systems’. 2015.
- [64] International Telecommunication Union, ‘Recommendation ITU-R BS.1534-3: Method for the subjective assessment of intermediate quality level of audio systems’. 2015.
- [65] A. Wilson, ‘Evaluation and Modelling of Perceived Audio Quality in Popular Music, towards Intelligent Music Production’, Ph.D., University of Salford (United Kingdom), England, 2017. Accessed: Sep. 29, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2558632031/abstract/B6F34F6C92BA4275PQ/1>

- [66] S. Zielinski, ‘On Some Biases Encountered in Modern Audio Quality Listening Tests (Part 2): Selected Graphical Examples and Discussion’, *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 64, no. 1/2, pp. 55–74, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.17743/jaes.2015.0094.
- [67] P. J. Carolan, A. Heinrich, K. J. Munro, and R. E. Millman, ‘Divergent effects of listening demands and evaluative threat on listening effort in online and laboratory settings’, *Front. Psychol.*, vol. 15, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1171873.
- [68] P. Počta and J. Beerends, ‘Subjective and Objective Assessment of Perceived Audio Quality of Current Digital Audio Broadcasting Systems and Web-Casting Applications’, *IEEE Trans. Broadcast.*, pp. 1–1, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TBC.2015.2424373.
- [69] R. Vanam and C. D. Creusere, ‘Evaluating low bitrate scalable audio quality using advanced version of PEAQ and energy equalization approach’, in *Proceedings. (ICASSP '05). IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 2005.*, Mar. 2005, p. iii/189-iii/192 Vol. 3. doi: 10.1109/ICASSP.2005.1415678.
- [70] T. Roberts and K. K. Paliwal, ‘An objective measure of quality for time-scale modification of audio’, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 149, no. 3, pp. 1843–1854, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1121/10.0003753.

- [71] J. M. Kates and K. H. Arehart, 'The Hearing-Aid Audio Quality Index (HAAQI)', *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 354–365, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1109/TASLP.2015.2507858.
- [72] A. Lerch, Arthur Claire, Bryan-KinnsNick, FordCorey, SunQianyi, and VinayAshvala, 'Survey on the Evaluation of Generative Models in Music', *ACM Comput. Surv.*, Oct. 2025, doi: 10.1145/3769106.
- [73] 'RECOMMENDATION ITU-R BS.1387-1 - Method for objective measurements of perceived audio quality', *R BS*.
- [74] C. Colomes, C. Schmidmer, T. Thiede, and W. C. Treurniet, 'Perceptual Quality Assessment for Digital Audio: PEAQ-The New ITU Standard for Objective Measurement of the Perceived Audio Quality', presented at the Audio Engineering Society Conference: 17th International Conference: High-Quality Audio Coding, Audio Engineering Society, Sep. 1999. Accessed: Aug. 19, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://www.aes.org/e-lib/inst/browse.cfm?elib=8055>
- [75] M. Chinen, F. S. C. Lim, J. Skoglund, N. Gureev, F. O’Gorman, and A. Hines, 'ViSQOL v3: An Open Source Production Ready Objective Speech and Audio Metric', Apr. 20, 2020, *arXiv*: arXiv:2004.09584. Accessed: Apr. 04, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2004.09584>
- [76] D. Moffat and M. B. Sandler, 'Approaches in Intelligent Music Production', *Arts*, vol. 8, no. 4, p. 125, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.3390/arts8040125.

- [77] M. Martinez Ramirez, D. Stoller, and D. Moffat, ‘A Deep Learning Approach to Intelligent Drum Mixing with the Wave-U-Net’, *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 142–151, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.17743/jaes.2020.0031.
- [78] D. Sheng and G. Fazekas, ‘A Feature Learning Siamese Model for Intelligent Control of the Dynamic Range Compressor’, May 01, 2019, *arXiv*: arXiv:1905.01022. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1905.01022.
- [79] C. Steinmetz, N. Bryan, and J. Reiss, ‘Style Transfer of Audio Effects with Differentiable Signal Processing’, *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 70, pp. 708–721, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.17743/jaes.2022.0025.
- [80] ‘Demonstrating Diff-MSTC: A Controllable and Context-Aware AI System for Multitrack Mixing in Digital Audio Workstation Cubase | Proceedings of the Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems’, ACM Conferences. Accessed: Jan. 10, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3706599.3721167>
- [81] D. Ronan, Z. Ma, P. M. Namara, H. Gunes, and J. D. Reiss, ‘Automatic Minimisation of Masking in Multitrack Audio using Subgroups’, Jan. 05, 2021, *arXiv*: arXiv:1803.09960. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.1803.09960.
- [82] A. Mourgela, ‘Perceptually Motivated, Intelligent Audio Mixing Approaches for Hearing Loss’, PhD Thesis, Queen Mary University of London, 2023. Accessed: Mar. 25, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://qmro.qmul.ac.uk/jspui/handle/123456789/92959>

- [83] A. Wilson and B. Fazenda, ‘User-guided Rendering of Audio Objects Using an Interactive Genetic Algorithm’, *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 67, no. 7/8, pp. 522–530, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.17743/jaes.2019.0035.
- [84] M. Črepinšek, S.-H. Liu, and M. Mernik, ‘Exploration and exploitation in evolutionary algorithms: A survey’, *ACM Comput. Surv.*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 1–33, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1145/2480741.2480752.
- [85] T. Chen *et al.*, ‘Learning to Optimize: A Primer and A Benchmark’, Jul. 02, 2021, *arXiv*: arXiv:2103.12828. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2103.12828.
- [86] N. Alamdari, E. Lobarinas, and N. Kehtarnavaz, ‘Personalization of Hearing Aid Compression by Human-in-the-Loop Deep Reinforcement Learning’, *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 203503–203515, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3035728.
- [87] V. Kronvall, *Mixing Music Using Deep Reinforcement Learning*. 2019. Accessed: Jan. 11, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kth:diva-266349>
- [88] E. R. Girden, *ANOVA: Repeated measures*. in *ANOVA: Repeated measures*. Thousand Oaks, CA, US: Sage Publications, Inc, 1992, pp. vi, 77.
- [89] J. P. Royston, ‘Some Techniques for Assessing Multivariate Normality Based on the Shapiro-Wilk W ’, *J. R. Stat. Soc. Ser. C Appl. Stat.*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 121–133, Jun. 1983, doi: 10.2307/2347291.

- [90] K. V. Mardia, 'Measures of Multivariate Skewness and Kurtosis with Applications', *Biometrika*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 519–530, 1970, doi: 10.2307/2334770.
- [91] G. V. Glass, P. D. Peckham, and J. R. Sanders, 'Consequences of Failure to Meet Assumptions Underlying the Fixed Effects Analyses of Variance and Covariance', *Rev. Educ. Res.*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 237–288, 1972, doi: 10.2307/1169991.
- [92] E. Schmider, M. Ziegler, E. Danay, L. Beyer, and M. Bühner, 'Is it really robust? Reinvestigating the robustness of ANOVA against violations of the normal distribution assumption', *Methodol. Eur. J. Res. Methods Behav. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 147–151, 2010, doi: 10.1027/1614-2241/a000016.
- [93] M. Friedman, 'The Use of Ranks to Avoid the Assumption of Normality Implicit in the Analysis of Variance', *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.*, vol. 32, no. 200, pp. 675–701, Dec. 1937, doi: 10.1080/01621459.1937.10503522.
- [94] J. W. Mauchly, 'Significance Test for Sphericity of a Normal n-Variate Distribution', *Ann. Math. Stat.*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 204–209, 1940.
- [95] H. Huynh and L. S. Feldt, 'Estimation of the Box Correction for Degrees of Freedom from Sample Data in Randomized Block and Split-Plot Designs', *J. Educ. Stat.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 69–82, 1976, doi: 10.2307/1164736.
- [96] S. W. Greenhouse and S. Geisser, 'On methods in the analysis of profile data', *Psychometrika*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 95–112, Jun. 1959, doi: 10.1007/BF02289823.

- [97] R. Bakeman, 'Recommended effect size statistics for repeated measures designs', *Behav. Res. Methods*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 379–384, Aug. 2005, doi: 10.3758/BF03192707.
- [98] S. Olejnik and J. Algina, 'Generalized eta and omega squared statistics: measures of effect size for some common research designs', *Psychol. Methods*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 434–447, Dec. 2003, doi: 10.1037/1082-989X.8.4.434.
- [99] J. Cohen, *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences*, 2nd edn. New York: Routledge, 2013. doi: 10.4324/9780203771587.
- [100] I. Jolliffe, 'Principal Component Analysis', in *Wiley StatsRef: Statistics Reference Online*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2014. doi: 10.1002/9781118445112.stat06472.
- [101] M. S. Bartlett, 'Tests of significance in factor analysis', *Br. J. Psychol.*, vol. 3, pp. 77–85, 1950.
- [102] H. F. Kaiser, 'A second generation little jiffy', *Psychometrika*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 401–415, 1970, doi: 10.1007/BF02291817.
- [103] G. D. Hutcheson, *The Multivariate Social Scientist*. SAGE Publications, Ltd., 1999. doi: 10.4135/9780857028075.
- [104] H. F. Kaiser, 'The application of electronic computers to factor analysis', *Educ. Psychol. Meas.*, vol. 20, pp. 141–151, 1960, doi: 10.1177/001316446002000116.

- [105] W. R. Zwick and W. F. Velicer, 'Comparison of five rules for determining the number of components to retain', *Psychol. Bull.*, vol. 99, no. 3, pp. 432–442, 1986, doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.99.3.432.
- [106] R. B. Cattell, 'The Scree Test For The Number Of Factors', *Multivar. Behav. Res.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 245–276, Apr. 1966, doi: 10.1207/s15327906mbr0102_10.
- [107] J. L. Horn, 'A rationale and test for the number of factors in factor analysis', *Psychometrika*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 179–185, Jun. 1965, doi: 10.1007/BF02289447.
- [108] L. W. Glorfeld, 'An Improvement on Horn's Parallel Analysis Methodology for Selecting the Correct Number of Factors to Retain', *Educ. Psychol. Meas.*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 377–393, Jun. 1995, doi: 10.1177/0013164495055003002.
- [109] H. Abdi and L. J. Williams, 'Principal component analysis', *WIREs Comput Stat*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 433–459, Jul. 2010, doi: 10.1002/wics.101.
- [110] L. Breiman, J. Friedman, R. A. Olshen, and C. J. Stone, *Classification and Regression Trees*. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC, 2017. doi: 10.1201/9781315139470.
- [111] L. Breiman, 'Random Forests', *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, Oct. 2001, doi: 10.1023/A:1010933404324.
- [112] J. H. Friedman, 'Greedy function approximation: A gradient boosting machine.', *Ann. Stat.*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 1189–1232, Oct. 2001, doi: 10.1214/aos/1013203451.

- [113] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, ‘XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System’, in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, in KDD ’16. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Aug. 2016, pp. 785–794. doi: 10.1145/2939672.2939785.
- [114] A. Akman and B. W. Schuller, ‘Audio Explainable Artificial Intelligence: A Review’, *Intell. Comput.*, vol. 3, p. 0074, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.34133/icomputing.0074.
- [115] A. Premkumar, P. T. Rajendran, and V. V. Menon, ‘Learning Quality from Complexity and Structure: A Feature-Fused XGBoost Model for Video Quality Assessment’, Jun. 11, 2025, *arXiv*: arXiv:2506.09795. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2506.09795.
- [116] V. Lyberatos, S. Kantarelis, E. Dervakos, and G. Stamou, ‘Perceptual Musical Features for Interpretable Audio Tagging’, in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing Workshops (ICASSPW)*, Apr. 2024, pp. 878–882. doi: 10.1109/ICASSPW62465.2024.10669903.
- [117] C. Strobl, A.-L. Boulesteix, A. Zeileis, and T. Hothorn, ‘Bias in random forest variable importance measures: illustrations, sources and a solution’, *BMC Bioinformatics*, vol. 8, p. 25, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.1186/1471-2105-8-25.
- [118] A. Altmann, L. Toloşi, O. Sander, and T. Lengauer, ‘Permutation importance: a corrected feature importance measure’, *Bioinformatics*, vol. 26, no. 10, pp. 1340–1347, May 2010, doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btq134.

- [119] L. S. Shapley, 'Notes on the N-Person Game — II: The Value of an N-Person Game', Aug. 1951, Accessed: Jan. 19, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/4837582/notes-on-the-n-person-game-ii/5674259/>
- [120] S. M. Lundberg *et al.*, 'From local explanations to global understanding with explainable AI for trees', *Nat. Mach. Intell.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 56–67, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s42256-019-0138-9.
- [121] C. Molnar, *Interpretable Machine Learning*. Lulu.com, 2020.
- [122] M. G. Kendall and B. B. Smith, 'The Problem of S_m Rankings', *Ann. Math. Stat.*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 275–287, Sep. 1939, doi: 10.1214/aoms/1177732186.
- [123] C. Spearman, 'The Proof and Measurement of Association between Two Things', *Am. J. Psychol.*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 72–101, 1904, doi: 10.2307/1412159.
- [124] B. Efron and R. J. Tibshirani, *An Introduction to the Bootstrap*. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC, 1994. doi: 10.1201/9780429246593.
- [125] W. H. Kruskal and W. A. Wallis, 'Use of Ranks in One-Criterion Variance Analysis', *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.*, vol. 47, no. 260, pp. 583–621, 1952, doi: 10.2307/2280779.
- [126] M. Tomczak and E. Tomczak-Łukaszewska, 'The need to report effect size estimates revisited. An overview of some recommended measures of effect size', vol. 21, pp. 19–25, Jan. 2014.

- [127] M. Kulesza, ‘DSP techniques for determining “wow” distortion’, *J. Audio ...*, Jan. 2007, Accessed: Dec. 02, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/71859958/DSP_techniques_for_determining_wow_distortion
- [128] M. Brandt and J. Bitzer, ‘Detection of Hum in Audio Signals’, 2010. Accessed: Dec. 02, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Detection-of-Hum-in-Audio-Signals-Brandt-Bitzer/c4b5cdc55198abe15074b78f8f30c89f326a1a08>
- [129] G. Ballou, *Handbook for Sound Engineers*. Taylor & Francis, 2008.
- [130] J. Coughlan-Allen, ‘Unknown Pleasure: interpretations of the mystery hiss in Feist’s 2017 album’, *Pop. Music*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 310–327, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1017/S0261143023000521.
- [131] M. C. Killion, ‘Noise of ears and microphones’, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 424–433, Feb. 1976, doi: 10.1121/1.380886.
- [132] T. Gerkmann, ‘Synthesis of Perceptually Plausible Multichannel Noise Signals Controlled by Real World Statistical Noise Properties’, *J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, Jan. 2017, Accessed: Dec. 02, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/80902862/Synthesis_of_Perceptually_Plausible_Multichannel_Noise_Signals_Controlled_by_Real_World_Statistical_Noise_Properties

- [133] ‘Real-time audio programming 101: time waits for nothing’. Accessed: Dec. 02, 2024.
[Online]. Available: <http://www.rossbencina.com/code/real-time-audio-programming-101-time-waits-for-nothing>
- [134] J. T. Claussen, ‘Welcome to the glitch and make some noise: Understanding media through audio hacking’, *J. Music Technol. Educ.*, vol. 15, no. Exploring Audio and Music Technology in Education: Pedagogical, Research and Sociocultural Perspectives, pp. 7–26, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1386/jmte_00043_1.
- [135] M. Cartwright and B. Pardo, ‘SOCIAL-EQ: CROWDSOURCING AN EQUALIZATION DESCRIPTOR MAP’.
- [136] W. A. Sethares, ‘Local consonance and the relationship between timbre and scale’, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 94, no. 3, p. 1218, Aug. 1998, doi: 10.1121/1.408175.
- [137] P. Daniel, ‘Psychoacoustical Roughness’, in *Handbook of Signal Processing in Acoustics*, D. Havelock, S. Kuwano, and M. Vorländer, Eds, New York, NY: Springer New York, 2008, pp. 263–274. doi: 10.1007/978-0-387-30441-0_19.
- [138] M. Hoffman and P. Cook, ‘Real-Time Dissonancizers: Two Dissonance-Augmenting Audio Effects’, p. 4, 2008.
- [139] D. Williams, ‘Tracking timbral changes in metal productions from 1990 to 2013’, doi: 10.1386/MMS.1.1.39_1.

- [140] D. Giannoulis, M. Massberg, and J. Reiss, ‘Digital Dynamic Range Compressor Design—A Tutorial and Analysis’, *AES J. Audio Eng. Soc.*, vol. 60, Jul. 2012.
- [141] M. Holters and U. Zölzer, ‘GstPEAQ – An Open Source Implementation of the PEAQ Algorithm’, Dec. 2015.
- [142] ‘The Cadenza Project’. Accessed: Dec. 02, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://cadenzaproject.github.io/>
- [143] ‘EBU R 128’, *Wikipedia*. Jan. 05, 2026. Accessed: Jan. 23, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=EBU_R_128&oldid=1331293331
- [144] ‘LAME MP3 Encoder’. Accessed: Dec. 03, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://lame.sourceforge.io/>
- [145] M. Weger, T. Hermann, and R. Höldrich, ‘Real-time auditory contrast enhancement’, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.21785/icad2019.026.
- [146] M. Schoeffler *et al.*, ‘webMUSHRA — A Comprehensive Framework for Web-based Listening Tests’, *J. Open Res. Softw.*, vol. 6, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.5334/jors.187.
- [147] Z. Rafii, A. Liutkus, F.-R. Stöter, S. I. Mimitakis, and R. Bittner, ‘MUSDB18-HQ - an uncompressed version of MUSDB18’. Zenodo, Aug. 01, 2019. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3338373.
- [148] K. Grivcova, C. Pike, and T. Nixon, ‘A Subjective Evaluation of High Bitrate Coding of Music’, presented at the Audio Engineering Society Convention 144, Audio

- Engineering Society, May 2018. Accessed: Sep. 16, 2022. [Online]. Available:
<http://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=19397>
- [149] B. McFee *et al.*, *librosa/librosa: 0.11.0*. (Mar. 11, 2025). Zenodo. doi:
10.5281/zenodo.15006942.
- [150] I. Jordal *et al.*, *iver56/audiomentations: v0.43.1*. (Sep. 13, 2025). Zenodo. doi:
10.5281/zenodo.17112730.
- [151] *numpy/numpy*. (Jan. 25, 2026). Python. NumPy. Accessed: Jan. 25, 2026. [Online].
Available: <https://github.com/numpy/numpy>
- [152] A. F. Gad, ‘PyGAD: An Intuitive Genetic Algorithm Python Library’, Jun. 11, 2021,
arXiv: arXiv:2106.06158. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2106.06158.
- [153] Sergio Guadarrama and Anoop Korattikara and Oscar Ramirez and, Pablo Castro and
Ethan Holly and Sam Fishman and Ke Wang and, Ekaterina Gonina and Neal Wu and
Efi Kokiopoulou and Luciano Sbaiz and, Jamie Smith and Gábor Bartók and Jesse
Berent and Chris Harris and, and Vincent Vanhoucke and Eugene Brevdo, *{TF-
Agents}*: *A library for Reinforcement Learning in TensorFlow*. (Jan. 23, 2026).
Python. tensorflow. Accessed: Jan. 25, 2026. [Online]. Available:
<https://github.com/tensorflow/agents>
- [154] M. Storsjö, *mstorsjo/fdk-aac*. (Jan. 16, 2026). C++. Accessed: Jan. 21, 2026. [Online].
Available: <https://github.com/mstorsjo/fdk-aac>

[155] *facebookresearch/encodec*. (Jan. 18, 2026). Python. Meta Research. Accessed: Jan. 21, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/facebookresearch/encodec>

